

**PILOTs for robotic INspection and maintenance
Grounded on advanced intelligent platforms and
prototype applications**

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- Results and Evaluation -**

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Acronyms

Abbreviation	Explanation
AESA	Agencia Estatal de Seguridad Aérea (Spanish for “State Agency for Aviation Safety”)
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
ARO	Airport Reservation Office
A-SCAN	An Ultrasound Scan
ASME	American Society of Mechanical Engineers
ATEX	ATmosphères EXplosives (French for "Explosive Atmospheres") - Common name for Directive 2014/34/EU
BVLOS	Beyond Visual Line Of Sight
CAD	Computer Aided Design
CNOA	Centre Nationale Opérationnel Aérien (French for “National Air Operations Centre”)
CTR	Controlled Traffic Region
DDHL	Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer
DMS	Data Management System
DSAC	Direction de la Sécurité de l’Aviation Civile (French for “Directorate of Civil Aviation Safety”)
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
gRCS	general Robot Control Station
HD	High Definition
HQ	High Quality
HMI	Human Machine Interface
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance

IA	Innovation Action
ICT	Information Communication Technologies
IL	Inspection Location
IMU	Inertial Measurements Unit
IoT	Internet of Things
IoU	Intersection over Union
IR	Infrared
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
IVP	Intelligence and Visualization Portal
JSA	Job Site Analysis
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEL	Lower Explosion Limit
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
mRCS	mission-specific Robot Control Station
MTOW	Maximum Take-Off Weight
NDT	Non-Destructive Testing
NE	North East
NW	North West
OSS	Optical Steady Shot
P&ID	Piping & Instrumentation Diagram
POI	Point of Interest
PPE	Person Protective Equipment
PTZ	Pan-Tilt-Zoom
PV	Pressure Vessel

REST	Representational State Transfer
RGB	Red, Green, Blue
RMCP	Robotic Mobile Contact Platform
SDK	Software Development Kit
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
SSO	Single Sign On
SW	Software
TEB	Timed-Elastic-Bands
UAS	Unmanned Aircraft System
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UGV	Unmanned Ground Vehicle
UT	Ultrasonic Testing
UTM	Unmanned Traffic Management
UUID	Universal Unique Identifier
VLOS	Visual Line Of Sight
VT	Visual Testing
WP	Work Package
WSN	Wireless Sensor Network

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the document

Following the integration of the PILOTING I&M platform and services with each of the robotic solutions in early 2022, this document serves to report the results of the first round of experiments with the integrated PILOTING system in each of the pilot scenarios (refinery, viaduct and tunnel). See Table 1 for a list of all the executed pilot experiments.

Table 1. Pilot experiments performed during the first PILOTING validation phase.

Pilot Demonstrations	Use Cases	Responsible partner-Assigned robot(s)
Refinery pilot case Pilot demonstration (1 st phase) 12-14/9/2022	Tank Large Structure Inspection	CATEC (AEROX)
	Tank Local Visual Inspection	CATEC (AEROCAM)
	Pipe Inspection	CATEC/WTR (HYBRID)
	Pressure Vessel Inspection	WTR (BIKE)
	Ground Monitoring	ROBOTNIK (RISING) & ETHZ (UGV)
Viaduct pilot case Pilot demonstration (1 st phase) 18-22/7/2022 ¹	Visual Inspection	CATEC (AEROCAM)
	Installation of survey targets, bearing inspections and sensor installations	USE (VIAD-DRONE)
Tunnel pilot case Pilot demonstration (1 st phase) 30/9-8/10/2022	General Inspection	ROBOTNIK (CART)
	Local Inspection	ROBOTNIK (CART) & USE (TT-DRONE)

Moreover, this document analyses the fulfilment of the Key Performance indicators, or KPI's, defined in deliverable D3.2, and also the verification during the pilot experiments of the original project requirements per use case.

Finally, the document also identifies best practices, as well as opportunities for improvement to take forward and develop for the final round of experiments in late 2023.

¹ Plus two more weeks of technological pilot experiments that were performed during June and July 2022.

1.2. Scope of the document

This document contains the results of the work performed in WP8 during the first development and experimental cycle of the project. As it was considered in the project planning, PILOTING considers two development and experimental cycles in order to be able to gain experience in the first cycle, and apply the identified improvements and lessons learnt in the second one. Then, this document describes the project results from the first experimental cycle for the three considered pilot scenarios.

1.3. Structure of the document

First, the document starts with Section 2. where it is explained how the use can start an inspection mission for each of the different use cases and robotic platforms in the three different pilot scenarios. Also, this Section explains the final integration of the PILOTING I&M platform with the robotics vehicles. Then, the document is organized to report out the site experiment results from Refineries (Section 3.), Viaducts (Section 4.) and Tunnels (Section 5.). Section 6. provides a summary of the analysis of the KPI's originally defined in deliverable D3.2, while the traceability matrices with the original project requirements are shown in Annex I: Requirements Validation.

Finally, Section 7. provides a summary of best practices and lessons learned derived from the site testing followed by the conclusions (Section 8.).

2. Planning of pilot experiments using the PILOTING I&M platform and services

2.1. Definition of the inspection plan using the IVP

The Intelligence and Visualization Portal (IVP, see deliverable D6.4) serves as a prime high-level entry-point for creating digital representations of the physical assets to be inspected, managing the inspection plans to be executed during robotic deployments, and contextualizing the data collected after a mission for expert analysis and reporting purposes. The exact workflow, system integration, and communications between the components of the PILOTING I&M ecosystem are detailed in deliverable D.7.2. The main points are summarized in this section for self-consistency and clarity for the reader.

The first version of the IVP was successfully deployed online and integrated with the PILOTING I&M platform and services to allow proper end-to-end execution of the pilot experiments. Authorized users can securely access the IVP at <https://portal.piloting-project.eu/>. This allowed the partners to have enough time to define an inspection plan from the web portal and verify their system integrity with the gRCS, before even going to the field trials.

3D models are central to digital inspection workflow in PILOTING, making it more intuitive to share information about the dimensions and geometry of the asset, indicate the inspection locations, or also acting as reference model for the robotic navigation and present the inspection results. For certain classes of assets (Pressure Vessel, Pipes, Above Ground Storage Tank), the IVP offers a dedicated modelling tool to easily build parametrized 3D mesh models. For the other use cases, 3D point-cloud models were generated during a preliminary mission by using laser scanners.

Figure 1. Visualization of 3D asset models created from the IVP modeling tool (left) or generated during a preliminary mission (right).

After creating a digital representation of an asset, users can begin to define an inspection plan. An inspection plan conveys, through the DDHL, all the high-level information that gRCS needs in order to plan and execute a robotic field deployment. This includes files and data describing the inspection locations of interest (e.g.: points, areas drawn from the asset model), the inspection tasks to be performed and instructions on how to perform them (e.g.: Visual, UT, Cleaning), as well as details of the robotic system and its payloads.

Several inspection plans can be created, depending on the mission scope. In addition, an inspection plan can be repeated multiple times. This allows to split the mission tasks to complete them (e.g.: a drone needs to fly several times), but also to enable spatial and temporal analytics between the dataset collected.

Figure 2. Visualization of different inspection plans created from the IVP (the blue arrows indicate the order of the inspection locations).

For each of the defined use cases and validation scenarios, this digital inspection planning workflow, implemented for PILOTING, were proven to be working effectively, as evidenced by the successful integration and completion of the pilot trials that will be described in Sections 3. , 4. and 5. .

2.2. User access and Mission Specific Data Management through PILOTING I&M Platform

Once the inspection plans are defined using the IVP, the Mission specific data has to be stored and managed by the Data Management System (DMS), and then later transmitted to the general Robot Control Station (gRCS), through the Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer (DDHL), where the detailed inspection mission will be defined (see deliverable D7.2 for more details)

Then, we will attempt to showcase the outcomes of the functionalities briefly described thereafter, with which during the pre-mission phase the authorised/authenticated users (**Authorisation Module**) define the inspection plans and tasks, and the accompanying properties (e.g. asset, inspection location, assigned robotic system), which afterwards are stored in the DMS and are ready for the mission execution phase (**Pre-mission's and During-mission's files and the file management**), harmonised (**Data Harmonisation**) and distributed to gRCS in order to perform the missions (**Definition of the detailed planning**). Concluding, with the successful execution of the mission specific tasks, the corresponding data that were collected will be seen in the associated FileMetadata entity (**Post-mission phase**).

- **Authorisation Module** functionality of the DMS, where the user can have access in IVP, and therefore are able to upload the asset map, define the inspection locations, and the plan, and upload all the necessary files, through which the robotic missions will be executed (**pre-mission phase**).
- **Pre-, During-, Post-mission and file management**, which will be able to handle all the necessary files for the efficient formulation of the inspection plans, tasks and missions, and therefore to store the collected data (**pre-, during- & post-mission phases**)
- **Data Harmonisation** before and after the execution of the tasks (**pre-mission & during-mission phases**)

- **Definition of the detailed planning** for the execution of the mission plans/tasks through the gRCS (**during-mission phase**)

2.2.1. *Authorisation Module: User access Data Management System*

As it was indicated before, the first step in order to access the IVP and create the inspection plan and all the related files are the creation of a user's account. For this process, DMS has initiated the Keycloak-based authentication/authorisation module that is deployed under the OAuth2.0 protocol, comprising the two logical modules of the Identity Provider and the User Management, which are responsible to create secured user identities and managing user's capabilities with certain deployed roles (for further details see D3.2 and D6.3). For the needs of the PILOTING project, 24 unique users were created for almost every partner within the consortium (creation of one or more users), with the exception of this step to be only the pilot partners, who will explore the whole PILOTING solution during the second and final phase of the project. Table 2 showcases that the integration activities started to occur within the early stages of the project with the first users to be the partners directly associated with the DDHL (INLECOM) and IVP (QUASSET), who, in fact, are directly connected components. The rest of the users related to the RCS and the robotic systems started to interact with the DMS, within and after the integration phases, in order to exchange and store the produced data. In this case, it is worth to be mentioned that user access through the Keycloak module had to be provided to all users who explore the IVP and the generation of the inspection plan and the ones who explore the DMS API in order to publish or consume the generated data.

For the needs of the pilot demonstrations, nine different scenarios were planned to be tested with nine different robotic systems to be used for the missions' executions, which are deployed by the corresponding partners that are presented in Table 1. As we can see, the majority of the partners were requested for an account generation, in order to have access to the created data and files that are associated with the inspection plan/mission. At a later stage, and with a will to demonstrate the whole scenario with the contribution of the pilot partners (mainly during the pre-mission phase and the definition of the inspection procedure) additional authorized accounts will be created for the three pilot partners (i.e., Chevron, Ferrovia and Egnatia).

Table 2. Generated users during PILOTING experiments.

Users' Encrypted ID	Partner	Datetime of user generation
b3998e4d-f040-43e3-a929-ccc8ec790bb2	INLECOM	11/29/21 1:18:49 PM
131a1787-5fca-409e-9111-8bc7ee86e6c4	QUASSET	12/03/21 16:35:11 PM
c17c238e-b496-4f9b-9c01-dc1752ae456e	CATEC	4/27/22 11:26:10 AM
09db6b5a-dd0d-4585-8cbc-b3cbf4ce7eab	INLECOM	4/27/22 11:27:15 AM
7ee38649-6e38-4b75-8c93-83f16671189e	ETHZ	4/27/22 11:29:28 AM
f7299efa-34fc-4cd1-a6e6-306d61b9615b	GEIR	4/27/22 11:32:40 AM
f8b3d06e-ebc1-4d26-b5ba-29757d2e6a3f	GEIR	4/27/22 11:39:59 AM
acc86168-59ff-4ccf-8d63-289078d7df90	GEIR	4/27/22 11:40:48 AM

bff8f91f-eef5-46aa-9d05-f3d4d04dcbc0	GEIR	4/27/22 11:42:00 AM
1996b2e9-0580-4edc-93c2-a25c380f035e	INLECOM	4/27/22 11:28:10 AM
46d9a30a-0b5b-4fdd-b440-64fa52b244fb	ETHZ	4/27/22 11:30:43 AM
5f112ced-c780-490c-803f-f17967cf9770	USE	4/27/22 12:10:02 PM
af24401f-36df-48dd-a3e2-19ff4f86404e	ICCS	5/3/22 4:49:28 PM
0c5cb219-55d8-412d-bb43-d96584d49dbc	CATEC	5/3/22 09:47:28 AM
1d1246c7-be9d-44de-93ba-a49afd040f26	ICCS	5/4/22 3:15:53 PM
d488e26b-7a73-4140-a456-a83fd23bf1c5	ROBOTNIK	5/6/2022 12:05:31 PM
8caeff16-cfd1-4ae0-9348-4533731df59b	ROBOTNIK	5/9/22 10:24:45 AM
26538e52-3040-4e5d-9b53-41808c4fc56f	CATEC	5/11/22 12:41:24 PM
fbcb75661-d06c-4053-9627-0d7348b60db0	CATEC	7/29/22 12:33:40 PM
0382897b-afb8-4aaa-81ab-2e4f63d2808b	QUASSET	9/21/22 1:27:44 PM
1043ef3c-fdf6-4955-852d-264261903b47	ICCS	10/24/22 12:20:13 PM
ba75bf73-877c-4d02-99dc-ed1291ac6f87	QUASSET	10/4/22 16:03:56 PM

A simple email invitation was generated upon user request and delivered to the users (Figure 3). After the successful creation of the user account, the user was able to have access to both IVP and DMS API, with the first case to be feasible through the DMS Keycloak server, (Figure 4), and the second through Postman (see D6.3 for further details).

Figure 3. User registration with the email invitation.

Figure 4. Login page to the IVP, powered by the DMS Keycloak server.

2.2.2. Pre-, During-, & Post-Mission and File Data Management by the DMS

Continuing, we showcase the outcomes of the phases’ execution workflow, as it was thoroughly described in D7.2, presenting the benefits of the integration of the I&M PILOTING platform components during the pilot cases and the successful indexing and storage of collected data. As a common workflow it is supposed to be followed at every validation scenario, which is independent of the inspection location, the type of robotic system and payload and the data generation, we will present one indicative example for each general pilot case (i.e., refinery, viaduct, and tunnel). However, in the table that follows we present the overall results regarding the number of inspection plans, tasks, missions the used payloads and the finally created data that were collected during pilots and stored in the DMS backend.

Table 3. The whole generated inspection plans, missions, and the collected data during pilot demonstrations.

	Pre-mission phase				During-mission phase		Post-mission phase
	Assets	Inspection Plan	Robotic Systems	Payload	Missions	Mission Tasks	File Metadata
Refinery	5	6	3	9	4	4	8
Viaduct	2	3	2	4	8	22	19
Tunnel	7	6	2	1	4	19	13
TOTAL	14	15	7	14	16	45	40

a. Example for the Refinery validation scenario

Taking as an example the refinery pilot scenario, and as it is depicted in Section 3. of this current document, three inspection locations were defined to be executed by different robotic systems, with one of them being the inspections alongside the large structure tank. For this specific asset, two inspection plans were executed and associated with the two ultrasonic thickness (UT) readings that were performed by the AEROX in dedicated positions (see AEROX’s trajectory over tank 504). The whole information that was created for this inspection plan is presented in Figure 5 and explained hereafter.

Figure 5. Example of the inspection validation scenario on the Large Structure Tank 504 that was implemented by the AEROX robotic system.

So, trying to translate the aforementioned validation plan in the information that is stored in the DMS, (Figure 5), we can see that at first during the pre-mission phase one asset was created, namely “Tank 504”, which is associated with two inspection locations (“*Inspection Area 1 and 2*”), denoted with a specific bounding box. The JSON objects below present the generated properties for these inspection locations.

Table 4. Inspection locations' properties. As it is depicted both of them are associated with the same Asset “Tank 504”, which have the UUID: 4de652d4-e009-41d6-b684-c9e71dace312.

Inspection Location 1	Inspection Location 2
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "5560ecd9-bdea-4c1b-a823-9ccfc8875f16", "Name": "InspectionArea 1", "Subtype": "Annotation 3D", "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-12T16:57:54.304706Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-12T16:57:54.304847Z", "Properties": {...}, "depth": 0.49324868640027386, "width": 0.683481833010157, "height": 6.226184096492827, }</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "4c2bf14d-610f-4044-8578-af3ec2464d77", "Name": "InspectionArea 2", "Subtype": "Annotation 3D", "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-14T06:55:18.143605Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-14T06:55:18.143717Z", "Properties": {...}, "depth": 1.0413197087685349, "width": 0.5484647541123774, "height": 1.9737139367879013, }</pre>

<pre> "assetId": "4de652d4-e009-41d6-b684-c9e71dace312", "subtype": "Annotation 3D", "objectType": "InspectionArea" } </pre>	<pre> "assetId": "4de652d4-e009-41d6-b684-c9e71dace312", "subtype": "Annotation 3D", "objectType": "InspectionArea" } </pre>
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For these locations, two inspection plans were created, which afterwards were translated through the RCS into specific missions. The following table depicts the association of the inspection plans and missions, for this specific asset.

Table 5. Definition of the inspection plans for the inspection locations, and associated missions that will be executed from the robotics.

Inspection Plan 1	Inspection Plan 2
<pre> { "UniqueID": "0bb40ec4-1cfa-4f77-9d4e-9cac49b68969", "Name": "Inspection plan Tank 504 Single Line", "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-12T16:59:19.434596Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-12T16:59:19.434702Z", "Description": "Inspection plan of a single line in tank 504 from Chevron Oronite", "Properties": { "site": "Refinery Chevron Oronite", "toDate": "2022-09-16T16:58:31.517Z", "assetId": "4de652d4-e009-41d6-b684-c9e71dace312", "fromDate": "2022-09-13T16:58:23.244Z" } } </pre>	<pre> { "UniqueID": "4772407c-b37e-442d-a9a8-266cf6026620", "Name": "Inspection plan Tank 504 Rectangle", "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-14T06:44:05.360422Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-14T06:44:05.360540Z", "Description": "Inspection covering a rectangle area over the tank's surface near the manholes", "Properties": { "site": "Refinery Chevron Oronite", "assetId": "4de652d4-e009-41d6-b684-c9e71dace312", "fromDate": "2022-09-14T06:42:02.132Z" } } </pre>
Associated mission	Associated mission
<pre> { "UniqueID": "007b86e7-8350-432b-94ee-d8146f4743d3", "Name": "mission_20220913100420", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-09-13T11:10:27Z", "Description": null, "Properties": { "SyncId": 1799026144, "Completed": true }, "InspectionPlan": "0bb40ec4-1cfa-4f77-9d4e-9cac49b68969" } </pre>	<pre> { "UniqueID": "15170bf0-2709-4f4f-ae7e-e911956047e9", "Name": "mission_20220914094920", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-09-14T10:09:04Z", "Description": null, "Properties": { "SyncId": 144523716, "Completed": true }, "InspectionPlan": "4772407c-b37e-442d-a9a8-266cf6026620" } </pre>

For each inspection, one or more inspection tasks could be defined at a specific location on the asset. The need for execution of the inspection plans alongside Tank 504 and two subsequent inspection tasks was defined, one for each of the two inspection locations. As it can be observed, there is a complete association between the inspection tasks and the location and task that they had to be

associated with. As the inspection task/missions were performed with the same robotic system and the same payload, a unique UUID should have existed in both tasks, a fact that can be seen in the extracted JSON objects that are presented below.

Table 6. Definition of the inspection tasks, and the association with the inspection plans, location, robotic systems and payloads.

Inspection Task 1	Inspection Task 2
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "67026cae-33ef-40a1-b424-3911eae9b21", "Name": "Ultrasonic Inspection 1", "Description": null, "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-12T16:59:56.815667Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-12T16:59:56.815740Z", "Properties": { "index": 0, "inspectionType": { "id": "83339fce-38dd-4af8-83f3-4c310194e459", "name": "Ultrasonic Inspection" }, "inspectionOrder": ["BA78BE10-54B7-47F6-BC72-63A144F70E3E", 1], "inspectionPlanId": "0bb40ec4-1cfa-4f77-9d4e-9cac49b68969", "roboticSystemIds": ["64517634-27b2-42e1-b036-6b5909661f71"], "sensorPayloadIds": ["b6b056fb-bf77-41f5-a374-2e42e7fb6495"], "inspectionTaskOrder": 0, "inspectionLocationId": "5560ecd9-bdea-4c1b-a823-9ccfc8875f16", "inspectionLocationOrder": 0 } }</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "6216e7cc-3a43-454c-a82f-51d4ec61f139", "Name": "Ultrasonic Inspection 1", "Description": null, "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-14T07:30:49.850055Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-14T07:30:49.850102Z", "Properties": { "index": 0, "inspectionType": { "id": "83339fce-38dd-4af8-83f3-4c310194e459", "name": "Ultrasonic Inspection" }, "inspectionOrder": ["F2EF0DB6-2216-47CF-9721-B420103C1343", 1], "inspectionPlanId": "4772407c-b37e-442d-a9a8-266cf6026620", "roboticSystemIds": ["64517634-27b2-42e1-b036-6b5909661f71"], "sensorPayloadIds": ["b6b056fb-bf77-41f5-a374-2e42e7fb6495"], "inspectionTaskOrder": 0, "inspectionLocationId": "4c2bf14d-610f-4044-8578-af3ec2464d77", "inspectionLocationOrder": 0 } }</pre>
Robotic System	Payload
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "64517634-27b2-42e1-b036-6b5909661f71", "Name": "AEROX", "Description": "Aerial robot for the inspection of large structures in refineries", "CreationDatetime": "2021-11-29T13:44:22.232481Z", }</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "b6b056fb-bf77-41f5-a374-2e42e7fb6495", "Description": "AEROX - Ultrasonic sensor", "Specifications": null, "SerialNumber": null, "Type": "Ultrasonic sensor", }</pre>

<pre>"UpdateDatetime": "2021-11-29T13:44:22.232521Z", "Properties": { "General": "Performs ultrasonic contact inspection autonomously" }, "Payload": ["b6b056fb-bf77-41f5-a374-2e42e7fb6495"] }</pre>	<pre>"CreationDatetime": "2021-11-29T13:43:23.182176Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2021-11-29T13:43:23.182209Z", "Properties": { } }</pre>
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Continuing, within the RCS, the during-mission phase is taken place with the mission and specific mission tasks were generated and initiated. The DMS was responsible to forward to the DDHL and afterwards to gRCS/mRCS the data related to the relevant Inspection Tasks, Inspection Types, Inspection Locations, Asset, and other metadata or files, associated with any of these entities. Having collected all the aforementioned, the gRCS/mRCS is able to create the detailed mission and mission tasks taking into consideration the specificities of the operational area. As a result, Ultrasonic thickness measurements (UTM) were generated and stored in the FileMetadata of the corresponding mission tasks, (Table 7).

Table 7. The generated mission tasks for each mission and the file metadata, containing the collected observations.

Mission Task 1	Mission Task 2
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "0a5e3aed-44c7-4460-b09e-1e5f8c1a4bcc", "Name": "mission_task_0", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-09-13T11:10:29.186000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "67026cae-33ef-40a1-b424-3911eae9b21", "InspectionType": "83339fce-38dd-4af8-83f3-4c310194e459", "Mission": "007b86e7-8350-432b-94ee-d8146f4743d3" }</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "50c38069-7222-44a8-99ef-bda4603f32da", "Name": "mission_task_0", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-09-14T13:08:16.832000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "6216e7cc-3a43-454c-a82f-51d4ec61f139", "InspectionType": "83339fce-38dd-4af8-83f3-4c310194e459", "Mission": "15170bf0-2709-4f4f-ae7e-e911956047e9" }</pre>
Generated FileMetadata	Generated FileMetadata
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "0a5e3aed-44c7-4460-b09e-1e5f8c1a4bcc", "Files": [{ "UniqueID": "c5afb0f0-dc63-4eaa-beee-b1e1abf50d1c", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/7208e1ec-6bd5-484c-a687-857dccc461c6/", "MimeType": "text/tsv", "Size": "445", "OriginalName": "scan_67026cae-33ef-40a1-b424-3911eae9b21.tsv", "Content": "mRCS - UT_thickness", "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-19T11:12:51.004725Z", }] }</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "50c38069-7222-44a8-99ef-bda4603f32da", "Files": [{ "UniqueID": "a3ed38d9-569e-4d17-948b-0c138a9ad8aa", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/a1abcd78-d9bf-498c-b97d-65efda9a6af2/", "MimeType": "text/tsv", "Size": "1352", "OriginalName": "scan_6216e7cc-3a43-454c-a82f-51d4ec61f139.tsv", "Content": "mRCS - UT_thickness", "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-19T12:08:57.608630Z", }] }</pre>

<pre> "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-19T11:12:51.004854Z", "Properties": { "UTMeasurement": { "p_x": -0.424489, "p_y": 13.056, "p_z": 1.82942, "q_w": null, "q_x": null, "q_y": null, "q_z": null, "p_x_final": -0.435209, "p_y_final": 13.0653, "p_z_final": 8.36052, "timestamp": "2022-09-13T11:10:31Z", "left_vector_x": null, "left_vector_y": null, "left_vector_z": null, "forward_vector_x": null, "forward_vector_y": null, "forward_vector_z": null, "euler_angle_z_phi": null, "euler_angle_z_psi": null, "euler_angle_x_theta": null } } }, { "UniqueID": "790724ed-2331-48d3-b0c7-099f4295286d", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/b43a5601-c187-485a-aff5-0517efd6b295/", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "228", "OriginalName": "UT_measurements_0a5e3aed.csv", "Content": "mRCS - UT_measurements", "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-19T11:12:51.554067Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-19T11:12:51.554190Z", "Properties": null }], { "Name": "mission_task_0", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-09-13T11:10:29.186000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "67026cae-33ef-40a1-b424-3911eaec9b21", "InspectionType": "83339fce-38dd-4af8-83f3-4c310194e459", "Mission": "007b86e7-8350-432b-94ee-d8146f4743d3" } </pre>	<pre> "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-19T12:08:57.608703Z", "Properties": { "UTMeasurement": { "p_x": -0.674833, "p_y": 13.1893, "p_z": 3.15213, "q_w": null, "q_x": null, "q_y": null, "q_z": null, "p_x_final": 0.0210512, "p_y_final": 12.8571, "p_z_final": 5.23224, "timestamp": "2022-09-14T10:09:08Z", "left_vector_x": null, "left_vector_y": null, "left_vector_z": null, "forward_vector_x": null, "forward_vector_y": null, "forward_vector_z": null, "euler_angle_z_phi": null, "euler_angle_z_psi": null, "euler_angle_x_theta": null } } }, { "UniqueID": "fc182d1a-b8ee-4ef7-a733-9f93de4953f9", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/9fb0cbd8-331a-4802-be73-cd03c1ceea8e/", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "229", "OriginalName": "UT_measurements_50c38069.csv", "Content": "mRCS - UT_measurements", "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-19T12:08:58.202230Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-19T12:08:58.202268Z", "Properties": null }], { "Name": "mission_task_0", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-09-14T13:08:16.832000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "6216e7cc-3a43-454c-a82f-51d4ec61f139", "InspectionType": "83339fce-38dd-4af8-83f3-4c310194e459", "Mission": "15170bf0-2709-4f4f-ae7e-e911956047e9" } </pre>
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b. Example for the Viaduct validation scenario

A similar rationale will be followed for the description of the viaduct scenario, which as it is depicted in Section 4. of this current document, two assets existed in Alora, where the Arroyo del Espinazo Viaduct exists, with the first to be used for the IoT sensors’ installation (namely “USE_ALORA”) and the other for the two-validation scenario (namely “Alora_demo”). For analysis purposes, we will exploit the second case, where three additional inspection locations were created with the first to be related to the general inspection and the two subsequent to the local inspections in dedicated positions in the 2 pillars. The whole information that was created for this inspection plan is presented in Figure 6 and explained hereafter.

Figure 6. Example of the inspection validation scenario on the Alora demo that was implemented by the AEROX robotic system.

So, trying to translate the aforementioned validation plan in the information that is stored in the DMS, (Table 8), we can see that for each pillar a dedicated inspection plan was generated for the Alora demo asset parent, where three dedicated inspection location areas were defined with a bounding box. JSON objects below present the generated properties for this inspection location.

Table 8. Inspection locations' properties. As it is depicted both of them are associated with the same Asset “Alora_demo”, which have the UUID: a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9.

Inspection Location 1	Inspection Location 2	Inspection Location 3
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "3d1b2361-2d10-4f92-9410-53d1f60dbcdd", "Name": "Beam", "Subtype": "Annotation 3D", "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:42:19.086178Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:42:19.086257Z", "Properties": { "posX": 14.588786671029712, "posY": -9.576507420871636, "posZ": 11.385204140600266, "repr": { "name": "Beam",</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "e8b09ebb-3e9c-4b38-b3af-f493cd44f740", "Name": "Pillar 1", "Subtype": "Annotation 3D", "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:42:19.067989Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:42:19.068069Z", "Properties": { "posX": -5.379675618658553, "posY": 2.7514056508677007, "posZ": 6.790561709029292, "repr": { "name": "Pillar 1", "type": "InspectionArea", "uuid": "5DC94580-0B7C-4D9B-A752-5B4985AA65B7",</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "744b26d8-c6cd-45ba-a23c-fce83e34f360", "Name": "Pillar 2", "Subtype": "Annotation 3D", "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:42:19.067940Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:42:19.068013Z", "Properties": { "posX": 33.713422528302715, "posY": -22.38483696872136, "posZ": 5.337540339631426, "repr": { "name": "Pillar 2", "type": "InspectionArea", "uuid": "EF098A11-902A-4C0A-BB33-1E00FDFAD8C",</pre>

<pre> "type": "InspectionArea", "uuid": "4C3D3576-3D95-40A2-9F2F-EF00251BF1BF", "layer": 10, "matrix": [289.16662161687464, 183.19388134978274, -1.398569969983826, 0, 15.731278816363723, 24.83140111189308, 1.2748090375626393e-17, 0, 0.01745898319451281, 0.011060678019958529, 5.058598336800632, 0, 14588.786671029713, -9576.507420871636, 11385.204140600265, 1], "areaBounds": { "depth": 505.86405572816267, "width": 34231.46056178088, "height": 2939.5095073462494, "areaPosition": [14588.786671029713, 11385.204140600263, 9576.507420871638] }, "connectors": [{ "connectorName": "BASE", "rotationAngle": 0 }], "parameters": { "radius": 50, </pre>	<pre> "layer": 10, "matrix": [21.091328007554825, 30.362597722884548, 0, 0, -3.155900009638372, 2.192240692638756, 0, 0, 0, 50.2290457893947, 0, -5379.675618658553, 2751.405650867701, 6790.561709029292, 1], "areaBounds": { "depth": 5022.90457893947, "width": 3696.9331311290725, "height": 384.26064234184497, "areaPosition": [-5379.675618658553, 6790.561709029293, -2751.4056508676995] }, "connectors": [{ "connectorName": "BASE", "rotationAngle": 0 }], "parameters": { "radius": 50, "zoneBboxMaxX": 0, "zoneBboxMaxY": 0, "zoneBboxMaxZ": 0, "zoneBboxMinX": 0, "zoneBboxMinY": 0, "zoneBboxMinZ": 0 }, "renderOrder": 106, "transparent": true }, </pre>	<pre> "layer": 10, "matrix": [2.970801311358649, -2.0165755811300707, 0, 0, 22.150495930196488, 32.631914703537056, 0, 0, 0, 57.880072586586195, 0, 33713.42252830271, -22384.83696872136, 5337.540339631426, 1], "areaBounds": { "depth": 5788.007258658619, "width": 359.0576208073065, "height": 3943.965424762962, "areaPosition": [33713.42252830271, 5337.540339631421, 22384.83696872136] }, "connectors": [{ "connectorName": "BASE", "rotationAngle": 0 }], "parameters": { "radius": 50, "zoneBboxMaxX": 0, "zoneBboxMaxY": 0, "zoneBboxMaxZ": 0, "zoneBboxMinX": 0, "zoneBboxMinY": 0, "zoneBboxMinZ": 0 }, "renderOrder": 106, "transparent": true }, </pre>
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<pre> "zoneBboxMaxX": 0, "zoneBboxMaxY": 0, "zoneBboxMaxZ": 0, "zoneBboxMinX": 0, "zoneBboxMinY": 0, "zoneBboxMinZ": 0 }, "renderOrder": 106, "transparent": true }, "depth": 2.9395095073462496, "width": 34.23146056178088, "height": 0.5058640557281627, "assetId": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9", "subtype": "Annotation 3D", "objectType": "InspectionArea", }, "Asset": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9" } </pre>	<pre> "depth": 0.384260642341845, "width": 3.6969331311290725, "height": 5.02290457893947, "assetId": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9", "subtype": "Annotation 3D", "objectType": "InspectionArea", }, "Asset": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9" } </pre>	<pre> "depth": 3.943965424762962, "width": 0.35905762080730647, "height": 5.788007258658619, "assetId": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9", "subtype": "Annotation 3D", "objectType": "InspectionArea", }, "Asset": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9" } </pre>
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Continuing, three inspection plans were created explicitly for the two pillars, which afterwards were translated through the RCS into specific missions. As can be seen, in the viaduct case, more for a specific inspection plan, e.g., dfee2a52-f351-47ea-87ca-e4504d8e9701, three missions were created, but each of the missions contained at least 3 dedicated tasks, with the first to be responsible to create the 3D map, the second LiDAR observations, and the final the collection of images. The following table depicts the association of the inspection plans and missions, for this specific asset.

Table 9. Definition of the inspection plans for the inspection locations, and associated missions that will be executed from the robotics.

Inspection Plan 1	Inspection Plan 2	Inspection plan 3
<pre> { "UniqueID": "2eb9b2a3-0e85-400d-99c7-bbc3847d2139", "Name": "Alora Demo", "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:52:06.804739Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:52:06.804871Z", "Description": null, "Properties": { "site": "Viaduct Arroyo Espinazo", "toDate": "2022-07-26T06:51:57.002Z", "assetId": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9", </pre>	<pre> { "UniqueID": "dfee2a52-f351-47ea-87ca-e4504d8e9701", "Name": "Pillar 1 specific inspection", "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-20T06:40:11.745881Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-20T06:40:11.745972Z", "Description": null, "Properties": { "site": "Viaduct Arroyo Espinazo", "toDate": "2022-07-20T06:40:05.187Z", "assetId": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9", </pre>	<pre> { "UniqueID": "8363a65a-b336-4ef9-807c-3becfd55336e", "Name": "Pillar 2 Inspection", "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-20T08:02:41.866339Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-20T08:02:41.866380Z", "Description": null, "Properties": { "site": "Viaduct Arroyo Espinazo", "toDate": "2022-07-20T08:02:38.296Z", "assetId": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9", </pre>

<pre>"fromDate": "2022-07-20T06:51:53.295Z", }, "Asset": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9" }</pre>	<pre>"fromDate": "2022-07-20T06:40:02.733Z", }, "Asset": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9" }</pre>	<pre>"fromDate": "2022-07-20T08:02:36.270Z", }, "Asset": "a5e9c851-5f96-4e7a-a637-e8b9687ae4a9" }</pre>
<p>Associated mission</p>	<p>Associated mission</p>	<p>Associated mission</p>
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "21f57f67-2f44-47a7-8556-eef3b7be4f23", "Name": "mission_19_07_complete", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-07-19T08:49:03Z", "Description": "Inspected the complete viaduct", "Properties": { "Map": "alora_2021_03_11.pcd", "SyncId": 209650002, "Sensors": [{ "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": -0.36 } }, "Name": "Lidar Ouster OS0-128", "uuid": "a19932ae-847e-477d-934b-33463c3da185", "Description": "Lidar sensor with 90° fov and 128 lasers" }], "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0,</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "9d83bb2a-221f-42e2-bd44-fb4f5439726b", "Name": "mission_20220722082942", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-07-22T06:32:34Z", "Description": null, "Properties": { "Map": "alora_2021_03_11.pcd", "SyncId": 1602700711, "Sensors": [{ "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": -0.36 } }, "Name": "Lidar Ouster OS0-128", "uuid": "a19932ae-847e-477d-934b-33463c3da185", "Description": "Lidar sensor with 90° fov and 128 lasers" }], "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0,</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "5ae0f020-981d-40ca-a54b-f42eb6227f0a", "Name": "mission_especifica_2_", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-07-21T07:50:18Z", "Description": null, "Properties": { "Map": "alora_2021_03_11.pcd", "SyncId": 2017727225, "Sensors": [{ "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": -0.36 } }, "Name": "Lidar Ouster OS0-128", "uuid": "a19932ae-847e-477d-934b-33463c3da185", "Description": "Lidar sensor with 90° fov and 128 lasers" }], "tf": {</pre>

<pre> "y": 0, "z": 0 } }, "Name": "Autopilot DJI A3 Pro", "uuid": "369024b2- f65c-44a3-926d-a8fd1d1c9bef" }, { "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": -0.4 } } }, "Name": "Altimeter Lightware", "uuid": "2b4f4fac- c7c5-424d-98cc-df35645cc145", "Description": "Laser Lightware Altimeter" }, { "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0.15 } } }, "Name": "Camera Sony Alpha7R-IV", "uuid": "138b0aed- d3b6-4ddc-bc2b-de482cd1ec9c", "Description": "Camera with a 85mm lens. Rotation may vary" }], </pre>	<pre> "z": 0 } }, "Name": "Autopilot DJI A3 Pro", "uuid": "369024b2-f65c- 44a3-926d-a8fd1d1c9bef" }, { "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": -0.4 } } }, "Name": "Altimeter Lightware", "uuid": "2b4f4fac-c7c5- 424d-98cc-df35645cc145", "Description": "Laser Lightware Altimeter" }, { "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0.15 } } }, "Name": "Camera Sony Alpha7R-IV", "uuid": "138b0aed-d3b6- 4ddc-bc2b-de482cd1ec9c", "Description": "Camera with a 85mm lens. Rotation may vary" }], "Completed": true }, </pre>	<pre> "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 } }, "Name": "Autopilot DJI A3 Pro", "uuid": "369024b2-f65c- 44a3-926d-a8fd1d1c9bef" }, { "tf": { "Rotation": { "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": -0.4 } } }, "Name": "Altimeter Lightware", "uuid": "2b4f4fac-c7c5- 424d-98cc-df35645cc145", "Description": "Laser Lightware Altimeter" }, { "tf": { "Rotation": { </pre>
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<pre> "Completed": true }, "InspectionPlan": "2eb9b2a3-0e85-400d-99c7-bbc3847d2139" } } </pre>	<pre> "InspectionPlan": "dfee2a52-f351-47ea-87ca-e4504d8e9701" } } </pre>	<pre> "w": 1, "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0 }, "Translation": { "x": 0, "y": 0, "z": 0.15 } }, "Name": "Camera Sony Alpha7R-IV", "uuid": "138b0aed-d3b6-4ddc-bc2b-de482cd1ec9c", "Description": "Camera with a 85mm lens. Rotation may vary" } }, "Completed": true }, "InspectionPlan": "8363a65a-b336-4ef9-807c-3becfd55336e" } </pre>
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For each inspection plan, one or more inspection tasks could be defined at a specific location on the asset. In order to implement the inspection plans alongside the Alora asset three subsequent inspection tasks were defined, one for each inspection plan and inspection location. As it seems, there is a complete association between the inspection tasks and the location and task that they had to be associated with. As the inspection task/missions were performed with the same robotic system (AEROCAM) and the same payload (Sony Alpha 7R IV mounted on a Gremsy gimbal), a unique UUID should have existed in both tasks, a fact that can be seen in the extracted JSON objects that are presented below.

Table 10. Definition of the inspection tasks, and the association with the inspection plans, location, robotic systems and payloads.

Inspection Task 1	Inspection Task 2	Inspection Task 3
<pre> { "UniqueID": "1afd51fa-0b06-44f1-ba42-af0c6271834f", "Name": "Pillar 2 Visual Inspection", "Description": null, "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:52:34.891201Z", } </pre>	<pre> { "UniqueID": "41ff8941-289b-4a08-a861-48abbf013a26", "Name": "Visual Inspection Pillar", "Description": null, "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-20T06:40:48.604566Z", } </pre>	<pre> { "UniqueID": "2fc26b66-f441-4d9f-8ca4-045492dbacde", "Name": "Visual inspection Pillar 2", "Description": null, "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-20T08:03:05.654394Z", } </pre>

<pre> "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-14T06:52:34.891248Z", "Properties": { "index": 0, "inspectionType": { "id": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fba7", "name": "Visual inspection" }, "inspectionOrder": ["EF098A11-902A-4C0A-BB33-1EE00FDFAD8C", 3], "inspectionPlanId": "2eb9b2a3-0e85-400d-99c7-bbc3847d2139", "inspectionTypeId": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fba7", "roboticSystemIds": ["297fc6f7-6227-4ede-b996-cd18d66e9975"], "sensorPayloadIds": ["14506157-8937-4a46-a895-352faf91be59"], "inspectionTypeName": "Visual inspection", "inspectionTaskOrder": 0, "inspectionLocationId": "744b26d8-c6cd-45ba-a23c-fce83e34f360", "inspectionLocationName": "Pillar 2", "inspectionLocationOrder": 2, "inspectionLocationSubtype": "Annotation 3D" } </pre>	<pre> "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-20T06:40:48.604643Z", "Properties": { "index": 0, "inspectionType": { "id": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fba7", "name": "Visual inspection" }, "inspectionOrder": ["5DC94580-0B7C-4D9B-A752-5B4985AA65B7", 1], "inspectionPlanId": "dfee2a52-f351-47ea-87ca-e4504d8e9701", "inspectionTypeId": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fba7", "roboticSystemIds": ["297fc6f7-6227-4ede-b996-cd18d66e9975"], "sensorPayloadIds": ["14506157-8937-4a46-a895-352faf91be59"], "inspectionTypeName": "Visual inspection", "inspectionTaskOrder": 0, "inspectionLocationId": "e8b09ebb-3e9c-4b38-b3af-f493cd44f740", "inspectionLocationName": "Pillar 1", "inspectionLocationOrder": 0, "inspectionLocationSubtype": "Annotation 3D" } </pre>	<pre> "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-20T08:03:05.654449Z", "Properties": { "index": 0, "inspectionType": { "id": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fba7", "name": "Visual inspection" }, "inspectionOrder": ["EF098A11-902A-4C0A-BB33-1EE00FDFAD8C", 1], "inspectionPlanId": "8363a65a-b336-4ef9-807c-3becfd55336e", "inspectionTypeId": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fba7", "roboticSystemIds": ["297fc6f7-6227-4ede-b996-cd18d66e9975"], "sensorPayloadIds": ["14506157-8937-4a46-a895-352faf91be59"], "inspectionTypeName": "Visual inspection", "inspectionTaskOrder": 0, "inspectionLocationId": "744b26d8-c6cd-45ba-a23c-fce83e34f360", "inspectionLocationName": "Pillar 2", "inspectionLocationOrder": 0, "inspectionLocationSubtype": "Annotation 3D" } </pre>
<p>Robotic System</p>	<p>Payload</p>	
<pre> { "UniqueID": "297fc6f7-6227-4ede-b996-cd18d66e9975", "Name": "AEROCAM", "Description": "Aerial robot for the visual inspection of viaducts", "CreationDatetime": "2021-11-29T13:41:55.912226Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2021-11-29T13:41:55.912265Z", "Properties": { </pre>	<pre> { "UniqueID": "14506157-8937-4a46-a895-352faf91be59", "Description": "AEROCAM - Inspection camera", "Specifications": "Sony Alpha 7R IV mounted on a Gremsy gimbal", "SerialNumber": null, "Type": "Digital camera", "CreationDatetime": "2021-11-29T13:38:49.457228Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2021-11-29T13:38:49.457263Z", "Properties": { "General": "Fully configurable. Possibility of using different lenses." } </pre>	

<pre> "General": "Navigates autonomously in GNSS-degraded scenarios using LIDAR, takes HQ pictures.", }, "Payload": ["14506157-8937-4a46-a895-352faf91be59"] } </pre>	<pre> } </pre>
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Continuing, within the RCS, with the mission and specific mission tasks were generated and initiated. The DMS was responsible to forward to the DDHL and afterwards to gRCS/mRCS the data related to the relevant Inspection Tasks, Inspection Types, Inspection Locations, Asset, and other metadata or files, associated with any of these entities. Having collected all the aforementioned, the gRCS/mRCS is able to create the detailed mission and mission tasks taking into consideration the specificities of the operational area. So, for the purpose of the three identified missions, five total mission tasks were created and performed alongside the inspection location, with only the first mission to operate three mission tasks; information that was also revealed in Table 8. Table 11 presents the generation of the tasks and the associated metadata of each mission task that contains the generated measurements from the robotic systems. In this pilot case, we are positive to say the all three mission-phases have been performed as we are able to see the predicted annotations on the images, a result that is provided by the Artificial Intelligence (AI) services. By adding this information, we shall declare that the retrieved result will be large enough, and thus, instead we decided to provide the API GET request, from where the file metadata can be retrieved with only a sample of the returned JSONB.

Table 11. The generated mission tasks for each mission and the file metadata, containing the collected observations.

Mission Task 1	Mission Task 2	Mission Task 3
A	A	A
<pre> { "UniqueID": "d1ae7fa2-a448-4d80-a99f-c51bd67a18a8", "Name": "mission_task_1", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-07-19T10:31:02.530000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "1fd45c6c-4b3f-4eb7-b42b-626f94d318fa", "InspectionType": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fbea7", "Mission": "21f57f67-2f44-47a7-8556-eef3b7be4f23" } </pre>	<pre> { "UniqueID": "b594ec77-bbea-4d85-8310-6d78cf3737b4", "Name": "mission_task_0", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-07-22T08:30:16.575000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "41ff8941-289b-4a08-a861-48abbf013a26", "InspectionType": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fbea7", "Mission": "9d83bb2a-221f-42e2-bd44-fb4f5439726b" } </pre>	<pre> { "UniqueID": "8e5202d6-52e3-44c6-a9e0-4e55fa719205", "Name": "mission_task_0", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-07-21T09:48:13.525000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "2fc26b66-f441-4d9f-8ca4-045492dbacde", "InspectionType": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fbea7", "Mission": "5ae0f020-981d-40ca-a54b-f42eb6227f0a" } </pre>
B		
<pre> { "UniqueID": "23284a6d-df14-4776-ab1a-04998774284e", "Name": "mission_task_0", } </pre>		

<pre>"ExecutionDatetime": "2022-07-19T10:31:02.530000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "b34e961c-2f3d-43e5-82f7-cd38cffbafbe", "InspectionType": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fbea7", "Mission": "21f57f67-2f44-47a7-8556-eef3b7be4f23" }</pre>		
<p>C</p>		
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "17271c11-817f-4d20-91a4-cc67e4cbd9bd", "Name": "mission_task_2", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-07-19T10:31:02.530000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "1afd51fa-0b06-44f1-ba42-af0c6271834f", "InspectionType": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fbea7", "Mission": "21f57f67-2f44-47a7-8556-eef3b7be4f23" }</pre>		
<p>Generated FileMetadata from mission task 1:</p> <p>https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/MissionTask/d1ae77a2-a448-4d80-a99f-c51bd67a18a8/FileMetadata/</p> <pre>{ "UniqueID": "e49485b0-e78a-4659-b69e-f0358334f95f", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/b2249cd0-a072-4ce0-a73a-54651f2223d9", "MimeType": "image/jpeg", "Size": "21149502", "OriginalName": "DSC00012.JPG", "Content": "mRCS - Image", "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-19T14:51:45.023387Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-19T14:51:45.023425Z", "Properties": { "thumbnail": { "url": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/5c9ce465-ca95-4d4d-b892-ad081f5308aa" } } }</pre>	<p>Generated FileMetadata from mission task 2:</p> <p>https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/MissionTask/b594ec77-bbea-4d85-8310-6d78cf3737b4/FileMetadata/</p> <pre>{ "UniqueID": "20581eba-30ec-47eb-bde6-888d4a499c3d", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/3432631e-f9d3-451a-babe-3ce9eb77ba23", "MimeType": "image/jpeg", "Size": "24185833", "OriginalName": "DSC00006.JPG", "Content": "mRCS - Image", "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-29T09:53:54.191181Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-29T09:53:54.191228Z", "Properties": { "thumbnail": { "url": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/44398f30-5a19-4b42-a3ff-8f395dceb879" } } }</pre>	<p>Generated FileMetadata from mission task 3:</p> <p>https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/MissionTask/8e5202d6-52e3-44c6-a9e0-4e55fa719205/FileMetadata/</p> <pre>{ "UniqueID": "e6d20492-6665-41a7-8d73-ef22e727359f", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/1f62c760-9a14-482c-9a7b-6fb45e0825e2", "MimeType": "image/jpeg", "Size": "16264496", "OriginalName": "DSC00001.JPG", "Content": "mRCS - Image", "CreationDatetime": "2022-07-28T14:45:46.635526Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-07-28T14:45:46.635604Z", "Properties": { "thumbnail": { "url": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/e4ebf234-39b3-423a-a33f-4a7379af001f" } } }</pre>

<pre> }, "Annotations": [{ "regions": [{ "id": "7064063a", "tags": ["bounding box", "yolo", "corrosion"], "type": "polygon", "points": [], "confidence": 0.2496599406003952, "boundingBox": { "top": 3168, "left": 4854, "width": 9222, "height": 6336 } }], "algoType": "YOLOv5" </pre>	<pre> }, "Annotations": [{ "regions": [{ "id": "682b7bba", "tags": ["bounding box", "yolo", "corrosion"], "type": "polygon", "points": [], "confidence": 0.2534787356853485, "boundingBox": { "top": 5198, "left": 2406, "width": 848, "height": 506 } }], "id": "682b7ce6", "tags": ["bounding box", "yolo", "corrosion"], "type": "polygon", "points": [], "confidence": 0.23821787536144257, "boundingBox": { "top": 315, "left": 5292, "width": 509, "height": 348 } }], "algoType": "YOLOv5" } </pre>	<pre> }, "Annotations": [{ "regions": [{ "id": "fe103ae0", "tags": ["bounding box", "yolo", "corrosion"], "type": "polygon", "points": [], "confidence": 0.2481997311115265, "boundingBox": { "top": 891, "left": 8754, "width": 1085, "height": 854 } }], "algoType": "YOLOv5" } </pre>
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c. Example for the Tunnel validation scenario

In the tunnel experimental case, two validation scenarios, one general and one local visual inspection were executed in two specific inspection locations, the drainage and the road tunnel. As is described in detail in Section 5. of this current document, in the first case, two robotic systems, the TT-DRONE and the CART were used for the implementation of the local and general inspection, respectively, while in the road tunnel both inspection types were implemented by CART. As an example, we will describe only the workflow of the execution of the inspection plan, with the UUID- “22520ddb-83b7-4299-a8a9-8ebf365785ee”, which was conducted by the TT-DRONE in the drainage asset (UUID-“0fa509cd-84d4-4b89-b74c-89351dcec0d6”). A graphical illustration of the aforementioned is depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Example of the inspection validation scenario on the drainage tunnel that was implemented by the TT-DRONE robotic system.

For this particular asset, more than 10 different inspection locations were defined, in which the inspections alongside the asset had been created. In terms of simplicity, we will present three locations that are associated with the three indicative inspection tasks that are presented in Table 13. As can be seen in Table 12 , both inspection points show the specific target points where the robot will create the local inspection exist, as well as the general inspection area bounding box.

Table 12. The generated inspection locations, for this asset.

Asset - 0fa509cd-84d4-4b89-b74c-89351dcec0d6 – “Drainage tunnel”		
Inspection Location 1	Inspection Location 2	Inspection Location 3
{ "UniqueID": "1e7887d1-8417-4897-8071-e037c666f68b", "Name": "InspectionPoint 5", "Subtype": "Annotation 3D",	{ "UniqueID": "540b9533-4039-4e6f-be56-3c93ae0da985", "Name": "InspectionPoint 3", "Subtype": "Annotation 3D",	{ "UniqueID": "d4a90caa-bcaa-4d5f-b9a5-df83c3e859bb", "Name": "InspectionPoint 4", "Subtype": "Annotation 3D",

<pre>"CreationDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:08:03.547959Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:08:03.548034Z", "Properties": {...}, "Asset": "0fa509cd-84d4-4b89-b74c-89351dcecd06" }</pre>	<pre>"CreationDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:08:03.576296Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:08:03.576337Z", "Properties": {...}, "Asset": "0fa509cd-84d4-4b89-b74c-89351dcecd06" }</pre>	<pre>"CreationDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:08:03.387299Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:08:03.387370Z", "Properties": {...}, "Asset": "0fa509cd-84d4-4b89-b74c-89351dcecd06" }</pre>
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Furthermore, for the inspection locations and this inspection plan, three visual and local inspection tasks were arranged and defined, (Table 13). In terms of defying the inspection type, all of the tasks were performed in the context of the visual inspection, and thus, all the inspection tasks are associated with the same inspection type.

Table 13. The generated visual inspection tasks, for this specific inspection plan.

Inspection plan -22520ddb-83b7-4299-a8a9-8ebf365785ee – USE_METSOVOU_1		
Inspection Task 1	Inspection Task 2	Inspection Task 3
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "f945cb7d-1cd0-4e6c-ab93-cb2968e51f05", "Name": "Visual inspection 1", "Description": null, "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:13:38.485217Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:13:38.485363Z", "Properties": { "index": 0, "inspectionType": { "id": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fbae7", "name": "Visual inspection" } }, "inspectionOrder": ["6B7A538F-6669-4F77-9220-1EB1BFCBF619", 4], "inspectionPlanId": "22520ddb-83b7-4299-a8a9-8ebf365785ee", "roboticSystemIds": ["5e90ea19-5e71-45ad-ae06-9e95836b5950"], "sensorPayloadIds": ["bd490b1e-c3bc-4b92-af51-abce68ab1352"], "inspectionTaskOrder": 0, "inspectionLocationId": "540b9533-4039-4e6f-be56-3c93ae0da985", }</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "d2053555-f8c1-45c6-b4e9-379b37b361c9", "Name": "Visual inspection 1", "Description": null, "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:13:38.502126Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:13:38.502173Z", "Properties": { "index": 0, "inspectionType": { "id": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fbae7", "name": "Visual inspection" } }, "inspectionOrder": ["9F3FDED6-58C9-499A-AC8D-A2BAC5565D43", 5], "inspectionPlanId": "22520ddb-83b7-4299-a8a9-8ebf365785ee", "roboticSystemIds": ["5e90ea19-5e71-45ad-ae06-9e95836b5950"], "sensorPayloadIds": ["bd490b1e-c3bc-4b92-af51-abce68ab1352"], "inspectionTaskOrder": 0, "inspectionLocationId": "1e7887d1-8417-4897-8071-e037c666f68b", }</pre>	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "fb0aeb09-e32d-4d98-86bd-b2fa3afe8c87", "Name": "Visual inspection 1", "Description": null, "CreationDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:13:38.482729Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-09-30T16:13:38.482773Z", "Properties": { "index": 0, "inspectionType": { "id": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fbae7", "name": "Visual inspection" } }, "inspectionOrder": ["29A99C89-3A27-43A7-B243-5F9755AE941A", 3], "inspectionPlanId": "22520ddb-83b7-4299-a8a9-8ebf365785ee", "roboticSystemIds": ["5e90ea19-5e71-45ad-ae06-9e95836b5950"], "sensorPayloadIds": ["bd490b1e-c3bc-4b92-af51-abce68ab1352"], "inspectionTaskOrder": 0, }</pre>

<pre>"inspectionLocationOrder": 3 } }</pre>	<pre>"inspectionLocationOrder": 4 } }</pre>	<pre>"inspectionLocationId": "d4a90caa-bcaa-4d5f-b9a5- df83c3e859bb", "inspectionLocationOrder": 2 } }</pre>
Inspection Type		
<pre>{ "UniqueID": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382fba7", "Name": "Visual", "Description": null, "CreationDatetime": "2022-01-17T13:12:24.897123Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-01-17T13:12:24.897156Z", "Properties": { "displayName": "Visual inspection" } }</pre>		

Continuing, during the RCS one mission was defined for this inspection, with the number of the mission tasks to be identically the same as the inspection tasks. The mission tasks were performed with the TT-DRONE, as can be seen in the Robotic System response, and with the same Payload, which is the high-resolution camera “Sony A6400 + E PZ 16-50mm F3.5-5.6 OSS Lens”. According to the FileMetadata stored in the specific mission tasks, high quality images and localisation files were collected during the mission.

Table 14. The generated mission, and mission tasks, the assigned robotic system and payload to perform the mission tasks, and the associated FileMetadata for a specific Mission Task with UUID-"15b375a6-e848-45de-aa50-6f8a7f70c014".

Mission	<pre>{ "UniqueID": "415a75d1-9818-458e-b786-8094d226f850", "Name": "mission_00002", "ExecutionDatetime": "2021-10-01T11:08:12Z", "Description": null, "Properties": { "Map": "METSOVOU_USE.pcd", "SyncId": 1065449314, "Sensors": [{ "Name": "Lidar", "uuid": "14506157-8937-4a46-a895-352faf91be59", "Description": "RPLIDAR A3" }], "Completed": true } },</pre>
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	"InspectionPlan": "22520ddb-83b7-4299-a8a9-8ebf365785ee" }	
Mission Task 1	Mission Task 2	Mission Task 3
{ "UniqueID": "15b375a6-e848-45de-aa50-6f8a7f70c014", "Name": "mission_task_3", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-10-01T10:04:10.382000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "f945cb7d-1cd0-4e6c-ab93-cb2968e51f05", "InspectionType": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382f85e7", "Mission": "415a75d1-9818-458e-b786-8094d226f850" }	{ "UniqueID": "1173c05c-2f9d-4bbb-bca9-fb831cd2de1a", "Name": "mission_task_4", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-10-01T10:04:10.382000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "d2053555-f8c1-45c6-b4e9-379b37b361c9", "InspectionType": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382f85e7", "Mission": "415a75d1-9818-458e-b786-8094d226f850" }	{ "UniqueID": "d1307047-056b-466a-9815-ffbdfbdf7c13", "Name": "mission_task_2", "ExecutionDatetime": "2022-10-01T10:04:10.382000Z", "Notes": null, "Description": null, "Properties": null, "InspectionTask": "fb0aeb09-e32d-4d98-86bd-b2fa3afe8c87", "InspectionType": "5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267e382f85e7", "Mission": "415a75d1-9818-458e-b786-8094d226f850" }
Robotic System	Payload	
{ "UniqueID": "5e90ea19-5e71-45ad-ae06-9e95836b5950", "Name": "TTDRONE", "Description": "Aerial Robot for the local visual inspection of tunnels. Tethered to the CART ground robot.", "CreationDatetime": "2021-11-29T12:57:45.560791Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2021-11-29T12:57:45.560823Z", "Properties": { "General": "Takes-off from the roof of the ground robot, goes to the specified inspection points and takes the inspection images. This robot has an extended flight time due to the tethered system." }, "Payload": ["bd490b1e-c3bc-4b92-af51-abce68ab1352"] }	{ "UniqueID": "bd490b1e-c3bc-4b92-af51-abce68ab1352", "Description": "TTDRONE - Inspection Camera", "Specifications": "Sony A6400 + E PZ 16-50mm F3.5-5.6 OSS Lens", "SerialNumber": null, "Type": "Digital Camera", "CreationDatetime": "2021-11-29T12:42:36.417443Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2021-11-29T12:42:36.417477Z", "Properties": { "Resolution": "6000x4000p (24M)" } }	
File Metadata 1	File Metadata 2	File Metadata 3
{	{	{

<pre> "UniqueID": "15b375a6-e848-45de-aa50-6f8a7f70c014", "Files": [{ "UniqueID": "f58bbcb-eb1f-47b3-b8c2-425d7e96d981", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/83979ef0-050c-428e-ab6a-ed07a0587102/", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "81536", "OriginalName": "localization_telemetry_15b375a6.csv", "Content": "mRCS - localization_telemetry", "CreationDatetime": "2022-10-26T10:00:15.672191Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-10-26T10:00:15.672235Z", "Properties": null }] </pre>	<pre> "UniqueID": "c1dd08f8-d925-4319-abc6-efc8481a3ce5", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/f4c62bc2-596a-4053-b370-cabfae7ba8df/", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "81536", "OriginalName": "localization_telemetry_15b375a6.csv", "Content": "mRCS - localization_telemetry", "CreationDatetime": "2022-10-26T09:55:47.820737Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-10-26T09:55:47.820780Z", "Properties": null } </pre>	<pre> "UniqueID": "5ff6fc91-d6e6-41e0-848b-d3a31fa7e36a", "URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/40722cc3-72c5-47d6-81fa-2b828108d53e/", "MimeType": "image/jpeg", "Size": "7143424", "OriginalName": "img_00003.jpg", "Content": "mRCS - Image", "CreationDatetime": "2022-10-26T10:00:13.184199Z", "UpdateDatetime": "2022-10-26T10:00:13.184262Z", "Properties": {...}, "missionTaskId": "15b375a6-e848-45de-aa50-6f8a7f70c014" } </pre>
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2.2.3. *Middleware connection prior to mission execution through Data Distribution and Harmonization Layer (DDHL)*

Continuing, this section will attempt to describe the role of the Data Distribution & Harmonization Layer (DDHL) on the I&M PILOTING platform with respect to the workflow as it was thoroughly described in D7.2.

The DDHL offers a set of APIs that can be used by the general Robotic Control Station (gRCS) in order to:

1. Obtain all the information regarding an Inspection Plan that has been already defined through the IVP (Inspection Plan, Asset, Location, Type, Robotic Systems and Personnel that will be involved in the inspection and path to useful files)
2. Download all the required files (Asset model) for the execution of a mission

Prior to the Mission, the gRCS downloads from the DDHL both the Inspection Plan and the model of the Asset where the Mission is going to be executed as illustrated in the following Figure 8 and Figure 9.

Figure 8. Communications between gRCS, DDHL and DMS.

Figure 9. Flow diagrams regarding the pre-Mission actions of the gRCS.

Progressing, the gRCS is responsible to communicate with the DDHL and post all the generic data of the Mission.

As illustrated in the following Figure 10, the DDHL will instantiate the Mission and Mission Task objects, upload the input files, create the file metadata objects, and save them to the database by utilizing the APIs of the DMS. In case of failure, the DDHL will roll back the changes that have been made to the database and eventually inform the gRCS about the failure.

Inspection planning for the first pilots has been fully transversal for all robotic platforms, as gRCS has been used. In this section we will proceed to explain the design of the inspections taking as an example the AERO-CAM platform for the viaduct use case. However, the same procedure has been applied to the rest of the robotic platforms.

The planning of an inspection starts with the download of an inspection plan created in the IVP. Each inspection plan has a unique UUID identifier that is entered into the gRCS along with the user credentials and password of the user in charge of planning.

Figure 10. DDHL data download in the gRCS.

With the information and the asset downloaded, one can proceed to complete the inspection plan using the gRCS editor mode, as shown in Figure 11. In this mode, waypoints are added and areas and/or inspection points are connected to establish the route and actions to be performed.

The downloaded asset is the same as the one used in the IVP and uses the same coordinate reference system. This is a very important fact as it allows to always be able to design inspection plans and capture data in a consistent way using the same reference frame. In addition, this allows the repeatability of inspection at different time instants and the visualization and evaluation of the results in the same 3D model on the IVP once the mission is concluded.

Figure 11. Waypoints editor mode in the gRCS.

Once the inspection is ready, the user returns to run mode where the gRCS can establish connection with the robotic platform and the inspection can be uploaded. The robotic platform receives the list of actions to be executed and creates intermediate waypoints if necessary. In addition, when connection with the platform is established, it starts sending telemetry to the gRCS to have feedback of the robot status and inspection execution.

From the gRCS interface, the mission management commands are displayed, so the operator can start and finish the mission if the robot is ready for it. Once the inspection execution is finished, the gRCS interface itself packages all the data and has a specific menu for its upload through DDHL, as shown in the following figure:

Figure 12. Post mission data upload to DDHL in the gRCS.

Finally, the following figures show the operation of the gRCS with different robotic platforms:

Figure 13. gRCS running with AERO-CAM.

Figure 14. gRCS running with BIKE.

Figure 15. gRCS running with AEROX.

Figure 16. gRCS running with UGV.

Figure 17. gRCS running with RISING.

Figure 18. gRCS running with VIAD-DRONE.

Figure 19. gRCS running with TTDRONE.

Figure 20. gRCS running with CART.

In short, the state of integration of robotic platforms with gRCS, after the validation pilot experiments, is as shown in Table 15 and Table 16:

Table 15. Robotic platforms integration status with gRCS (1/2).

Robotic Platforms	AERO-CAM	VIAD-DRONE	UGV	RISING	TTDRONE
gRCS Integration Status	Fully integrated	Fully integrated	Fully integrated*	Functional but still in progress	Fully integrated

Table 16. Robotic platforms integration status with gRCS (2/2).

Robotic Platforms	CART	AEROX	BIKE	HYBRID	SATELITTE
gRCS Integration Status	Functional but still in progress	Fully integrated	Fully integrated*	In progress but very similar to AEROCAM	Not needed. Part of HYBRID platform

*Component integration is complete and functional, but improvements are pending for smoother operation.

3. Refinery experiments and results

3.1. Description of Refinery Location

Chevron Oronite site is located in the north of France in Gonfreville L'Orcher near the port of Le Havre. It is a live industrial facility, Europe's largest additive manufacturing facility. As the plant processes hydrocarbon products, some areas of the plant are rated as explosive atmosphere (ATEX) zones. For the purpose of the experiments as part of this project, all testing will be carried out in safe zones with no ATEX regulations.

The plant is a large industrial complex which offers multiple opportunities to test inspection procedures at height making it an ideal candidate for the PILOTING project, addressing a wide range of inspection categories such as large structure inspection, inspection of pipework at height, internal vessel inspection, ground monitoring and manipulation of equipment.

Figure 21. A general view of the Chevron Oronite Plant.

Testing for all refinery work scopes was conducted in the northern part of the Oronite plant split over three main work areas: 1. The Tank farm; 2. The water treatment plant; and 3. A decommissioned module.

- **The tank farm** offered access to a large storage tank to conduct UT inspection at height.
- **The water treatment plant** offered up two work areas. A ground level pipe rack to conduct UT inspection on pipe work and some pipelines in constant use for the IoT vibration sensors (wireless sensors network) for leak detection.
- **A decommissioned process module** offered up three work areas, a pressure vessel for internal inspection purposes, a congested facility for ground monitoring work scopes (navigation and manipulation) and additionally it offered up an area for inspection imagery at height for AI defect recognition (corrosion) work scopes.

Figure 22. Map of inspection areas in Oronite plant.

Table 17. Environmental conditions experience during week of testing.

Environmental conditions	
temperature	~18 deg C ambient temp.
light conditions	Natural lighting. Mis of full sun, clear skies in first half of week, Overcast for second half of week.
humidity	Approx 60% humidity
wind velocity (potentially not that important as not flying)	3-10 knots
wind direction (same as above)	East-Northeast

3.1.1. Flight Authorisation process

FADA-CATEC is a registered Spanish UAS operator. These flights cannot be included into ‘Open’ category, due airspace restrictions and specific local ground considerations for industrial areas. Therefore, a flight authorization process for ‘Specific’ category was requested.

Figure 23. Restriction area for Open category around Chevron Oronite.

As these flights scenario is set in France, a Cross-Border authorization was required, in order to get the flight permits, which requires two steps:

- 1- AESA documental inspection and authorisation of the flight operation, as aeronautical authority from the country of origin of the operator.
- 2- DSAC verification of this authorisation, checking local conditions and zonification, as authority from the destination country for the proposed flights.

Operational authorisation for the ‘Specific’ category has been issued by AESA, Spanish aeronautical authority, for these flight operations, with “**ESP-OA-00019/000**” number.

Confirmation acceptability from DSAC has “**FRA-CBO-2022FADA001/000**” number.

Figure 24. Aeronautical chart Chevron Oronite area.

In addition, some more specific and local authorisations were needed for these flight operations. Flights were planned in the prohibited airspace P-28, and inside the HAROPA port area:

- CNOA P-28 access Authorisation, with number “**220819-P28-1202-1248**”
- HAROPA port – DT Le Havre: Authorisation number “**2022-SPS-158**”

All these flight authorizations were obtained on time. It is important to point out that these flight authorizations are the same as the ones required by commercial aerial works, which it is a major milestone to facilitate the future exploitation of the developed technologies.

3.2. Refinery Large Structure (Tank) Inspection

In standard size oil refinery (100.000 barrels) it is estimated that 40.000 to 60.000 thickness measurement points are needed within a 3 to 5 years interval. About 60% to 75% of the inspection cost in this type of facility is dedicated to ultrasonic thickness measurements. Refinery structures suffer continuous corrosion due to the natural characteristics of petroleum products. Corrosion may lead to equipment failure that can provoke large accidents and explosions in such critical infrastructures. Then, the measurement of wall thickness, linked to corrosion level, is critical to the safe operation of Oil & Gas refineries.

In dealing with large continuous structures such as the storage tanks used in PILOTING, Chevron’s main requirements are to remove people from working at heights and to reduce the time and cost of accessing these difficult to reach structures. For these reasons the AeroX platform was selected to conduct UT thickness readings on a large storage tank at the Oronite plant.

The chosen area for experimental inspection with the AeroX was a tank in the uppermost left corner of the plant’s tank farm (close to the main reception area), as seen in Figure 22. Look into Table 18 and Table 19 for information about the area of inspection and the asset condition respectively. Examine Figure 25 for on-site setup display.

Table 18. Description of the inspection area for AeroX.

Plant / Area description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France.
Experiment area	Tank farm in NW area of the facility.

Table 19. Description of the tank inspected by AeroX.

Tank conditions	
Tank material	Carbon steel.
Wall plate thickness	8.18mm nominal thickness.
Coating material and thickness	Unknown thickness. Most likely 2-3 coats/layers.
Other equipment or obstructions present	No major obstructions.

<p>Pipe elevation</p>	<p>Base of accessible tank wall, approximately 1.4m above ground level. Tank height about 20m.</p>
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Figure 25. AeroX experiment set up at tank farm.

Down below, Table 20 shows the results of manually comparing a hand tool UT measurement against the drone UT measurement on a section of the lower tank (visualize procedure with both Figure 26 and Figure 27). Readings were taken next to the tank plate corner on opposite sides of a weld seam, as well as in the mid plate at the base. The AeroX platform was manually lifted into position to perform these measurements. This formed part of the validation that the UT probe was able to read the thickness within expected accuracy levels.

Figure 26. Selecting test points to validate the UT measurement on tank plate.

As seen from Table 20 initially the AeroX was unable to get consistent readings when probing the tank’s wall, with approx. 0.3 to 0.5mm error in the accuracy from the manual readings. This was mainly due to a somewhat feeble signal post-processing method, that was being affected by several factors. For example, in addition to the usual affairs related to noise, the lack of perpendicularity between the probe’s sensor and the inspected surface in some cases, was demeaning the signal to great effect. Overall, more work is needed to improve the accuracy and reliance of the UT probe measures, both in the software and hardware domain. Taking this into consideration, new and more robust signal post-processing algorithms are to be implemented, along with the corresponding enhancement in the mechanical design.

Figure 27. Manually placing the AeroX to validate the hand measurements.

It is fair to note that when using a clean calibration block, in a properly fixed environment, the AeroX’s UT probe was able to get the correct readings. Therefore, our room for improvement in this regard pivots around providing a more accurate and seamless result throughout dynamic operations.

Table 20. Results of AeroX UT measurements against hand tool measurements.

Tank plate UT measurement validation					
# Point		Manual reading	AeroX 1 st reading	AeroX 2 nd reading	Measured gap
1	Left of weld	8.3	7.8	7.9	0.4
2	Right of weld	8.2	7.8	7.9	0.3
3	Mid plate	8.5	8.1	8.2	0.3

Over its time spent at the Chevron’s Oronite plant, the AeroX system performed seven tests in total (ranging approximately from 10 to 15 minutes in duration), all of which related to two unique

experiment profiles. The first of them consisted of a longitudinal ultrasonic scan along the vertical axis, covering almost all the way up to the tank's top (see Figure 29). The second involved following a path that traversed an area defined by a singular rectangle, which surrounded the numerical markings seen in Figure 28 by a margin of a few meters. Altogether, three and four trials were done for the first and second experiment profiles respectively. However, just one iteration of each type was accomplished seamlessly and without any interruption whatsoever, due to factors like loss of tracking by the total station or RMCP performing issues, as we will explain later in this section.

It is important to point out that during these inspection missions, an advanced contact control algorithm was used to automatically maintain the contact of the aerial robot while flying. This advanced control software facilitates importantly the operation of the aerial robot during the inspection, since once the first contact is performed, the aerial robot operator has to only focus on the location of the UT sensor and taking UT measurements, since the maintenance of the contact of the aerial robot with the surface is done automatically. This control algorithm worked very smoothly during the experiments both in static conditions and dynamic conditions (where the crawler with the UT measurement was moving along the surface of the tank with up to 15 meters of continuous movement).

Figure 28. AeroX platform performing a line scan.

Figure 29. The AeroX platform at the upmost part of the tank.

Figure 30. gRCS representation of the crawler's pose near the tank's top. Please refer to Figure 28 for a direct comparison with the real world.

Spatial data of both the multi-rotor body and the crawler were recorded and monitored, thanks to the total station (fixed high precision laser-based positioning system from Leica Geosystems) and a position estimator reliant on its feedback. From this, we were able to correlate UT measures with a specific 3D point on the targeted asset, thus bringing position repeatability to the table (i.e., the ability to come back and perform a UT inspection in the same location). In this version of the robotic vehicle, the guidance of the crawler was performed by the robot vehicle operator and with the support of the visualization tool of the gRCS. In this way, it is possible for the robotic operator to know if the UT sensor (on the robotic vehicle crawler) was positioned in the location where the UT inspection was supposed to take place, and if not, be able to guide the crawler to the inspection location. The use of the total station, with reference points of the tank itself, allows to use at any time the same reference

system and be able to position the UT sensor on the same position in different inspections performed in different days. This capability of the robotic vehicle is of great importance for the end-users. Figure 28 and Figure 30 share the purpose of displaying the correspondence accuracy between the real world and the estimated crawler position. All the associated information was visualized in real time through the gRCS, and once each mission was succeeded, the data was uploaded back to the post-mission section in the IVP platform.

The trajectories made by the AeroX during the previously mentioned tests can be examined in the Figure 31, sourced from the PILOTING portal. The spatially correlated ultrasonic measurements can also be found on the IVP, although it currently lacks an integrated representation.

Figure 31. Trajectory followed by AeroX, both in the vertical line and the rectangular area experiments.

It is relevant to note that through all AeroX's performances, several slight issues related to the crawler were found. The latter went from eventual difficulties operating the crawler's probe mechanism due to design faults, to running out of contact gel because of a hasteful expenditure. Even though these problems do not pose a critical threat by themselves, they translate into delays and degrade any continuous operation to be performed. Therefore, our aim is also focused on improving the crawler's design and operational capabilities in this sense.

3.3. Refinery Pipe Inspection

The second main structures in a refinery environment are pipes and pipe racks. For these structures the major inspection requirement is wall thickness measurements using ultrasonic sensors in the parts of the structure where corrosion is most prevalent such as bends, elbows, T-sections and reducers.

For PILOTING we elected not to fly the HYBRID due to safety considerations with the landing procedure and instead chose to focus on the UT satellite crawler robot which was guided along the pipes and used to acquire UT thickness measurement data. The area selected was in the process piping area of the plant and was performed on pipes at or close to ground level.

Table 21. Description of the inspection area for HYBRID.

Plant / Area Description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France.
Experiment Area	The water pumping station in NW area of facility. Provided accessible pipe work of sufficient size (8") to test the HYBRID and UT Crawler robot.

Pipework	
Pipe material	Carbon Steel
diameter and thickness	8 Inch Schedule 40 (8.18 mm nominal thickness)
Coating material and thickness	Unknown thickness. Most likely 2-3 coats/layers.
(See diagram below)	Pipe support structure dummy leg welded directly to process pipe elbow
Pipe support separation (along the pipe)	13.5 ft (4100 mm)
Parallel pipe distance separation	minimum 140 mm
parallel pipe characteristics	Nearest obstacle was conduit tray below pipe ~ 140 mm clearance. Tray ~140-200 mm wide and carrying multiple ground cables.
Other equipment or obstructions present	No major obstructions as pipe runs at grade.
Pipe elevation	Elevation approx. 50 cm above ground level

Figure 32. HYBRID testing setup.

The onsite preparation includes a verification of the of the thickness reading using the full measurement chain on a calibration block of known size and accuracy. In this case a standard UT step gauge with at least one reference thickness in the range of the nominal and minimum permissible wall thickness of the asset to be inspected. If required, variables such as the speed of sound may be fine-tuned in this step to align the measurement with the expected value. The block is inlaid into an 8-inch pipe section to account for the impact the surface curvature might have on the measurement. This is carried out to a recognized standard or application specific procedure and associated operating instruction by an accredited inspector for the applicable NDT technique.

Figure 33. UT calibration at the 15 mm step.

The experiments were conducted on a section of water utility piping. Figure 34 shows a hand drawn layout of the area created during the onsite mission preparation. Depending on the type, age and criticality of the targeted piping, it is common that only an abstracted P&ID diagram (Piping & Instrumentation Diagram) may be available in the lead up to the mission. Details of the pipe support design or even the total length of a tubing section shown in the sketch might not be available at that point and have to be captured when at site.

Figure 34. Sketch of water utility piping (Lower Section) with details on pipe supports.

An inspection plan that would be typical for such a pipe section was created by the end-users to test the capabilities of the system. The sketch in Figure 35 outlines the chosen locations that might typically be classified as critical and designated for inspection.

Figure 35. Sketch diagram of pipework section used for HYBRID Piloting. Note star showing location in conjunction with the image in Figure 34.

Figure 36 is a photo of the targeted pipe section to be inspected. Note the darker underside of the piping where stagnant water from rain has deteriorated the surface. Localized areas of corrosion are present around the full circumference. As this type of water piping is deemed non-critical, it represents a worst-case scenario in terms of conditions to be encountered. Such surface conditions can make the acquisition of reliable wall thickness measurements using ultrasound difficult. The relatively high wall thickness of 8.18 mm and likely lower weld quality manufacturing requirements result in tall welds with a steep toe angle, posing a challenging obstacle. The carbon steel of the pipe has a protective coating of typically two to three layers totalling around 0.2 to 0.3 mm thickness.

Figure 36. Image of test area pipework – Note yellow star showing location in Figure 34. Sketch.

As this experiment was to be conducted without the drone flying, it was instead manually placed in a location where sufficient landing clearance would be available. From there, the satellite deployed from its bay. By manual remote control based on a video feed from the two navigation cameras on the satellite, a pilot maneuvered the crawler successively to each previously defined inspection location. With the UT sensor mounted on the satellite, connected to an instrument on the flyer, communicating through the drone's wireless link to a ground station laptop running an analysis software, wall thickness readings were captured in each targeted inspection location. All 10 measurements could be captured within one deployment and within the 3 meters tether range of the drone. Upon completion, the satellite returned to its bay and the drone retrieved from the area.

Figure 37. HYBRID set up on the pipe section with the UT crawler deployed and taking UT measurements.

Experiments were run based on a calibration block supplied by the Oronite facility. Hand UT measurements were also acquired by a certified inspection crew at the same 10 points as the HYBRID UT crawler for direct comparison and validation.

The table below shows the results of the crawler UT measurements versus the UT measurements taken manually by the qualified inspector using conventional UT measurement tools.

Table 22. Results of UT crawler measurements against hand tool measurements.

Utility water piping (Lower section) UT Measurement (mm)				
# point		Ut reading (drone)	Ut reading (UT hand)	Measurement gap
1	Top pipe	7,57	8,06	0,49
2	Top pipe	8,11	8,35	0,24
3	top tee	9,5	9,47	-0,03
4	Side tee	10	9,98	-0,02
5	Side tee	10,2	10,45	0,25
6	Side pipe	7,9	8,04	0,14
7	Bottom Elbow	8,28	8,07	-0,21
8	Bottom Elbow	8,3	7,79	-0,51
9	side pipe	7,6	7,96	0,36
10	Side pipe	7,75	7,95	0,2

The UT measurements were performed blindly, with no previous knowledge of nominal pipe thickness, corrosion allowance, pipe coating specification or previous inspection records. It can be clearly seen that there is correlation between the two sets of results, thus confirming that the UT crawler performed exceptionally well in the industrial site tests with an excellent correlation success rate, always within 1 mm accuracy, in line with expectations

A second set of measurements were performed on an elbow in the upper section of the utility water piping. A standalone magnetic crawler was used that was configured with hardwired ethernet communication through the umbilical. This will be the satellite to be integrated in the second iteration of the integrated HYBRID system. The ethernet communication allows more advanced position control and reading of the of integrated sensors. The combination of accelerometer, inclinometer and odometry sensors and a predefined 3D model from the asset builder on the I&M platform allow localization of the satellite on the asset. The goal of this test was to validate this second iteration of the satellite subsystem and to record a mission that can be used for the development of the DDHL interface for upload to the I&M platform. It also recorded the time needed to acquire each measurement.

Figure 38. Image of the test area in the upper section of the utility water piping (left). 3D view of the recorded mission with the captured measurement points (right).

Table 23. Results of UT ethernet crawler measurements.

Utility water piping (upper section) UT measurement (mm)				
#point		UT reading	Mission time (s)	Δ time (s)
1	12' elbow	7.46	20.28	0
2	12' elbow	7.10	50.92	30.64
3	3' elbow	8.38	79.27	28.98
4	6' elbow	8.02	103.22	23.95
5	9' elbow	8.58	150.37	47.15
6	0' straight	7.58	308.02	157.65
7	9' straight	7.96	348.62	40.60
8	9' straight	7.84	376.38	27.76
9	0' straight	8.40	434.38	58.00
Average				51.84
Median				35.62

The satellite UT crawler performed well in the congested pipe rack areas tested. Separation on certain areas of the pipe work was as low as 100mm between piping on the racks and the UT crawler was able to navigate between the pipes with ease to allow a full 360deg inspection of the circumference of the pipe being inspected.

A major success was the ability of the UT crawler to navigate across rough weld seams on the pipework. In previous outdoor validation (controlled) testing, we had proven the UT crawler capable of traversing weld seams, but the test pipework was typically cleaned and welds were smaller (1 to 2mm proud from pipe surface), whereas in the live refinery testing the crawler traversed welds double this size on rougher and dirty pipe coatings with relative ease.

The UT crawler was tested extensively on a section of piping with an Elbow and a T-section and was able to navigate sufficiently throughout, only limited by its tether length to the aerial platform.

Another success of the UT crawler was that experiments were effectively conducted under BVLOS conditions (Beyond Visual Line Of Sight) with the crawler being teleoperated from the main operator control station some distance from the pipework being inspected.

3.4. Refinery Pressure Vessel Inspection

Inspection of confined spaces such as the Pressure Vessel used during the site testing for PILOTING is a major concern for refinery owners such as end user Chevron. The associated risks for inspections doing confined space entry are high due to cramped and dirty conditions and are typically lengthy jobs involving a lot of preparation and specialized training. The use of ‘camera on a stick’ avoids entry using inspectors but only offers a limited view of the structures and is a completely manual process.

For this work scope the PILOTING project employed the BIKE robot which is a magnetic crawler designed for such a task.

Table 24. Description of work area for BIKE.

Plant / Area Description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France.
Experiment Area	A multi-level decommissioned module housing a mix of process piping and vessels. Pressure vessel used was in the NE section of the module on the ground floor.

Pressure Vessel	
Vessel material	Carbon Steel
Wall Thickness	12 mm nominal thickness
Coating material and thickness	No coating
Access	Scaffold erected to allow for level access to manway
Other equipment or obstructions present	Manway flange lip encountered and not on schematic drawings

Figure 39. BIKE robot set up and ready to enter Pressure vessel manway (left). BIKE robot doing inspection inside Pressure Vessel (middle). BIKE software display showing the 3D model of vessel and location of BIKE robot inside (right).

The BIKE was tested by a pre-defined sequence of validation tests. The results of all the tests performed are listed in the following sections.

Transportation

System was shipped to the site on a Euro pallet. The shipment included all system components as well as the tools and protective equipment for three operators. Furthermore, the shipment also contained testing equipment, which would not be required for an actual inspection mission.

Measurement Equipment Verification

VT (Visual Testing) equipment (the inspection camera) and UT (Ultrasonic Testing) equipment must be verified / calibrated prior to as well as after an inspection mission. To test if the equipment could be positively verified, the inspection camera performance was verified using a standardized camera test-chart and the ultrasound sensor performance was verified by means of a calibration block.

Figure 40. Test chart on inspection camera at 60cm distance. The camera is able to resolve the details and colors.

Figure 41. UT calibration using a 0.5 in. calibration block (12.7 mm). Thickness reading matches perfectly.

Both, the camera as well as the ultrasonic sensor could be verified before and after any robotic deployments and consistently produced correct measurements.

Mobility Capabilities and Safety Demonstration

Gas Detection:

The BIKE platform carries an on-board sensor to measure the percentage of LEL (Lower Explosion Limit) of gas concentration. The gas-detection system needs to be verified prior to use by use of calibrated test gas.

If the concentration of combustible gas near the sensor exceeds a pre-set threshold (20% LEL) the robotic system must shut down the robot and completely de-energize the BIKE.

System shutdown on combustible gas concentration exceeding threshold level was successfully verified using 50% LEL Methane calibrated gas.

Deployment:

The deployment method of BIKE had to be altered due to a protruding flange, which was not in scope of BIKE capabilities. This property of the manway flange was not indicated on the drawings; hence no mitigation was prepared. Tools exist to deploy the BIKE under such conditions, however, non were available on-site. The issue was mitigated by adding a person to the confined space entry permit, allowing for manual placement of BIKE inside the asset.

Figure 42. Protruding manway flange.

Mobility:

The BIKE robot is supposed to drive on the entire vessel shell, including vertically up, overhead as well as doing the transition from cylinder to head section

All BIKE mobility capabilities (except for the deployment) were successfully verified by moving the BIKE along the internal vessel surface. Vertically up, upside-down, and transition from cylindrical section to vessel head.

Figure 43. Test path for BIKE mobility verification.

Localization Demonstration and Map Verification

In an initial step, the rotating LIDAR was used to extract a point-cloud of the visible environment. The point-cloud was used to verify the accuracy of the environment model. In case of significant discrepancies, this would have allowed to correct the model prior to continuation. Correct localization based on the asset model was verified by moving the robot to points of interest and comparing the reported position to the actual one (determined from actual features with known locations such as nozzles). Results were documented by capturing images and reported robot poses.

Results:

1. The environment model was very accurate; nozzle-locations and diameters were correct.
2. Several nozzles, including the manway, were protruding. This was not indicated in the drawings and the model had to be updated accordingly.

Figure 44. Protruding nozzles after model update.

3. The modelled vessel-head deviated from the true shape. A point-cloud overlay shows maximum deviations due to head shape mismatch of about 7 cm along the longitudinal axis. It was however impossible to compensate for this source of error. The modeling tool does not allow for custom head shapes, and the drawings do not give sufficient information about the exact shape. A localization error along the longitudinal axis was to be expected.

Figure 45. Pointcloud overlay on asset model. Deviation in head-area.

4. A total of seven localization accuracy checks in various locations were performed. Accuracy was clearly within 10 cm. The biggest measured deviation was 7.5 cm. (note that the model uncertainty along x-axis was in the same range).

Figure 46. Accuracy tests by pointing the camera at known locations. This tests overall accuracy, including the pointing accuracy of the camera. Object of interest is always found within the zoomed in image.

Figure 47. Accuracy tests by driving the BIKE very closely to a known location (nozzle) using the navigation camera and measuring the distance in the localization tool. This tests localization of the robot only and the error should remain within specifications.

Surface Preparation Demonstration

An inspection plan containing a representative set of points of interest was used for this demonstration. The plan contained several ultrasonic spot measurements and one ultrasonic raster scan inspection. The surface preparation tool was mounted on the robot and the designated areas were prepared for ultrasonic thickness readings. The results were documented by capturing images on the inspection camera and by taking thickness readings in the cleaned areas.

Results:

The surface preparation tools were working properly, and cleaning was clearly possible. However, the surface had already been prepared rather nicely. Hence, no difference in ultrasound coupling performance was observed on prepared vs. unprepared surfaces.

Figure 48. Cleaned area is clearly visible.

Figure 49. Cleaning was tested on a small spot (left side) and a larger area (on the right).

Inspection Demonstration

An inspection plan containing a representative set of points of interest was used for this demonstration. The plan contained several visual inspections, ultrasonic spot measurements and one ultrasonic raster scan inspection.

The system was equipped with the UT module and the inspection camera.

Once deployed in the asset, the inspection was performed according to procedures for visual and ultrasonic testing. The robot was moving autonomously, and inspections were performed and recorded at the points of interest.

Time was automatically tracked in the mission data. From this data cost savings and other information can be directly derived.

Results:

1. The inspection was performed successfully.
2. A full mission report was created:
File: b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad_3.docx
3. An inspection time analysis (over two full inspection runs) was performed
File: Inspection_Time_Analysis.docx

Total Inspection Time Analysis

Inspection of asset of V1506

Dimensions:

L = 2.4m, Diameter = 1.3m

Total Time: 1 h 57 min

The robot was actively used for 45 minutes inside the asset.

For a total of 10 well distributed inspection locations.

Figure 50. Vessel Inspection Demonstration UT Spots.

Table 25. Inspection demonstration steps.

Description	Minutes	Notes / Deviations
Setup (Unboxing, Placing, Connections, Starting computers, including water reservoir, pump, gas detection system, table, chairs, two computers)	25	Done by 3 persons. But it would normally include less equipment and only 1-2 persons
Calibration of Camera. Testchart mounted at arms-length from camera lens with robot outside	5	Done in daylight, basic functionality check only
Calibration of UT sensor	5	Had some SW issues took 15 min. should be max 5 min
Placement of robot inside asset	10	Done by hand due to protruding flange. Would be faster if driving in was possible.
Inspection	45	Depends on number of pictures etc. See details on inspections 1 and 2 below
Removing robot from asset	5	Done by hand due to protruding flange.
Out calibration of Camera	2	Done in daylight, basic functionality check only
Out calibration of UT	5	Was not possible due to time constraints, using nominal time

Packing up	15	
Total Time	117	

All translations were done with BIKE in Auto-Mode.

Inspections were performed in manual mode, raster scan mode and point-by-touch mode

No general visual overview data was collected. If required, this would add a few minutes to the total time.

Below the specific timing for two inspections are detailed.

Inspection 1

File: b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad_3.mission_db

Inspection Time: 45 minutes

Table 26. Inspection 1 details.

Visual Inspections	UT Spot Inspections	UT Raster Scan
7 locations distributed over asset 23 pictures (overview and close-up) 1-3 minutes per location	2 spots 1 minute per spot	Only simulated, no UT data recorded 14.5 minutes

Inspection 2

File: b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad_4.mission_db

Inspection Time: 45 minutes

Table 27. Inspection 2 details.

Visual Inspections	UT Spot Inspections	UT Raster Scan
7 locations distributed over asset 14 pictures (overview and close-up) 1-2 minutes per location	3 spots 1 minute per spot	200x100 mm Area 5 mm line separation 15.5 minutes

Repeatability Demonstration

The inspection as performed for the Inspection Demonstration was repeated and all results were logged for comparison. Figure 51 shows a visual inspection from the first inspection run and Figure 52 shows the same point of interest from the second run. The comparison shows a quite good location repeatability. The difference in illumination brightness and resulting glare results from the inspector adjusting the light intensity manually during the second run for improved image quality.

Figure 51: Visual Inspection of Pipe Elbow Point of Interest from Inspection 1.

Figure 52: Visual Inspection of Pipe Elbow Point of Interest from Inspection 2.

Results: A full second inspection run was performed and a report generated. The results and locations matched very well and certainly within the specified range.

File: b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad_4.docx

The mission database files for run 1 and run 2 are:

b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad_3.mission_db

b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad_4.mission_db

3.5. Refinery Ground Monitoring

Due to the hazardous nature of the refinery environment, operators are constantly looking for opportunities to reduce the amount of time staff need to be out in the facilities doing dull, dangerous, or dirty work. There are many routine operations that currently require the presence of a person such as a technician or inspector to conduct operator rounds to check equipment health amongst other things. This type of routine and mundane ground monitoring is a good use case for robotics and covers inspection of equipment, possible manipulation of equipment and if necessary to raise an alarm is something it out of the ordinary.

PILOTING will focus on multiple ground monitoring tasks such as autonomous navigation around a facility using two robots the RISING (Robotnik) and UGV (ETHZ), and use of static sensors on pipelines for a period of approximately 14 months to assess leak detection and or flow anomalies (ICCS).

In addition to autonomous navigation, the RISING robot will additionally attempt stair climbing and rough ground testing as part of its navigation and will capture imagery of the plant such as Infrared (IR), Thermal and RGB. The UGV robot in addition to autonomous navigation will conduct autonomous manipulation of a hand wheel valve.

The area selected to run the ground monitoring experiments is in the decommissioned process module.

Table 28. Description of work area for ground monitoring

Plant / Area Description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France.
Experiment Area	A multi-level decommissioned process module housing a mix of process piping and vessels. RISING and UGV experiments done on ground level and Aerocam to fly around perimeter and acquire hi-res imagery.

RISING

The Ground monitoring tests with the RISING were done according to specification and KPI definition, also aiming to verify that adaptations done in the robot were significant and properly addressed.

Figure 53. RISING robot running autonomous navigation.

In order to check further these points, the envisioned validation tests conducted are explained in the following sections

Equipment Verification

- *The robot is inspected to check if it has integrated a gas detection system, a traction system for operating on different surfaces, a lidar, a datalink for ground communications, and different cameras including a thermal one.*
- *A reliable time of operation is ensured by the robot's capability of exchanging battery packages.*
- *Robustness of the robot is inspected against certain conditions during the test, such as water splashing and dust presence.*

In this regard, conclusions could be extracted not only by inspecting the equipment but also by analyzing the robot behavior within the very first mission tests.

The highlights here would be that:

- RISING robot could move smoothly in all different terrains, including different types of asphalt, cement and steel grating (straight and v-shaped). The rubber compound on the tracks is resistant and less fragile than previous ones. On the other hand, the rubber stoppers are degrading fast in aggressive soils and are subject to maintenance actions (week-wise with intense use). In this sense, the rubber stoppers are not only easy to manufacture and change but also cost-effective, not really compromising the robot operation.
- Up to 4 video streams in the visual spectrum and 1 thermal video/picture can be retrieved any time from the robot. The specific depth cameras are good for environment contextualization but visual feedback is not being use right now for navigation or obstacle avoidance.

- Environmental conditions favored the validation of robustness against water splashing, as a light rain was present during experiments. Sealings and encapsulations worked as expected.

Battery endurance is above expectations. After daily experiments, robot never went under 50%. Wireless charging proved to work flawlessly, and full charge achieved again in around 2h. A complete exchange/extraction of the battery can also be done in less than 2 minutes.

Mapping

- *The robot is tele-operated around the plant with a LIDAR to acquire 3D scans while traversing the site. The 3D scans are processed offline to build a final 3D map of the plant that is useful for creating and navigating within an inspection plan.*

RISING robot has been improved with the addition of a 90°x360° dome like LIDAR (Robosense RB-Pearl) that features 32 lines and a horizontal resolution of 0.2°/0.4° and Vertical resolution of 2.81°. While the reconstructed environment could be kind of poor with a single still measurement, the robot movement combined with 576000 pts/second provide dense pointclouds that can be used

Figure 54. Maps generated in pcd format.

In the images we can see a raw pointcloud (white coloured) of roughly 1.5 million points, that was later on treated and optimized in order to have around 700k points (green coloured).

Such 3D maps were created by teleoperating the robot in the area and then launching an specific instruction to transform the data. The data was gathered in a 10-15 minutes timespan, while the processing algorithm was taking longer, requiring the robot the same timespan or even longer depending on the parameters given.

Autonomous Navigation

- *The robot is commanded manually to a predefined entry point to the designated and pre-mapped area.*
- *The robot, starting from the base station, autonomously navigates to a pre-specified location through a set of waypoints while avoiding obstacles.*

For the autonomous navigation tests, it was required to have successfully created the map in the previous test. Multiple maps were generated in order to better address some of the terrain features that allegedly could impede a smooth navigation. This is specially true for the “containment” steps all around the decom zone.

After some tests, the robot was able to recognize the steps and proposed routes following existing accesses through ramps.

Figure 55. RISING robot running autonomous navigation.

Given the boost in the agility of the robot, an alternate strategy was identified, so that the robot could be specified an entry point, right in front of the obstacle (containment step) and commanded to execute a routine in order to overcome it (by moving the flippers). This was tested in a teleoperated fashion as well, but improvements can be made in this direction.

Inspection

- An inspection plan created and downloaded to the robot can be executed together with the autonomous navigation system.
- At the end of the inspection plan, the robot returns autonomously to the base station.
- All relevant sensing (images, thermal, audio) is recorded, and associated with a location and a timestamp.
- Time is automatically tracked in the mission data. From this data cost savings and other information required for PGM-KPI-B-01 and PGM-KPI-B-02 can be directly derived.

Once the map was tuned and uploaded to the portal, different missions and inspection points were issued within the PILOTING portal.

Figure 56. Ground inspection portal site.

With the gRCS instance launched in the Robot and local ground control (in a dedicated laptop) the robot was able to perform such missions, mainly consisting on navigating to a point and then gathering data by moving the PTZ mechanism and recording pictures (in the thermal and visible spectrum).

Figure 57. GRCS RISING interface.

The data is recorded in a dedicated folder following the defined structured readable by DMS. Then, each inspection folder has an associated telemetry (recording the robot movement in the map), and different inspection devices with the media and the data of where those were recorded.

Figure 58. RISING mission folder structure.

Some highlights after mission are:

- Selecting inspection points within the portal can be hard if the pcl is not clean enough. Color can help to understand the pcl and have a mental image of the area to inspect.

- A different working flow could be taken into account; if a first teleoperated mission is done, the points of interest can be recorded easily. An easy process should be to load the POI directly into the portal with prior information.
- An added value considered during the test was to check whether pictures of certain assets can be made in different missions, at different times and still be able to compare both. Not only the robot navigation precision but also the field of view and positioning of sensors must be addressed here. An example of two different mission pictures is presented in the next figures

Figure 59. FLIR Imagery captured during ground inspection.

Stair climbing

- Robot is teleoperated in a certain environment where the traction system of the robot allows the vehicle to overcome different surfaces and stairs.
- A waypoint can be recorded associated with an stair climbing feature so that the robot can travel to the point and then activate an autonomous feature of climbing the stairs in a pre-recorded manner.

Figure 60. RISING robot attempting stair climb.

The stair climbing feature is one of the most challenging feature targeted by the RISING V2 modifications. There is also a direct link with a number of constraints that have been present through the project itself.

- Robot dimension come defined by the initial presence of a bigger battery and the allocation of a robotic arm (Kinova GEN3 robot) which at the moment of the pilots are not being used.
 - o The closest iteration of the robot served to mount a different battery that can be easily extracted and maintained.
 - o The arm selection issue has been already discussed. Kinova arm does not fit the force and robustness requirement in order to operate hand levers as per previous tests
- The existent chassis of the robot cannot be modified at the moment, and with this the weight distribution.
- Although flipper adaptation was convenient (gaining considerable clearance that helps obstacle overcoming), lifting even more the centre of mass represents a problem in steep stairs.

With these considerations and the result of different tests, it becomes clear that different stair tests with at least 37° are difficult to succeed.

Rising robot overcame steps up to the point where the operation was aborted due to the risk of damaging the robot and/or compromise the safety rules.

The conclusion is that there is room for improvement, making the solution more robust. The strategy and modifications needed are still being discussed.

Figure 61. RISING robot on an alternative stairwell.

UGV

Figure 62. UGV running autonomous navigation in the decommissioned module.

Figure 63. UGV autonomously manipulating a hand wheel valve.

Figure 64. UGV laptop display showing valve handwheel detection prior to manipulation.

The validation of the developed autonomous functionalities for the UGV robotic inspector has been carried out following the planned mapping, navigation and manipulation sessions.

3.5.1. *Mapping session*

The robot navigated the refinery in teleoperation mode while capturing the required data, in this case point clouds from a LiDAR scanner and IMU data, to build a 3D representation of the plant (a map). The map covers a total area of 30 m x 30 m (see Figure 65). However, the inspection was confined to a smaller area of 5 m x 10 m that was the area assigned to this pilot by the refinery plant. The UGV robotic inspector does not have any limitation, apart from 2h battery life time, on the area it can navigate.

Figure 65. 3D map reconstruction of the refinery by teleoperating the UGV.

3.5.2. *Autonomous navigation session*

The robot is then controlled from the ground control station providing target inspection points as waypoints on the previously built map. The robot successfully performed localization and followed autonomously and safely the waypoints while avoiding obstacles that were not present in the prior map (see Figure 62). In more detail, the robot loads the prior map and its traversability mask. The robot continuously localizes in the prior map through point cloud registration. The traversability mask (see Figure 66) is used to perform the global planning towards the next inspection waypoint. To follow the global plan and keep a safe operation, the robot uses a TEB local planner that allows it to safely avoid obstacles that did not appear in the prior map. The local planner is reactive, meaning that dynamic obstacles could also be avoided.

Figure 66. 2D traversability mask computed from the prior 3D map for the specifications of the UGV robot inspector.

3.5.3. Manipulation session

After autonomously navigating to a target inspection point for valve manipulation, the robot detected the asset (see Figure 67), in this case hand-wheel valves in 3D space (see Figure 68), and approached it (see Figure 63). Then, it started the manipulation task (see Figure 63) by turning the valve by a predefined angle set in the inspection plan (see Figure 69). The compliant approach and the adaptive gripper design allowed successful manipulations even under small errors in the 3D pose of the valve. After manipulation completion, the robot autonomously navigated to the final waypoint, the location of a base station.

Figure 67. UGV follows inspection waypoints and detects the target valve.

Figure 68. Typical detections of hand wheel valves in the refinery by the UGV.

Figure 69. UGV manipulating the detected hand-wheel valve by a predetermined angle.

It has been shown that the developed functionalities are robust and deliver reproducible results. The entire mission was repeated more than 5 times. When the valve was not detected or grasped successfully in the first attempt, the robot triggered the functionality again until successful detection and manipulation. Due to the compliance of the system, no damage to the robot nor the asset was caused. The measurement of the force required at the end-effector during the manipulation task was also recorded (see Figure 70).

Figure 70. Force measured at the end-effector during one valve manipulation action.

Finally, a summary of the main mission metrics are shown below.

Key Mission Metrics

- Total robot startup time: 10 min
- Total mission duration: 3 min 45 s
- Total valve detection duration: 1 min
- Number of valve detections before manipulation start: 3
- Valve manipulation duration: 30 s
- Valve turning angle step size: 120°
- Peak exerted absolute end-effector force: 2.9 N
- Replanning for obstacles not in map: successful
- Total data processing and DDHL upload time: 3 min
- Data processing and DDHL upload: successful

3.6. IoT Sensors

3.6.1. Introduction

Based on what was presented in D6.3 (section 7.3.2.1), it has been proved that the adoption of accelerometers for leak detection in pipelines of the refinery is a very promising strategy, even if presents some difficulties due to the nature of the inspected infrastructures. For example, some pipelines are not equipped with the components required to generate leaks and therefore, it is difficult to acquire a large and balanced leak dataset. Among all, the accelerometers in-situ sensors offer a good trade-off between low cost, reliability, and sensitivity and they can easily adapt to a fully automatic IoT system. Thus, accelerometer sensors have been selected as sensors to be used in the design of the IoT solution in the context of Task 6.4 and to be deployed on Chevron's facilities for the inspection of pipelines in refineries. The technical details of the proposed solution and its 1st pilot

demonstration of the two sequential pilot phases of the project (1st start on M32 and the 2nd on M46 of the PILOTING project) are described in the following paragraphs.

In the following sections, the various components comprising the whole IoT solution will be presented among with the application of the proposed solution in the refinery’s pilot case. First of all, after a general description of the proposed IoT solution, the specifications of the indoor and outdoor sensors and the IoT gateway are summarized. In the sequel, the solar power system used for supplying the IoT gateway with the required power is described. Secondly, the installation of the proposed solution in the refinery in order for the 1st pilot demonstration to be conducted is presented. The description includes the exact locations where the indoor and outdoor sensors, the IoT gateway and the solar power system were installed in the water piping system of the refinery, the parameterization of the IoT gateway in order to gather sensors’ measurements and send them to PILOTING I&M platform via the Data Distribution & Harmonisation Layer (DDHL).

3.6.2. *Pilot demonstration: Installation of the IoT Wireless solution*

The installation of the whole wireless sensor network (WSN) along with the supplementary solar power system that contributes to the power autonomy of the whole system was implemented in the Green water piping area inside the Oronite plant. More information regarding the hardware and software specifications that comprise the whole system will be given in the upcoming deliverable “D6.7-I&M data management system and IoT connectivity (2nd version)”.

Table 29. Description of work area for installation of the IoT Wireless solution

Plant / Area Description	
Plant	Oronite additives plant in Gonfreville, France.
Experiment Area	Water processing facility - Along Green water piping.

Both the indoor and outdoor vibration sensors were installed on water pipes in the Refinery on 13/09/2022, according to the detailed schedule that was defined prior to the pilot demonstration activities, and in collaboration with the pilot partner. It took about 2 hours to install everything and test the connectivity between the sensors and the gateway. The installation procedure included the attachment of (i) the sensors on the pipes, (ii) the solar panel, (iii) the box that contains the gateway, and finally connecting the box and the panel with a power wire.

Locations where bends and branches were preferred due to increased vibrations in these areas. The sensors are mounted securely with magnets. The images below illustrate the two different sensor types (i.e., indoor and outdoor) that were installed at the refinery.

Figure 71. Installation of indoor (a,b,e) and outdoor (c,d) sensors in refinery's pipelines.

Table below summarizes the main characteristics of the five sensors installed in the refinery.

Table 30. Summary of the main characteristics of the five sensors installed in the refinery.

Static Data	Description	Sensor 1	Sensor 2	Sensor 3	Sensor 4	Sensor 5
Unique identifier	The identifier of the sensor.	a3bb0bc5-c449-41be-bale-	fceb084d-603d-433d-8f92-	cc6d68f6-c35b-40d1-a8ae-	5845f4a3-df8f-4165-9c46-	04b6feec-2dbf-41f4-b8c1-

		7634acf4369e	9e0d3de8b304	295a558f56ef	daa6fc49cb8e	e76883e79690
name	The name of the sensor.	Vibration	Vibration	Vibration	Vibration	Vibration
type	The type of the sensor.	accelerometer (indoor)	accelerometer (indoor)	accelerometer (indoor)	accelerometer (outdoor)	accelerometer (outdoor)
address or sequence number	The mac address or the sequence number of the sensor	00:13:a2:00:41:e3:4d:de	00:13:A2:00:41:E2:35:51	00:13:A2:00:41:E3:2C:46	00:13:A2:00:41:E3:3A:22	00:13:A2:00:41:E3:2F:52
location of the sensor	The point where the sensor is installed.	49.49661,0.21250	49.49654,0.21248	49.49659,0.21250	49.49674,0.21227	49.49658,0.21252
frequency	Sampling rate of the sensor	300 sec				

Sensors communicate with a wireless gateway at sub-gigahertz frequencies. The gateway is placed in a waterproof case with a battery to provide the necessary power for the gateway to operate for approximately 60 hours. The battery is being charged with a 25W solar panel that is placed on a high point in the refinery.

Figure 72. Solar power system location.

The particular design of the data flow for the connection of the sensors with the IoT Gateway was implemented utilizing prior to the interconnection of the WSNs with the IoT Gateway. Such activity was fulfilled with a configuration of the IoT Gateway, a process that was facilitated with the pre-installed NODE-RED software. With more details, the gateway was configured to acquire data from each sensor every 5 minutes and send them to the MQTT server. As shown in the figure below, the msg.data are delivered to the backend in the desired JSON format.

Figure 73. Flow design in node-red.

The sensors produce data and then they are passed to a function that selects the desired format to be sent to MQTT. The purple node contains the information required for the connection with the MQTT server (IP, port, topic). The two bottom nodes are there for debugging the gateway, the green node outputs any messages from the gateway to the debug window in node-red. Finally, the wireless gateway is equipped with the Hologram 4G/LTE IoT, Global coverage, connectivity card that ensures the remote connection of the IoT solution. So far, the consumed data that are required for the data transmission is depicted in the figure below.

Figure 74. Data consumption ensuring wireless communication and data transmission.

Following iterative technical alignments with the IoT platform, the IVP has implemented the communication, adapter, and translation layers between the IVP server and the SensorThings API. This allows the IVP to retrieve the static sensor information from the SensorThings database and associate the collected data to the asset representation stored in the DMS. A first result is shown in Figure 75, where the observations and datastreams from the accelerometers installed at Chevron Oronite are visualized. The timeseries graph draws the root mean square values of the vibrational acceleration (measured in G) along each measurement axis and for a live period of approximately 10 days, at a frequency of 1 observation every 5 minutes. In addition, users can also view descriptions about the selected datastream, the related observed property, and the sensor information including a picture of installation site and a link to the manual documentation.

Figure 75. Visualization of the static sensor installed at Chevron Oronite from the IVP.

3.7. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – Data transmission, transformation and storing

3.7.1. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – AEROX

The DDHL as part of the I&M PILOTING platform is responsible to obtain the Mission Specific Data originating from the AeroX robotic system and upload it to the DMS.

Over the week spent at the Chevron’s Oronite plant, and from the successfully complete missions developed by AEROX, next it is shown an example of the mission specific data that was successfully uploaded to the DMS through the DDHL. Seen below are the unique identifiers of the objects created on the DMS regarding the Inspection Plans, the Missions, and the Mission Tasks.

Table 31. DMS Information regarding an AeroX Mission.

Inspection Plan	Mission	Mission Task	SyncID
0bb40ec4-1cfa-4f77-9d4e-9cac49b68969	007b86e7-8350-432b-94ee-d8146f4743d3	0a5e3aed-44c7-4460-b09e-1e5f8c1a4bcc	1799026144

Figure 76. Workflow diagram – Post Mission Data (AeroX).

As described in Section 2.2.3, the gRCS communicates with the DDHL prior to the execution of the Mission to instantiate the Mission and the Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and post the generic data to the DMS.

Progressing, the AeroX robotic system uploads the mission specific data (Table 32) to the DDHL enclosed in a compressed folder. The DDHL is responsible to unzip the folder, transform and post the data under the right Mission by utilizing the APIs of the DMS., as illustrated in Figure 76. In order to find the Mission created by the gRCS and to correlate the data with, the DDHL uses the SyncID property included in the mRCS data. As seen in Section 2.2.3, SyncID is a property included in both generic and mission specific data towards the synchronization of the data.

In case of failure, the DDHL will roll back the changes that have been made to the database and eventually inform the AeroX robot about the failure.

Table 32. Mission Specific Data provided by AeroX robot.

File Type	Description	Example Data Format
Config_file.json	The file contains the parameters of all the submissions generated. It provides information on the initial and final position, the UUIDs, the time and the SyncID.	<pre> 1 { 2 "startDate": "2022_02_20-12_50_12", 3 "endDate": "2022_02_21-12_56_50", 4 "uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", 5 "syncId": 8800, 6 "inspectionPlanUuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", 7 "data": [8 { 9 "timestamp": "2022-05-13 15:22:39", 10 "inspectionTaskUuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", 11 "attachment": "XXX.cscan.tsv", 12 "initialPosition": { 13 "x": 0.627707287528727, 14 "y": 1.093265669039484, 15 "z": 1.109273297614398 16 }, 17 "finalPosition": { 18 "x": 0.627707287528727, 19 "y": 1.093265669039484, 20 "z": 6.313613297614397 21 } 22 } 23] 24 } </pre>
Scan_X.tsv	The file provides depth measurement data of the inspection task X (where X corresponds to the corresponding inspection task UUID) defined in the inspection plan.	<pre> 1 Scan Thickness [mm] Image from channel:Ch:1 , generated from EuroscanV at 2022/02/15_09:19 2 X Axis = ScanScale = column start=0 end=40 step=0.1 3 Y Axis = IndexScale = line start=0 end=1 step=1 4 52.0783 5 47.778 6 50.4488 7 50.0006 8 49.2438 9 50.4043 10 49.2061 11 50.8598 </pre>

Seen below are indicative screenshots originating by the DDHL logs that capture the communication between the mRCS (AeroX), the DDHL and the DMS modules regarding the implementation of the Inspection Plan.

Table 33. Indicative screenshots from DDHL Logs.

<p>Inspection Plan UUID: 0bb40ec4-1cfa-4f77-9d4e-9cac49b68969</p>	<p>Mission UUID: 007b86e7-8350-432b-94ee-d8146f4743d3</p>
<p>Figure 77. gRCS fetches the Inspection Plan.</p>	
<p>Figure 78. gRCS uploads the generic data to the DMS through the DDHL.</p>	
<p>Figure 79. AeroX uploads the mission specific data to the DMS through the DDHL.</p>	

As described, the DDHL succeeded in instantiating both the Mission and the Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and uploading both the generic and the mission specific data to the DMS concerning the AeroX case.

3.7.2. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – HYBRID & SATELITE

The DDHL as part of the I&M PILOTING platform is responsible to obtain the Mission Specific Data originating from the HYBRID robotic system and upload it to the DMS. Taking into account that the integration of the DDHL with both HYBRID and SATELITE robotic systems is in progress, the mission specific data will be uploaded to the DMS the following period. Thus, this part of the document will be analysed in the next version. Anyway, it is important to point out that the interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform will be very similar to AEROX and BIKE (which are already completed and verified). Then, it is not expected much work to complete this integration.

3.7.3. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – BIKE

The DDHL as part of the I&M PILOTING platform is responsible to obtain the Mission Specific Data originating from the BIKE robotic system and upload it to the DMS.

Regarding the Refinery Pressure Vessel Inspection, and from the BIKE robot successfully performed missions, it will be shown an example of the Mission specific data that was successfully uploaded to the DMS through the DDHL. Seen below are the unique identifiers of the objects created on the DMS regarding the Inspection Plans, the Missions, and the Mission Tasks.

Table 34. DMS Information regarding BIKE Mission.

Inspection Plan	Mission	Mission Tasks	SyncID
b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad	e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132	ed4386e6-0a49-41e4-979d-844f1ddd8eb3	1979522218

Table 35. Mission Specific Data provided by the BIKE robot.

File Type	Description	Example Data Format
Capture folders	Each folder contains all the capture's data.	
Config File	The file provides general information such as SyncID, Inspection Plan UUID and Inspection Dates. Moreover, it provides the data for all the captures. Each capture may contain images, UT measurements or attachments.	<pre> { "Mission": { "Asset ID": "", "Asset Location": "", "Asset Type": "", "Customer Name": "", "Customer Address": "", "Inspection Start Date": "2022-09-14", "Inspection End Date": "2022-09-14", "Company Name": "", "Company Address": "", "Inspectors": "", "Equipment": "", "SW Version": "0.0.0.1", "Mission DB": "b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad_4.mission_db", "Sync ID": 1979522218, "Inspection Plan UUID": "b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad" }, "Captures": [{ "Capture": 1, "Robot": "Bike", "Inspection Task UUID": "0abf17b0-b38f-452f-868a-11242e2d8717", "Capture Type": "Cameras", "Capture Title": "", "Capture in Report": true, "AScans in Report": true, "Capture Location": "", "Capture Description": "", "Capture Recommendation": "", "Mission Time": "01:03:14", "System Time": "2022-09-14 14:28:34", "Robot x [m]": -1.599518347940567, "Robot y [m]": 0.399285860588823, "Robot z [m]": 0.3626933603769689, "Robot Quaternion real": 0.72468426651797514, "Robot Quaternion i": 0.7697245678726648, "Robot Quaternion j": -0.5884374180322982, "Robot Quaternion k": 0.12154990219924977, "Robot Forward Vector x [m]": 0.385899848954647, "Robot Forward Vector y [m]": -0.7537388203619458, "Robot Forward Vector z [m]": 0.3816309947809897, "Robot Left Vector x [m]": -0.9516159961106364, "Robot Left Vector y [m]": -0.223324467298117, "Robot Left Vector z [m]": 0.2187023748166936, "Robot Euler Angle Z [deg]": -1.757658224419216, "Robot Euler Angle X [deg]": 107.81226317787912, }] } </pre>

Figure 80. Workflow diagram – Post Mission Data (BIKE).

As described in Section 2.2.3, the gRCS communicates with the DDHL prior to the execution of the Mission to instantiate the Mission and the Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and post the generic data to the DMS.

Progressing, the BIKE robotic system uploads the mission specific data (Table 35) to the DDHL enclosed in a compressed folder. The DDHL is responsible to unzip the folder, transform and post the data under the right Mission by utilizing the APIs of the DMS., as illustrated in Figure 80. In order to find the Mission created by the gRCS and to correlate the data with, the DDHL uses the SyncID property included in the mRCS data. As seen in Section 2.2.3, SyncID is a property included in both generic and mission specific data towards the synchronization of the data.

In case of failure, the DDHL will roll back the changes that have been made to the database and eventually inform the BIKE robot about the failure

Seen below are indicative screenshots originating by the DDHL logs that capture the communication between the mRCS (BIKE), the DDHL and the DMS modules regarding the implementation of the Inspection Plan.

Table 36. Indicative screenshots from DDHL Logs.

Inspection Plan UID: b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad

Mission UID: e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132

```
2022-09-12 14:15:02,734,734,dahl,common,INFO,Get Full Inspection Plan commonView.py:62
2022-09-12 14:15:02,735,735,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionPlan/b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad/ALL/ dms.py 24
2022-09-12 14:15:02,735,735,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionPlan/b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad/ALL/ dms.py 24
2022-09-12 14:15:03,078,78,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/0bf17b8-b30f-452f-868a-11242e2d8717/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:03,078,78,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/0bf17b8-b30f-452f-868a-11242e2d8717/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:03,319,319,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:03,319,319,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:03,530,530,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:03,530,530,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:03,745,745,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:03,745,745,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:03,954,954,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/25a77dcb-3acb-4604-a63e-630c2449730b/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:03,954,954,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/25a77dcb-3acb-4604-a63e-630c2449730b/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:04,213,213,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:04,213,213,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:04,425,425,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:04,425,425,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:04,635,635,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:04,635,635,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:04,864,864,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/93555d87-784e-4b27-bda6-6378d16134ff/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:04,864,864,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/93555d87-784e-4b27-bda6-6378d16134ff/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:05,152,152,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:05,152,152,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:05,364,364,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:05,364,364,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:05,579,579,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:05,579,579,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:05,797,797,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/0f0d2b2f-391f-4c47-a659-7021d01a983/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:05,797,797,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/0f0d2b2f-391f-4c47-a659-7021d01a983/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:06,60,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:06,60,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:06,271,271,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:06,271,271,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:06,498,498,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:06,498,498,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:06,709,709,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/672622f-d097-431f-b42e-f3459242650a/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:06,709,709,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/672622f-d097-431f-b42e-f3459242650a/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:06,941,941,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:06,941,941,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:07,149,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:07,149,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:07,355,355,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:07,355,355,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:07,562,562,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/879358e-8ccc-4bc5-b6d4-868480ff0a/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:07,562,562,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/879358e-8ccc-4bc5-b6d4-868480ff0a/ALL/ dms.py 71
2022-09-12 14:15:07,813,813,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:07,813,813,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:07,813,813,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:07,813,813,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/d031f24-841b-49cd-a1d2-67e53254bbcd/ dms.py 57
2022-09-12 14:15:08,028,28,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Payload/0cf2e245-cbd2-45fb-91f1-53423000dfas/ dms.py 57
```

Figure 81. gRCS fetches the Inspection Plan.

```
2022-09-12 08:04:59,314,dahl,gRCS,INFO,Post Generic Data gRCSView.py:18
2022-09-12 08:04:59,325,325,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Mission By SyncID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Mission/Properties/67b2225ncld2263AK20197522218X70 dms.py 77
2022-09-12 08:04:59,325,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Mission By SyncID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Mission/Properties/67b2225ncld2263AK20197522218X70 dms.py 77
2022-09-12 08:04:59,623,623,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionPlan/b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad/ALL/ dms.py 24
2022-09-12 08:04:59,623,623,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionPlan/b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad/ALL/ dms.py 24
2022-09-12 08:04:59,966,966,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post Mission - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Mission - Body: {'Name': 'mission_20220914142337', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-09-14T14:23:37.222', 'Properties': {'SyncID': 'b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad'}} dms.py 91
2022-09-12 08:04:59,966,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post Mission - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/Mission - Body: {'Name': 'mission_20220914142337', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-09-14T14:23:37.222', 'Properties': {'SyncID': 'b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad'}} dms.py 91
2022-09-12 08:05:00,216,216,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Inspection Type By Inspection Task ID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/0bf17b8-b30f-452f-868a-11242e2d8717/InspectionType/ dms.py 173
2022-09-12 08:05:00,216,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Get Inspection Type By Inspection Task ID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/InspectionTask/0bf17b8-b30f-452f-868a-11242e2d8717/InspectionType/ dms.py 173
2022-09-12 08:05:00,439,439,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post Mission Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/MissionTask - Body: {'Name': 'mission_task_0', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-09-14T14:25:21.310', 'InspectionTask': '0bf17b8-b30f-452f-868a-11242e2d8717', 'InspectionType': '5b168646-7f3a-4d07-8f19-267e382f8e07', 'Mission': 'e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132'} dms.py 119
2022-09-12 08:05:00,439,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post Mission Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/MissionTask - Body: {'Name': 'mission_task_0', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-09-14T14:25:21.310', 'InspectionTask': '0bf17b8-b30f-452f-868a-11242e2d8717', 'InspectionType': '5b168646-7f3a-4d07-8f19-267e382f8e07', 'Mission': 'e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132'} dms.py 119
2022-09-12 08:05:00,680,680,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/File - Body: {'TempFiles/S4e28641-3905-47cd-975c-51154e730a3b/event_log.csv.dms.py 126
2022-09-12 08:05:00,680,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/File - Body: {'TempFiles/S4e28641-3905-47cd-975c-51154e730a3b/event_log.csv.dms.py 126
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2022-09-12 08:05:01,232,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/File - Body: {'TempFiles/S4e28641-3905-47cd-975c-51154e730a3b/path_followed.csv.dms.py 126
2022-09-12 08:05:01,700,700,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/FileMetadata - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/File/d6d31330-e142-4ec7-bf00-c6e0bd2567e0', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '31691', 'OriginalName': 'path_followed.csv', 'Content': 'gRCS - path_followed', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-10-26T08:05:01Z', 'object_id': 'e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132', 'contentType': '7'} dms.py 161
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2022-09-12 08:05:02,225,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/File - Body: {'TempFiles/S4e28641-3905-47cd-975c-51154e730a3b/planned_trajectory.csv.dms.py 126
2022-09-12 08:05:02,225,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/FileMetadata - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/File/3d0d8d95-5feb-4791-b2bd-275204734f1f', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '930', 'OriginalName': 'planned_trajectory.csv', 'Content': 'gRCS - planned_trajectory', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-10-26T08:05:02Z', 'object_id': 'e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132', 'contentType': '7'} dms.py 161
2022-09-12 08:05:02,225,dahl,dms,INFO,DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/FileMetadata - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/aps/File/3d0d8d95-5feb-4791-b2bd-275204734f1f', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '930', 'OriginalName': 'planned_trajectory.csv', 'Content': 'gRCS - planned_trajectory', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-10-26T08:05:02Z', 'object_id': 'e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132', 'contentType': '7'} dms.py 161
2022-09-12 08:05:02,518,518,dahl,gRCS,INFO,Success Response: {'mission': 'e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132', 'missionTasks': ['e64386e-0a49-41e4-979d-844f1d8d8b3'], 'files': ['49b5b74f-bd28-4f0b-b4ea-afaf77f36ae', 'd6d31330-e142-4ec7-bf00-c6e0bd2567e0', '3d0d8d95-5feb-4791-b2bd-275204734f1f'], 'fileMetadata': {'7005490-b392-4c7d-88ef-24d1e6cddf0', 'f0b99250-5d45-414c-b5cc-c5d1a2b1f7', 'e6c0b9e7-51c6-499a-87a8-dc3d-fede974'} gRCSView.py:28
2022-09-12 08:05:02,518,dahl,gRCS,INFO,Success Response: {'mission': 'e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132', 'missionTasks': ['e64386e-0a49-41e4-979d-844f1d8d8b3'], 'files': ['49b5b74f-bd28-4f0b-b4ea-afaf77f36ae', 'd6d31330-e142-4ec7-bf00-c6e0bd2567e0', '3d0d8d95-5feb-4791-b2bd-275204734f1f'], 'fileMetadata': {'7005490-b392-4c7d-88ef-24d1e6cddf0', 'f0b99250-5d45-414c-b5cc-c5d1a2b1f7', 'e6c0b9e7-51c6-499a-87a8-dc3d-fede974'} gRCSView.py:28
```

Figure 82. gRCS uploads the generic data to the DMS through the DDHL.

Figure 83. BIKE uploads the mission specific data to the DMS through the DDHL.

As described, the DDHL succeeded in instantiating both Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and uploading both the generic and the mission specific data to the DMS concerning the BIKE case.

3.7.4. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – RISING

The DDHL as part of the I&M PILOTING platform is responsible to obtain the Mission Specific Data originated by the RISING robotic system and upload it to the DMS. Although the mission was executed successfully, the integration of the DDHL with the RISING robotic system is still in progress. As a result, the mission specific data will be uploaded to the DMS the following period. Thus, this part of the document will be analysed in the next version.

3.7.5. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – UGV (ETHZ)

The DDHL as part of the I&M PILOTING platform is responsible to obtain the Mission Specific Data originating from the UGV (ETHZ) robotic system and upload it to the DMS.

Regarding the Refinery Ground Monitoring, and from the UGV (ETHZ) robot successfully performed complete missions, it is shown an example of the Mission specific data that was successfully uploaded to the DMS through the DDHL. Below you can find the unique identifiers of the objects created on the DMS regarding the Inspection Plans, the Missions, and the Mission Tasks.

Table 37. DMS Information regarding UGV (ETHZ) Mission.

Inspection Plan	Mission	Mission Tasks	SyncID
de06400d-323a-4ebb-9459-131cd140a23f	001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d	aaa0123b-05bc-485e-83e3-885501476498	1630552392

Figure 84. Workflow diagram – Post Mission Data (UGV - ETHZ).

As described in Section 2.2.3, the gRCS communicates with the DDHL prior to the execution of the Mission to instantiate both Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and post the generic data to the DMS. Progressing, the UGV (ETHZ) robotic system uploads the mission specific data (Table 38) to the DDHL enclosed in a compressed folder. The DDHL is responsible to unzip the folder, transform and post the data under the right Mission by utilizing the APIs of the DMS., as illustrated in Figure 84. In order to find the Mission created by the gRCS and to correlate the data with, the DDHL uses the SyncID property included in the mRCS data. As seen in Section 2.2.3, SyncID is a property included in both generic and mission specific data towards the synchronization of the data. In case of failure, the DDHL will roll back the changes that have been made to the database and eventually inform the UGV (ETHZ) about the failure.

Table 38. Mission Specific Data provided by UGV (ETHZ) robot.

File Type	Description	Example of Data Format
Haptic data	Measurement stamp, torque measurements expressed in the estimated rotation axis of the valve during manipulation.	timestamp, task_uuid, obj_ref_id, angle, torque
Config File	Configuration file with the sensor configuration of the robotic platform. This file provides the sensor list and the physical offset between them as well as inspection information (eg: Inspection Plan UUID)	<pre> { "startDate": "2022_05_10-14_55_39", "endDate": "2022_05_10-15_00_32", "syncId": 9500, "uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionPlanUuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionTaskUuids": ["XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX"], "type": "visual", "map": "map.pcd", "files": { "config": "config.json", "pictures_metadata": "pictures_metadata.csv", "pictures_folder": "pictures", "telemetry_data": "localization_telemetry.csv", "haptic_data": "haptic_sensing.csv", "objects": "objects.csv" }, "pictures": { "folder": "pictures", "sensor_uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "format": "jpg", "size": { "width": 1280, "height": 720 }, "fov": { "horizontal": 69.0, "vertical": 42.0 } } } </pre>
localization_telemetry.csv	Localization stamp and pose from the fusion sensor solution without GPS information. Origin referred to the refinery 3D model	timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w
objects.csv	Objects found during Inspection	timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, obj_ref_id, obj_type, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w, rotation_axis_x, rotation_axis_y, rotation_axis_z, opening_angle, obj_info_1, obj_info_2
Pictures folder	Individual files in a specific folder	
pictures_metadata.csv	Metadata for each image captured.	file_name, timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, cam_pos [3], cam_rot[4]

Seen below are indicative screenshots originating by the DDHL logs that capture the communication between the mRCS (UGV - ETHZ), the DDHL and the DMS modules regarding the implementation of the Inspection Plan.

Table 39. Indicative screenshots from DDHL Logs.

Inspection Plan UUID: de06400d-323a-4ebb-9459-131cd140a23f	Mission UUID: 001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d
---	---

```

09:03:32,223 ddhl.common INFO Get Full Inspection Plan commonView.py 62
2022-09-14 09:03:32,223,223 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionPlan/de06400d-323a-4ebb-9459-131cd140a23f/All/ dms.py 24
09:03:32,223 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionPlan/de06400d-323a-4ebb-9459-131cd140a23f/All/ dms.py 24
2022-09-14 09:03:32,460,460 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionTask/7f161aid-1db4-4d66-8a8f-9afdcdfb3c3/All/ dms.py 71
09:03:32,460 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionTask/7f161aid-1db4-4d66-8a8f-9afdcdfb3c3/All/ dms.py 71
2022-09-14 09:03:32,696,696 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Payload/bd490b1e-c3bc-4b92-af51-abce68ab1352/ dms.py 57
09:03:32,696 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Payload/bd490b1e-c3bc-4b92-af51-abce68ab1352/ dms.py 57
    
```

Figure 85. gRCS fetches the Inspection Plan.

```

14:10:25,145 ddhl.gRCS INFO Post Generic data gRCSView.py 14
18:10:25,154 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Mission By SyncID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/7Properties-67B822Syncldr223kAK20163052320270 dms.py 77
18:10:25,414 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionPlan/de06400d-323a-4ebb-9459-131cd140a23f/All/ dms.py 24
18:10:25,666 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post Mission - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/ - Body: {"Name": "mission_20220915075909", "ExecutionDate": "2022-09-15T07:59:09.700", "Properties": {"SyncID": 130552322}}
18:10:25,905 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Type By Inspection Task ID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionTask/23a0951e-3324-4a5b-b27c-7bc6137f1380/InspectionType/ dms.py 173
18:10:26,133 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post Mission Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/MissionTask/ - Body: {"Name": "mission_task_0", "ExecutionDate": "2022-09-15T07:59:52.074", "InspectionTask": "23a0951e-3324-4a5b-b27c-7bc6137f1380", "InspectionType": "5b186846-773a-44b7-8f19-2676382f8ea7", "Mission": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d"} dms.py 119
18:10:26,411 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {"/TempFiles/58333b23-e4c4-4f7e-8e57-5745dee103d8/event_log.csv dms.py 126
18:10:26,657 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {"URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/58333b23-e4c4-4f7e-8e57-5745dee103d8/event_log.csv", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "1280", "OriginalName": "path_followed.csv", "Content": "gRCS_path_followed", "CreationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:27", "object_id": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d", "content_type": "7"} dms.py 161
18:10:26,896 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {"/TempFiles/58333b23-e4c4-4f7e-8e57-5745dee103d8/path_followed.csv dms.py 126
18:10:27,201 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {"URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/3d0f0936-4030-4106-9405-25f64d60bc35/", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "44074", "OriginalName": "path_followed.csv", "Content": "gRCS_path_followed", "CreationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:27", "object_id": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d", "content_type": "7"} dms.py 161
18:10:27,464 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {"/TempFiles/58333b23-e4c4-4f7e-8e57-5745dee103d8/planned_trajectory.csv dms.py 126
18:10:27,696 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {"URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/54b06f06-04e5-4153-949c-147ef9f66b/", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "368", "OriginalName": "planned_trajectory.csv", "Content": "gRCS_planned_trajectory", "CreationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:27", "object_id": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d", "content_type": "7"} dms.py 161
18:10:27,921 ddhl.gRCS INFO Success Response: {"mission": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d", "missionTasks": [{"missionTask": "00a0123b-05bc-485e-83e3-885501476498"}], "files": [{"file": "58333b23-e4c4-4f7e-8e57-5745dee103d8/event_log.csv", "mimeType": "text/csv", "size": "1280", "originalName": "event_log.csv", "content": "gRCS_event_log", "creationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:26", "object_id": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d"}, {"file": "58333b23-e4c4-4f7e-8e57-5745dee103d8/path_followed.csv", "mimeType": "text/csv", "size": "1280", "originalName": "path_followed.csv", "content": "gRCS_path_followed", "creationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:27", "object_id": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d"}, {"file": "3d0f0936-4030-4106-9405-25f64d60bc35", "mimeType": "text/csv", "size": "44074", "originalName": "path_followed.csv", "content": "gRCS_path_followed", "creationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:27", "object_id": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d"}, {"file": "54b06f06-04e5-4153-949c-147ef9f66b", "mimeType": "text/csv", "size": "368", "originalName": "planned_trajectory.csv", "content": "gRCS_planned_trajectory", "creationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:27", "object_id": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d"}, {"file": "00a0123b-05bc-485e-83e3-885501476498", "mimeType": "application/json", "size": "219", "originalName": "mission_task_0.json", "content": "mission_task_0", "creationDate": "2022-09-15T07:59:52.074", "object_id": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d"}]}
    
```

Figure 86. gRCS uploads the generic data to the DMS through the DDHL.

```

18:10:57,368 ddhl.mRCS INFO Start - Post Mission Specific Data /apis/Mission/mRCS/ETHZ mRCSView.py 31
18:10:57,361 ddhl.mRCS INFO User: julian.keller mRCSView.py 32
18:10:57,428 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Mission By SyncID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/7Properties-67B822Syncldr223kAK20163052320270 dms.py 77
18:10:57,652 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Mission By Mission Task ID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d/MissionTask/ dms.py 84
18:10:57,879 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {"/TempFiles/0e2651-1a18-4bc3-b459-bfe5d90e11a/realSense.jpg dms.py 126
18:10:58,266 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {"URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/0e2651-1a18-4bc3-b459-bfe5d90e11a/realSense.jpg", "MimeType": "image/jpeg", "Size": "136721", "OriginalName": "DSC000000.jpg", "Content": "mRCS - Image", "CreationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:58", "Properties": {"ImageMetadata": {"Timestamp": "2022-09-15T08:00:46", "p.x": 4.18708651429566, "p.y": -2.7362737494294463, "p.z": 1.443136782120156, "d.x": -0.3455609878163747, "d.y": 0.407336431613982, "d.z": 0.5362289464106683, "a.w": 0.6535465775542795, "obj_ref_id": "None", "Size": 136721, "Width": 1280, "Height": 720, "Fov": {"Horizontal": 69.0, "Vertical": 42.0}}, "object_id": "aa0a123b-05bc-485e-83e3-885501476498", "content_type": "12"} dms.py 161
18:10:58,499 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {"/TempFiles/0e2651-1a18-4bc3-b459-bfe5d90e11a/realSense.jpg dms.py 126
18:10:58,876 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {"URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/111059161f1-1b04-4196-ef3-3e0a06e6d5d3/", "MimeType": "image/jpeg", "Size": "150789", "OriginalName": "DSC000001.jpg", "Content": "mRCS - Image", "CreationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:58", "Properties": {"ImageMetadata": {"Timestamp": "2022-09-15T08:02:38", "p.x": -0.233156496183656, "p.y": -1.244252468149285, "p.z": 1.256860154643878, "d.x": -0.8214959883193452, "d.y": 0.827935410158062, "d.z": 0.4790660944103617, "a.w": 0.383404998653091, "obj_ref_id": "1", "Size": 150789, "Width": 1280, "Height": 720, "Fov": {"Horizontal": 69.0, "Vertical": 42.0}}, "object_id": "aa0a123b-05bc-485e-83e3-885501476498", "content_type": "12"} dms.py 161
18:10:59,398 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {"/TempFiles/0e2651-1a18-4bc3-b459-bfe5d90e11a/localization_telemetry_0a0123b.csv dms.py 126
18:10:59,942 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {"URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/8302f505-e854-411a-9e58-ef69c956a237/", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "1628150", "OriginalName": "localization_telemetry_0a0123b.csv", "Content": "mRCS - localization_telemetry", "CreationDate": "2022-09-15T08:10:59", "object_id": "aa0a123b-05bc-485e-83e3-885501476498", "content_type": "12"} dms.py 161
18:11:00,200 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {"/TempFiles/0e2651-1a18-4bc3-b459-bfe5d90e11a/object_data_0a0123b.csv dms.py 126
18:11:00,548 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {"URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/8f21e608-ef4f-4731-ef93-fc6d453088d4/", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "91738", "OriginalName": "object_data_0a0123b.csv", "Content": "mRCS - object_data", "CreationDate": "2022-09-15T08:11:00", "object_id": "aa0a123b-05bc-485e-83e3-885501476498", "content_type": "12"} dms.py 161
18:11:00,824 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {"/TempFiles/0e2651-1a18-4bc3-b459-bfe5d90e11a/objects_found_0a0123b.csv dms.py 126
18:11:01,81 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {"URL": "https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/8302f505-e854-411a-9e58-ef69c956a237/", "MimeType": "text/csv", "Size": "1377", "OriginalName": "objects_found_0a0123b.csv", "Content": "mRCS - objects_found", "CreationDate": "2022-09-15T08:11:01", "object_id": "aa0a123b-05bc-485e-83e3-885501476498", "content_type": "12"} dms.py 161
18:11:01,319 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Patch Mission - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/ - Body: {"UniqueID": "001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d", "ExecutionDate": "2022-09-15T10:00:00", "Properties": {"SyncID": 163052392, "Completed": true, "Sensors": [{"uid": "148ddfc-d28-4d33-b85b-d3dcd4e588a", "Name": "rsldar", "Description": "16 Beams Lidar Sensor", "tf": {"Translation": {"x": 0.245, "y": 0.0, "z": 0.5055000000000001}, "Rotation": {"x": 0.0, "y": 0.0, "z": 0.7071067811865475, "w": 0.7071067811865475}}, {"uid": "d6d312df-70bc-4f84-8d34-77f101e0ebd31", "Name": "realSense_T265", "Description": "RealSense T265 Depth Camera", "tf": {"Translation": {"x": 0.3001000000000001, "y": 0.00129999999999995, "z": 0.3512}, "Rotation": {"x": 0.0, "y": 0.0, "z": 0.0, "w": 1.0}}, {"uid": "4903b6c1-2dfe-4480-83c5-eb949632d91", "Name": "imu", "Description": "XSense Imp", "tf": {"Translation": {"x": 0.2554, "y": 0.82397, "z": 0.1295}, "Rotation": {"x": 0.0, "y": 0.0, "z": 0.0, "w": 1.0}}, {"uid": "47258580-361e-4186-8b0f-29166d64266", "Name": "realSense_d435i", "Description": "RealSense D435i Depth Camera", "tf": {"Translation": {"x": 0.4467016948177946, "y": 0.0498927561941624, "z": 1.0357498529383453}, "Rotation": {"x": 0.03807459717934201, "w": 0.58373516850799, "z": 0.0197637246175958, "a": 0.828479760716052}}, {"Map": "map.pcd"}]} dms.py 98
    
```

Figure 87. UGV (ETHZ) uploads the mission specific data to the DMS through the DDHL.

As described, The DDHL succeeded in instantiating both Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and uploading both the generic and the mission specific data to the DMS concerning the UGV (ETHZ) case.

3.7.6 Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – Refinery wireless sensor network

For delivering the measurement data to the backend, a variety of choices can be used. In our case, the MQTT protocol was used to publish the data in JSON format to a specific topic (Topic name: ICCS_PILOTING_REFINERY). Both the gateway as well as the backend served deployed by DDHL followed the same protocol (i.e., with the first to subscribe dedicated messages approximately every five minutes to the aforementioned topic and the second to act as the backend component (i.e., DDHL), being responsible for storing the sensors’ observations. A sample of the collected data in the standard data format is depicted below both for outdoor and indoor sensors.

Outdoor sensor data
<pre>{</pre>

```
"nodeId":0,
"firmware":4,
"battery":"3.29",
"battery_percent":"99.64",
"counter":107,
"sensor_type":80,
"sensor_data":
{
  "mode":0,
  "odr":"800Hz",
  "temperature":35,
  "x_rms_ACC_G":0,
  "x_max_ACC_G":0,
  "x_velocity_mm_sec":0,
  "x_displacement_mm":0,
  "x_peak_one_Hz":0,
  "x_peak_two_Hz":0,
  "x_peak_three_Hz":0,
  "y_rms_ACC_G":0,
  "y_max_ACC_G":0,
  "y_velocity_mm_sec":0,
  "y_displacement_mm":0,
  "y_peak_one_Hz":0,
  "y_peak_two_Hz":0,
  "y_peak_three_Hz":0,
  "z_rms_ACC_G":0,
  "z_max_ACC_G":0,
  "z_velocity_mm_sec":0,
  "z_displacement_mm":0,
  "z_peak_one_Hz":0,
  "z_peak_two_Hz":0,
  "z_peak_three_Hz":0
},
"sensor_name":"One Channel Vibration Plus",
"type":"sensor_data",
"addr":"00:13:a2:00:41:e3:3a:22",
"received":1662127251610,
"original":
{
  "mac":"00:13:a2:00:41:e3:3a:22",
  "receive_options":
  {
    "ack":0,
    "broadcast":0,
```



```

    "rssi": {},
    "type": "receive_packet"
  },
  "rssi": 80,
  "modem_mac": "00:13:A2:00:41:E2:48:E1"
}

```

Afterward the successful storage of the collected observations, the DDHL is also responsible to consume the data and converted into the standard format of an Observation entity of SensorThingsAPI (see further information in D6.3). This standard format contains the id of the Datastream associated to the corresponding sensor in the database, along with the set of values of a measurement as well as the date and time the measurement was obtained.

The observation is then posted, through an API call, to the SensorThings database and is automatically linked to the correct Datastream, thus the correct corresponding sensor. A sample of the format of the data posted is depicted below, both for outdoor and indoor sensors.

Outdoor sensor data

```

{
  "Datastream":
  {
    "@iot.id": 139
  },
  "resultTime": "2022-10-17T02:05:04.170+00:00",
  "result":
  {
    "mode": 0,
    "odr": "800Hz",
    "temperature": 16.64,
    "x_rms_ACC_G": 0.117,
    "x_max_ACC_G": 0.037,
    "x_velocity_mm_sec": 4.01,
    "x_displacement_mm": 0.02,
    "x_peak_one_Hz": 60,
    "x_peak_two_Hz": 113,
    "x_peak_three_Hz": 238,
    "y_rms_ACC_G": 0,
    "y_max_ACC_G": 0,
    "y_velocity_mm_sec": 0,
    "y_displacement_mm": 0,
    "y_peak_one_Hz": 0,
    "y_peak_two_Hz": 0,
    "y_peak_three_Hz": 0,
    "z_rms_ACC_G": 0,
    "z_max_ACC_G": 0,
    "z_velocity_mm_sec": 0,

```

```
"z_displacement_mm": 0,  
"z_peak_one_Hz": 0,  
"z_peak_two_Hz": 0,  
"z_peak_three_Hz": 0  
}  
}
```

Indoor sensor data

```
{  
  "DataStream":  
  {  
    "@iot.id": 137  
  },  
  "resultTime": "2022-10-17T02:05:34.545+00:00",  
  "result":  
  {  
    "rms_x": 55.06,  
    "rms_y": 998.4,  
    "rms_z": 896.73,  
    "max_x": 194.71,  
    "max_y": 1155.09,  
    "max_z": 0,  
    "min_x": -174.21,  
    "min_y": 0,  
    "min_z": -961.84,  
    "temperature": 17  
  }  
}
```

4. Viaducts experiments and results

Ferrovial is the end user representing Viaduct Inspection operations. In this context, the experiments have been approached from two perspectives. The first is to perform a technical evaluation based on the developments that have been conducted during this first phase 1. The tests were mainly focused on verifying whether the flying devices are capable of carrying out the three expected use cases, from a technical point of view. For this purpose, Ferrovial has provided a key test area for the development of this first phase, a test area that allows the drones to demonstrate their capabilities within the scope of those use cases.

On the other hand, although business KPI was planned to be addressed during phase II, it has been also possible to validate some of them.

4.1. Description of Viaduct Location

The test location for Phase I meets all testing requirements for the three selected use cases. The height, climatic conditions and dimensions were suitable for testing.

The location selected is Alora, a small village in the interior of Malaga, through which the Spanish high speed train runs. Specifically, it is the Arroyo del Espinazo viaduct, whose location is as follows: <https://maps.google.com/?q=36.852707,-4.688210>

Figure 88. Map with the location of viaduct experiments.

Figure 89. General scenario of viaduct tests. Highspeed railway on the top.

Figure 90. Sensors and Monitoring Team checking the data before flights.

Figure 91. CATEC drone ready for the general inspection of viaduct.

Figure 92. CATEC drone conducting the inspections of one of the pillars.

The test area belongs to one of Ferrovial's main clients (ADIF; Spanish Public Railway Infrastructure Operator). It is a recently built viaduct, over which Spanish High Speed (AVE) trains run. In fact, the train frequency is very high (trains run approximately every twenty minutes). This was one of the main challenges as, by law, the drones could not exceed the height of the track.

In terms of dimensions, the viaduct in particular is more than 300 metres long and has an average height of about 40 metres. The weather conditions in the test area oscillate 22 Celsius degrees on average/year, light wind (depending on the time of year) and hardly any rain. In fact, in the summer (testing period of phase I), peaks of 40 degrees were reached, which made some test days particularly difficult. Despite the summer heat, these conditions remain optimal for this first phase of testing.

4.1.1. Flight Authorisation process

These flights are performed under ‘Open’ A3 category which requirements are:

- Registered UAS operator.
- Less than 25Kg UAS.
- Visual line of sight (VLOS).
- 120m maximum height.
- Do not fly near or over people.
- Fly at least 150m away from residential, commercial or industrial areas.

Figure 93. Flight restrictions.

Flight volume is inside the CTR of Málaga airport (LEMG), but outside of its security area. This requires a safety assessment previously coordinated with the aeronautical service provider of the area, ENAIRE.

In addition, each of these flights requires ARO (Airport Reservation Office) approval of a Flight Plan and real time coordination with Malaga Airport.

ENAIRE AIS-ESPAÑA		Mensaje de Plan de Vuelo		Fecha del envío del email: 28/09/2022 08:56	
Grabado Por					
LOGIN: ARO LEST		OFICINA ARO ICARO: OFICINA LEST			
Dia de vuelo		Nuevo día de vuelo		Hora de Depósito	
28 09 22 (DD/MM/AA)		(DD/MM/AA)		28 08 56 dd hh:mm UTC	
ESTADO PV					
ACTIVO					
Tipo de Mensaje: FPL		ARCID: CTC05	Reglas de Vuelo: V	Tipo de vuelo: G	
Aeronaves: Nº: <input type="text"/>		Tipo: VFHC	Estela: L	Equipo de COM: V	
		Equipo SSR: N	Equipo ADS: <input type="text"/>		
ADEP: ZZZZ	EOBT: 14 30	ADES: ZZZZ	EET Total: 02 30	ALTN: <input type="text"/>	
Ruta: <input type="text"/>					
Velocidad: KD020					
Nivel: VFR					
OTROS DATOS					
-RMK/PRUEBAS VUELO CON WP CON DETECCION DE OBSTACULOS UAS MITOM 15.5KG/ OPERATIVO DRON SEGUN AUTORIZACION REF. ENAIRE 5255/2022 PLANEIA / INDICATIVO DE LLAMADA CATEC01 OPR/FADA CATEC DEP/SANTIAGO CIUDAD DEST/SANTIAGO CIUDAD DOF/220928					
Autonomía: 02 35 HH:MM		Personas a bordo: TBN	Equipo radio de Emergencia: <input type="checkbox"/>		
Equipo de Supervivencia: <input type="text"/>		Tipo Chalecos: <input type="text"/>			
Nº: <input type="text"/>	Capacidad: <input type="text"/>	Cubierta: <input type="text"/>	Color: <input type="text"/>		
Color y Marcas del avión: NEGRO					
Observaciones: <input type="text"/>					
Piloto al Mando: FRANCISCO GARCIA ROMAN					
Login de Presentado			Respuesta		
CATEC.AVIONICA			ACEPTADO		

Figure 94. Approved Flight Plan.

4.2. Viaduct Visual Inspection (including surveying target installation)

In the inspection of viaducts, the first step is to start with a visual inspection to assess the condition of the infrastructure. This visual inspection is currently performed entirely manually, posing difficulties due to the wide variety of viaducts that exist. On the one hand, the work at height prevents a visual inspection of the entire viaduct without specialized machinery or climbers. On the other hand, the size of the infrastructure can make that a simple general visual inspection requires a lot of time to be performed manually.

In the PILOTING project, the procedure for the visual inspection of the viaducts includes a general inspection in which photographs are taken of the complete infrastructure to locate possible defects with artificial intelligence. The AERO-CAM platform has been used for this task. Once an area of interest is located, the VIAD-DRONE platform is used to place a surveying target of known geometry to obtain more detail. Once placed, AERO-CAM performs a more detailed visual inspection of the target to complete the information.

In the first pilot experiments, inspections have been concentrated on one of the spans of the Álora viaduct to validate the developments. For the planning and inspections execution, a 3D map has been made with a total station, as shown in the Figure 95.

Figure 95. On the left, span of the Álora viaduct used for the experiments. On the right, 3D model created with a total station.

Two inspections plans were designed during the first pilots. On the one hand, a general inspection covering the maximum possible area to obtain an overall view of condition of the infrastructure. On the other hand, once the sticker was placed by VIAD-DRONE, a specific inspection of the placement area was created. These plans were designed in the IVP web portal, as shown in Figure 96, to be subsequently downloaded in the gRCS and executed.

Figure 96. Inspection plans in the IVP.

The inspection plans were executed repeatedly on different days and in different light and wind conditions. These executions were performed from a ground team with the gRCS and mRCS software without direct line of sight with the AERO-CAM. All data were transmitted from the platform to the ground. The safety pilot was in the flight area with direct line of sight to the UAV. Communication between the different personnel was continuous via walkie-talkies.

Figure 97. Pilots execution with AERO-CAM in Álora. On the left, ground station receiving data in the gRCS. On the right, AERO-CAM flying executing the inspection.

General visual inspection

For the first step of the visual inspection (general visual inspection), an important number of complete inspection missions were successfully performed. All the results were uploaded to the IVP portal through the gRCS and mRCS for evaluation of the results. Figure 98 shows for the same asset and general inspection results, all the data from different flights overlapped for a comparative analysis between them. The colored lines show the trajectory followed by AERO-CAM in the different flights. On the other hand, the blue arrows show the camera positions for each photograph obtained. Figure 98Figure 99 shows a total of 6 overlapping flights and 57 photographs. In Figure 99 are represented 2 overlapping flights with 12 photographs.

Figure 98. Álora general inspection postmission data visualization in the IVP.

Figure 99. Alora pillar inspection post mission data visualization in the IVP.

It can be seen in Figure 98 and Figure 99 how the trajectories between different flights coincide, demonstrating the repeatability of the experiments. The results were satisfactory since the same experiments could be repeated many times and the images from the same locations could be captured for inspection. This is a very important characteristic for performing visual inspection and represents a high value for the end users in comparison with manual inspections. Also, in the last part of the Visual inspection mission (specific visual inspection), it will be demonstrated that not only the images are taken from the same position, but they cover a similar area of the viaduct (including for example the same survey target in all of them).

All flights were performed completely autonomously, from take-off, waypoint navigation, pictures capturing and landing. In order to perform these inspection missions autonomously, a LIDAR-based GNSS free localization system was implemented. Also, an automatic obstacle detection system was used as well in order to facilitate the supervision of the mission by the operator in BVLOS conditions. Both autonomously functionalities worked well allowing to complete a large number of inspection missions. Figure 100 shows the 3D visualization of the localization algorithm without GNSS running during an experiment. The UAV is represented by the red, green and blue XYZ axes. The yellow lines represent the transform from the UAV to its take-off point, and from the take-off point to the map origin. The non-straight green line represents the odometry in the previous instants. The current point cloud is also shown with respect to the map cloud.

Figure 100. 3D visualization of the localization algorithm without GNSS.

Figure 101 shows 3D visualization of the obstacle detector running during an inspection. The orange dots represent the 3D LiDAR visualization of the viaduct. Each portion represented as a 3D trapezoid in green is an area where the closest obstacle to the UAV, which is in the center, is searched for. The white dots represent the obstacle in each section, if any.

Figure 101. 3D visualization of the obstacle detector running during an inspection.

All the data were being retransmitted to the ground and the operator could see in the gRCS and mRCS each of the photographs obtained, as well as the trajectory in real time, the distance to the obstacles and other data such as battery, altitude, etc.

Figure 102. AERO-CAM mRCS working during an inspection in Álora.

An example of photographs obtained for a general inspection would be as follows:

Figure 103. Example of photographs of a general inspection with AERO-CAM in Álora.

Since the viaduct where the experiments have been performed are very recent, there are not significant details. Then, and after performing a general visual inspection, the detection of a possible failure in one of the pillars was simulated in order to proceed with the next two phases (survey target installation and specific visual inspection).

Survey target installation

Following the inspection plan designed in the PILOTING project, once the general visual inspection is performed and, thus, an overall condition of the infrastructure is obtained, the VIAD-DRONE robot places some surveying targets near to the inspection locations. These targets are small devices with a millimetric pattern, used as reference to improve the accuracy of visual inspections, which is the main goal of the target installation task. The main objective of the first pilot experiments was to perform the installation of some surveying targets in different locations of a real viaduct, in particular, near to those points where potential defects have been previously detected by the general visual inspection procedure.

The description of the scenario is shown in Figure 104. The experiments were performed in the same span of the Álora viaduct where the general visual inspection experiments took place, particularly. The VIAD-DRONE robot is commanded to perform the target installation near to two different

inspection locations (ILs). One of them is at considerable height in the surface of the pillar (IL_1). On the other hand, the second inspection location (IL_2) is located in the eighth control point used by the Total Station to build the viaduct asset model (map building procedure is described in detail in Deliverable 4.2 (“Data gathering sets”)). For that, the aerial robot navigates along an obstacle-free trajectory from the start point to the approach point, which is located perpendicularly to the installation surface and at a safe distance from the installation location. Then it makes contact with the surface of the pillar and attaches the target device near to the inspection location.

Figure 104. Scenario for the viaduct surveying target installation in the first pilot experiments.

As with the rest of inspection missions, the inspection plans were created in the IVP in accordance with the procedure detailed in Section 2. . Then, the inspection plans and the viaduct asset model were downloaded to the gRCS where the detailed planning of the inspection was created adding waypoints and connecting them with the inspection points, ensuring a safe and efficient route for the aerial robot in the environment. Figure 105-left shows the inspection plan and the inspection location (yellow semi sphere located in the surface of the pillar) designed in the IVP and Figure 105-right shows the planning of the inspection created in the gRCS for the same inspection plan. The waypoints to be followed by the aerial robot and the trajectory to be executed to reach to the inspection location are shown.

Figure 105. Inspection plan created from the IVP for the inspection location (left) and complete mission designed in gRCS (right).

The aerial robot used in the first pilots was the VIAD-DRONE with the target installation configuration described in Deliverable 4.1 (“PILOTING First Robotic Vehicles”). This platform is depicted in Figure 106, in Deliverable 4.1 only a CAD version of the VIAD-DRONE robot was provided. The pole and the retractile mechanism installed were those presented in Deliverable 4.1, but in this case they were installed in the lower part of the aerial robot instead of in the add-on bars of the platform. The surveying target model used in the first pilot experiments is also shown in the figure.

Figure 106. VIAD-DRONE with the surveying target installation configuration.

Some pictures of the VIAD-DRONE robot performing the target installation mission in the two designed inspection locations are shown in Figure 107. In particular, Figure 107-top-left shows the aerial robot at the approach point to the IL_1 , Figure 107-top-right shows the aerial robot performing the installation task at IL_1 . Similarly, Figure 107-bottom-left shows the aerial robot at the approach point to IL_2 and Figure 107-bottom-right shows the target installation at IL_2 , located at height in the viaduct. The navigation of the aerial robot was autonomously performed from the start point until each of the approach points. During the inspection the robot received no GNSS signal, hence robot pose estimation was achieved with no GNSS but using sensor fusion techniques that were implemented on board the robot and in real time.

In addition, the installation of the surveying target was performed by the direct contact of the retractile mechanism with the pillar surface. In this first stage of the project, the robot navigation was performed fully autonomously while the final part of the contact maneuver was performed manually to ensure

that the target was properly stuck at the desired location. For the second stage of the project, the entire mission will be performed fully autonomously and on board, including the navigation and also the part involving physically interaction.

Figure 107. VIAD-DRONE in the approach point for the target installation mission in IL_1 (top-left) and performing the surveying installation at IL_1 (top-right). VIAD-DRONE in the approach point for the target installation mission in IL_2 (bottom-left) and performing the surveying installation at IL_2 (bottom-right).

During the experiments, the gRCS commanded the missions for its execution. The UAV navigated autonomously in the Álora viaduct following an obstacle-free trajectory precisely designed for the safety of both the viaduct infrastructure and the aerial robot. All measurements were transmitted from the platform to the ground for monitoring the state and the performance of the missions in the gRCS, previously shown in Figure 105-right, and also the sensor measurements gathered and the aerial robot localization estimated in real time in a different ground control station designed for the purpose, depicted in Figure 108. In this figure, the measurements gathered from the camera and the 2D LIDAR (white lines and the upper red lines) are shown, as well as the estimated position of the aerial robot (in green in the middle) and the localization of the robot estimated with the Leica Total Station (in red), used as ground truth. The high similarity between green line (estimated with no GNSS) and the red line (ground truth computed by the Leica Total station) evidences the accuracy of the GNSS-denied localization method developed and experimented. All gathered measurements from the environment and the estimations of the robot pose were processed by the on-board computer.

Figure 108. Ground control station monitoring in real time the camera images and the 2D LIDAR measurements gathered during the flights, the VIAD-DRONE robot localization estimated by the localization methods (green) and by the Total Station (red).

Accurate aerial robot localization was estimated during the execution of the inspection plans using the on-board sensors and without GNSS measurements. In particular, the sensors used to estimate the aerial robot localization were a 2D LIDAR equipped with a 45° mirror to obtain the distance between the robot and the viaduct deck, a camera pointing downwards, and a laser altimeter pointed to the ground. The first version of the developed localization method was described in the Deliverable 5.1 (“Beta Version of Advanced Autonomous Functionalities for Aerial Robots”). Figure 109-top shows in blue and in each axis the VIAD-DRONE localization estimation during one of the first pilot flights of the viaduct target installation use case and in red the aerial robot localization estimated with a Total Station, used as ground truth. Figure 109-bottom shows the errors of the aerial robot localization in each axis, being the mean error in the x axis of about 0.1219 m, 0.1532 m in the y axis and 0.0436 m in the z axis, highlighting the high accuracy of the aerial robot localization estimation in this use case, critical to perform autonomous and accurate inspection missions.

Figure 109. VIAD-DRONE robot localization estimation in blue against the ground truth localization estimated with a Leica Total station in red (top) and the related localization errors (bottom).

Figure 110 collects the surveying target installation results obtained in the first pilot experiments. As mentioned before, the experiments focused on two inspection locations, and IL_2 . The robustness and the reliability of the system were validated by the proper surveying target installation near the two planned inspection locations. Moreover, in order to validate the repeatability of the system and also the aerial robot localization estimation results, some surveying targets were installed near to the same inspection location, IL_2 , as shown in Figure 110-top-right. The experiments were performed in different days and under different wind conditions evidencing the robustness both of the robot GNSS-denied pose estimation method and of the robot autonomous navigation system.

Figure 110. Results of the surveying target installation use case in first pilot experiments.

The inspection results gathered from the target installations carried out in Álora viaduct were uploaded to the IVP following the procedure detailed in Section 2. . Figure 111 shows one of the uploaded results. The inspector can visualize the performed trajectory of the drone during the missions (colored lines) and the inspection locations where the surveying targets are installed (yellow semi spheres), among others.

Figure 111. IVP uploaded results gathered in one of the surveying target installation experiments in the first pilots.

Specific visual inspection

With the surveying target in place, a specific inspection was carried out with the AERO-CAM platform. In this case the goal was to obtain photographs around the surveying target, not the entire viaduct. To test the repeatability of the operation, several consecutive attempts were made to obtain the photographs shown in Figure 112.

Figure 112. Example of 4 photographs of the same location of a specific inspection in 4 different flights with AERO-CAM in Álora.

The experiments were carried out under the same conditions as the general visual inspections. As can be observed in Figure 112, in all cases the target was successfully photographed, although with small deviations due to flight fluctuations.

4.3. Viaduct Bearing Inspection

The lifespan of viaducts can be severely affected by the degradation of the bearings, leading to significant defects in the structural behavior and durability of the asset. At the same time, their degradation might lead inspectors to identify other related pathologies that cannot be seen at a simple glance, such as unforeseen existing stresses or displacements. Then, the monitoring of the bearings becomes important as their performance is critical to the whole structural system. These types of operations are based on visual inspections that allow the specialists to assess different aspects on the evolution of the bearings. For the inspector to be able to find these defects, they must be very close to the bearing to be inspected in order to appreciate, evaluate, and measure defects with sufficient accuracy. Due to the height of the viaducts, bearing inspection usually implies the use of heavy machinery to reach them as they are points of the structure with limited access. PILOTING project proposes to perform bearing inspection procedures using aerial robots instead of human inspectors. The use of drone platforms to be able to collect data will result in significant reductions of disruption time while ensuring the safety of both, inspectors and infrastructure users, and minimizing the costs invested in heavy machinery used for access purposes.

Regarding the viaduct bearing inspection use case, the objective of the first pilot experiments was to perform visual bearing inspection of a real viaduct using an aerial robot. The robot should be able to

take high-quality pictures close to the bearings from different angles. The experiments were conducted in the same span of the Álora viaduct where the general visual inspection was performed, described in the last section.

The designed scenario is shown in Figure 113. Here, the VIAD-DRONE navigates to the attachment point. Then, to increase the safety of the operation and for enabling the robot to get close enough to the bearings, the aerial robot attaches to the deck and moves along it without losing the contact. Once the robot is near to the inspection points, at a specific distance, it takes pictures of the bearings. Then, it navigates back to the attachment point and flies to the starting point.

Figure 113. Design of the viaduct bearing inspection scenario for the first pilot experiments.

Similarly as with the rest of the inspections, the inspection plans were created in the IVP in accordance with the procedure described in Section 2. . Then, the viaduct map and the inspection plans were downloaded to the gRCS where the detailed planning of the inspections were created adding some waypoints and connecting them with the inspection points, ensuring a safe and efficient route for the aerial robot in the environment. The inspection plan designed in the IVP for performing the visual inspection of both bearing is shown in Figure 114-left. Figure 114-right shows the complete planning for the inspection created in the gRCS for the same inspection plan.

Figure 114. Inspection points designed in the IVP for the visual bearing inspection (left) and the downloaded inspection plan in the gRCS (right).

The aerial robot used for the viaduct bearing inspection use case is presented in Deliverable 4.1. The platform carries the gimbal device for image stabilization and the inspection camera. The used model of these two devices, as well as their technical specifications such as their weight, is further described in the deliverable. The platform used in the first pilots is depicted in Figure 115. Deliverable 4.1 showed only the CAD-designed version of VIAD-DRONE for this use case. The system that allows the aerial robot to establish contact with the bottom part of the viaduct's deck is the caterpillar system, also shown in the figure. They are further explained in Deliverable 4.1. The final platform built for the bearing visual inspection use case will be explained in detail in Deliverable 4.3.

Figure 115. VIAD-DRONE platform with the viaduct bearing inspection configuration.

Figure 116 shows a picture of VIAD-DRONE performing the visual bearing inspection. The VIAD-DRONE autonomously navigated in the Álora viaduct tracking a list of waypoints from the starting point to the approach point, a route designed for ensuring an appropriated and an obstacle-denied trajectory in the environment. The robot pose estimation was performed using GNSS-denied localization techniques that were implemented in real time and on board the robot. In the stage of the project, the last part of the mission, involving physical contact, i.e. navigation from the approach point to the attachment point and the navigation along the deck, were performed in manual mode. The inspection missions will be carried out fully autonomously in the second pilot experiments. The orientation control of the gimbal and the image capture were performed autonomously by the gRCS, taking into account the bearing positions with respect to the aerial robot localization in the environment.

Figure 116. VIAD-DRONE navigating in the Álora viaduct to perform the visual bearing inspection.

For enabling the GNSS-denied autonomous navigation of the robot, accurate and reliable localization of the drone was estimated fusing the measurements gathered by the sensors on-board. These sensors and the robot pose GNSS-denied estimation methods used were the same as in the viaduct target installation. Figure 117-top shows in blue the VIAD-DRONE localization estimation during one of the first pilot flights and in red the aerial robot localization estimated with a Total Station, used as ground truth. Figure 117-bottom shows the errors of the aerial robot localization in each axis, being the mean error in the x axis of about 0.1461 m, 0.0783 m in the y axis and 0.1161 m in the z axis, highlighting the high accuracy of the aerial robot localization, which critical to perform fully autonomous and accurate inspection missions.

Figure 117. VIAD-DRONE robot localization estimation in blue against the ground truth localization estimated with a Leica Total station in red (top) and the related localization errors (bottom).

Some pictures of the viaduct bearing inspection experiments are shown in Figure 118. High-quality images of the two bearings were taken by the on-board inspection camera. At the bottom, an image of the two bearings captured in the experiments is shown. At the top, images of the bearings taken from the capture point while VIAD-DRONE was in contact with the deck are shown. The control of the gimbal and the image capture were conducted autonomously and commanded by the gRCS. Based on the results and performance of the experiments, it was demonstrated that the aerial robot could perform bearing visual inspection with robustness and reliability, properly, and autonomously taking high-quality pictures of the inspection locations while it was in contact with the deck of the viaduct. These pictures could be used for real assessment of the bearings as they have a good level of detail for the operator to evaluate the viaduct infrastructure. Finally, inspection results generated after each inspection mission in the first pilot experiments was uploaded in the IVP.

Figure 118. Bearing visual inspection results obtained in the first pilot experiments.

4.4. Viaduct Sensor Installation

Both previous use cases rely on images to detect possible defects on the viaduct. However, there is a difference between detecting a defect and measuring the impact of this defect on the structure. There are devices that can help to detect different types of non-visible defects. Sensor boxes with some devices inside like accelerometers or IMUs are commonly used by traditional inspection procedures for monitoring the viaduct condition. In particular, they are used to measure useful information such as vibrations, accelerations or displacements of the viaduct structure. Locations where these boxes are placed are strategically chosen by qualified personnel. Most of times, for a good monitoring of the state of the infrastructure, the boxes are required to be installed in difficult to access locations (e.g. above the pillars). PILOTING project proposes the use of aerial robots with manipulation capabilities for installing these devices in such difficult to access places. Performing installation procedures using aerial robots avoids, among others, involving personnel working at high altitudes and the use of heavy machinery for accessing purposes, considerably reducing the time and the costs of the inspections and, what is more important, the safety of the operators.

The objective of the first pilot experiments for this use case was to install a sensor box on top of a viaduct pillar, close to the bearings, using an aerial robot with advanced capabilities. This use case inspections involve additional risks due to the difficult to access and considerably narrow locations where the aerial platform should navigate to perform the installation. The first pilot experiments were performed in the same span on the Álora viaduct than in the previous use cases, in particular in the pillar shown in Figure 119. This figure also depicts the developed procedure to perform the sensor box installation. This procedure is very similar to that of bearing inspection use case, replacing the visual inspection by the installation of the device. To perform the sensor box installation, the robot must navigate along the viaduct deck and reach the gap between the top part of the viaduct pillars and the deck (operational area) without losing the contact with the infrastructure. Once the operational area is reached, the sensor box is installed by the aerial robot at the installation point.

Figure 119. Scenario design for the viaduct sensor installation use case in the first pilot experiments.

Due to the additional and high risks implied in this use case inspections, the environment must comply with some requirements. On the one hand, due to the narrow gap between the viaduct deck and the top part of its pillars and also the relevant aerodynamic effects produced by the proximity of the aerial robot to the viaduct structure, it is extremely critical to the expert pilot to have clear line of sight with the robot while it is navigating in the operational area and performing the sensor box installation. On the other hand, once the sensor was installed and considering that the aerial robot has not manipulation capabilities to remove the installed box, an operator should access the top part of the pillars and remove it. Moreover, the robot should be manually recovered by an operator in case something goes wrong.

None of the abovementioned requirements were fulfilled by the span of the Álora viaduct where the first pilot experiments were performed as its pillars were at least 15 meters high. The expert pilot had not direct line of sight with the aerial robot. Besides, the top part of the pillars were difficult to access locations to an operator to remove the sensor box or recover the aerial platform it necessary. As the end-user was not able to find a suitable environment for the safe execution of the viaduct sensor box installation, even in a different viaduct, the adopted approach was to perform the complete inspection procedure as if the environment was suitable for carrying out the installation on top of the pillars and, at the end of the mission, to demonstrate the manipulation capabilities of the aerial robot on the ground. The inspection plan for performing the first pilot experiments were designed in the IVP and downloaded to the gRCS, shown in Figure 120. Despite the abovementioned approach for the first pilot experiments, the dimensions of the operational area of the Álora viaduct for the sensor box installation was accurately measured with a Leica Total Station. By comparing the gathered dimensions of the operational area with the VIAD-DRONE dimensions, it was concluded that the aerial robot design was suitable for enabling the aerial robot to execute the inspections although the environment was not suitable for developing the inspections.

Figure 120. Designed inspection plan downloaded in the gRCS.

Figure 121 shows the aerial robot used for the sensor box installation in the first pilot experiments. Deliverable 4.1 showed only the CAD-designed version of the VIAD-DRONE for this use case. The aerial robot used for the first pilots carried a sensor box prototype made of plastic and built with similar dimensions to the devices installed by the real inspection procedures. In the first pilots, the box did not contained real sensors inside. The cargo system for carrying the sensor box is also shown in Figure 121, it is the same as the one described in Deliverable 4.1. As for the visual bearing inspection use case, the caterpillar system was required for reliably making contact and navigate along the deck of the viaduct.

Figure 121. VIAD-DRONE with the sensor box installation configuration used in the first pilot experiments.

Figure 122 shows some pictures of the VIAD-DRONE executing the designed inspection in the first pilot experiments. Figure 122-left shows the VIAD-DRONE autonomously navigating in the environment and reaching the approach point. Figure 122-right shows the VIAD-DRONE attached the deck of the viaduct and navigating along it. As in the previous viaduct use cases, the execution of the inspection missions was commanded by the gRCS, in addition to the autonomous control of the cargo system actuators for the deployment of the sensor box. The ground station shown in Figure 120 was also used for monitoring the sensor measurements and the localization estimation of the robot during the experiments of this use case. The VIAD-DRONE autonomously navigated in the Álora

viaduct tracking a list of waypoints designed for ensuring a proper an obstacle-denied trajectory in the environment. The robot pose estimation was performed using GNSS-denied localization techniques that were implemented in real time and on board the robot. In the first stage of the project, the last part of the mission, involving physical contact, i.e. navigation from the approach point to the attachment point, the navigation along the deck and the navigation in the operational area for the installation were performed in manual mode. The inspection missions will be carried out fully autonomously in the second pilot experiments.

Figure 122. VIAD-DRONE robot performing the designed inspection plan for the sensor box installation in the first pilot experiments.

For enabling the GNSS-denied autonomous navigation of the robot, accurate and reliable localization of the VIAD-DRONE was estimated computing the measurements gathered by the on-board sensors. These sensors and the robot pose GNSS-denied estimation methods used were the same as in the previous viaduct use cases. Figure 123-top shows in blue the VIAD-DRONE localization estimation during one of the first pilot flights and in red the aerial robot localization estimated with a Total Station, used as ground truth. Figure 123-bottom shows the errors of the aerial robot localization in each axis, being the mean error in the x axis of about 0.0679 m, 0.2349 m in the y axis and 0.0234 m in the z axis. An approach with incremental accuracy and difficulty was adopted since the localization accuracy for physical contact interaction must be higher than for open-space robot navigation.

Figure 123. VIAD-DRONE robot localization estimation in blue against the ground truth localization estimated with a Leica Total station in red (top) and the related localization errors (bottom).

Figure 124 shows the sensor box deployment performed on the ground, strongly enhancing care and the safety of the platform given the level of development of the first stage of the project and also the unsuitable environment to perform the installation. The aerial robot was autonomously commanded by the gRCS to drop the sensor box at the starting point of the inspection. The manipulation capabilities of the aerial robot were validated. In the second stage of the project, a suitable location for the sensor box installation on top of the pillars must be found and provided by the end-user in order to perform more realistic inspection missions. The KPIs evaluation and the requirements validation associated to the viaduct sensor box installation use case will be detailed in Section 6. and Annex I: Requirements Validation, respectively.

Figure 124. Sensor box deployment on the ground. The VIAD-DRONE was autonomously commanded by the gRCS drop the sensor box at the starting point.

4.4.1. IoT Sensors

Within the scope of PILOTING project, sensors (accelerometers) have been installed by Ferrovial to measure the movements that a certain point of the viaduct may have. In this case, it has been carried out on the Rioverde viaduct, in the province of Malaga (coordinates as follows: 36.525613, -4.958596). It is one of the viaducts with the highest traffic density in Spain, as it forms part of the route from north to south (between France and Morocco).

Figure 125. Signal of Rio Verde Viaduct.

Figure 126. Viaduct views from the top of one pillar.

It was therefore crucial to be able to digitally monitor the movement of this bridge. Five digital accelerometers that transmit the information wirelessly to a gateway were installed in September 19th 2022. In addition, they store the information on a memory card installed in each of them in case the signal is lost. The position of each sensor is as follows:

Figure 127. Platform to monitoring data with each sensor location.

In this image, nodes A, C & D are allocated within the board. B and E are allocated in the top of the pillars 1 and 2.

On the other hand, the installation of the five accelerometers and the gateway took 5 hours on Monday 19th September (photos attached):

Figure 128. Sensors E and D installation procedures.

Once installed, the gateway then sends the records to a platform, which "decodes" them and displays them as shown below:

Figure 129. Graph visualization from B1 sensor behaviour.

The information shows the maximum vibration records for each day. The platform itself associated with the sensors allows the records to be compared with each other in order to know which part of the viaduct is registering the strongest movements.

In addition, to ensure the transmission of information to the other PILOTING members, the entities INLECOM, ICCS and Ferrovial have worked on an interface (similar to the one used for the refinery wireless sensor network) to be able to integrate the information of these sensors in the DMS, and also

be able to visualize them in the IVP. Then, in a similar fashion to the refinery use case, the IVP offers an interface to retrieve and visualize the data collected from the viaduct sensors and stored in the IoT platform. The connection between the backend components was established and the first data has been received, as illustrated in Figure 130. This figure shows the recorded vibrations along the z-axis of the sensors – the values measured in g depict the raw data, sampled at a frequency of approximately 1Hz. In the next steps, the IVP will implement a caching mechanism to analyze and reduce the granularity of the data in order to extract the relevant information, by computing for example the maximum vibrations recorded over a certain period.

Figure 130. Visualization of the static sensor installed at the Rioverde viaduct.

To conclude, key point addressed during phase I are shown as follows:

1. 5 sensors have been installed in Rio Verde Viaduct in Malaga (South of Spain)
2. Each sensor measures the vibration (higher peak of vibration) of the bridge.
3. The information gathered by each sensor is sent by 3G to a Gateway that also sends by 3G the information to an online monitoring platform every 3 hours.
4. The information gathered by the sensors was also integrated in the DMS, and it is possible to visualize using the IVP.
5. Sensors was installed on September 19th and was expected would be working for 15 days (until October 2nd), but as mid-november sensors are still gathering data since duration of batteries was better than expected.

4.5. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – Data transmission, transformation and storing

4.5.1. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform - AEROCAM

Regarding the general inspection of the Viaduct case, the AEROCAM robot successfully performed 15 Missions for 3 Inspection Plans. The Mission specific data has been successfully uploaded to the DMS through the DDHL. Below you can find an example of the unique identifiers of the objects created on the DMS regarding the Inspection Plans, the Missions, and the Mission Tasks.

Table 40. DMS Information regarding AEROCAM Missions.

Inspection Plan	Mission	Mission Tasks	SyncID
2eb9b2a3-0e85-400d-99c7-bbc3847d2139	78e38aac-4872-4d2e-bc68-a0f25afd0958	dfe425b3-2085-42d6-8cbf-4bc7505bcaba	1307878634
		9be32c3b-b683-430e-b0c7-48bc2af76f4a	
		69c3f8a5-26be-4597-a68b-01d8f3c3378b	

Figure 131. Workflow diagram – Post Mission Data (AEROCAM).

As described in Section 2.2.3, the gRCS communicates with the DDHL prior to the execution of the Mission to instantiate both Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and post the generic data to the DMS. Progressing, the AEROCAM robotic system uploads the mission specific data (Table 41) to the DDHL enclosed in a compressed folder. The DDHL is responsible to unzip the folder, transform and post the data under the right Mission by utilizing the APIs of the DMS., as illustrated in Figure 131. In order to find the Mission created by the gRCS and to correlate the data with, the DDHL uses the SyncID property included in the mRCS data. As described in Section 2.2.3, SyncID is a property included in both generic and mission specific data towards the synchronization of the data. In case of failure, the DDHL will roll back the changes that have been made to the database and eventually inform the AEROCAM about the failure.

Table 41. Mission Specific Data provided by AEROCAM.

File Type	Description	Example Data Format
Pictures	Individual files in a specific folder	
Pictures Metadata	Metadata for each taken picture	picture_file_name, timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w, mm_per_pixel, distance
Localization Telemetry	Localization stamp and pose from the fusion sensor solution without GPS information. Origin referred to the viaduct 3D model	timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w
GPS Telemetry	Localization stamp and pose solution from GPS sensor	timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, latitude, longitude, altitude
Config File	Configuration file with the sensor configuration of the robotic platform. This file provides the sensor list and the physical offset between them as well as inspection information (eg: Inspection Plan UUID, SyncID)	<pre>{ "startDate": "2022_02_11-12_53_26", "endDate": "2022_02_11-12_56_40", "syncId": 10000, "uid": "xxxxxxxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx", "inspectionPlanId": "xxxxxxxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx", "inspectionTaskId": ["xxxxxxxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx", "xxxxxxxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxxxxxxxxxxxxxx"], "type": "visual", "map": "alora_2021_03_11.pcd", "files": { "pictures_metadata": "PictureMetadataLogging.csv", "pictures_folder": "photos", "telemetry_data": "LocalizationTelemetryDataLogging.csv", "gps_data": "GPSTelemetryDataLogging.csv" }, "sensors": [{ "id": 1 }, { "id": 2 }, { "id": 3 }, { "id": 4 }], "pictures": { "folder": "photos", "sensor_uid": "14506157-8937-4a46-a895-352fa91be59", "format": "jpg", "size": { "width": 9584, "height": 6336 }, "fov": { "horizontal": 23.9, "vertical": 16.1 } } }</pre>

Seen below are indicative screenshots originating by the DDHL logs that capture the communication between the mRCS (AEROCAM), the DDHL and the DMS modules regarding the implementation of several Inspection Plans.

Table 42. Indicative screenshots from DDHL Logs.

Inspection Plan UUID: 2eb9b2a3-0e85-400d-99c7-bbc3847d2139	Mission UUID: 78e38aac-4872-4d2e-bc68-a0f25afd0958
<p>Figure 132. AEROCAM uploads the mission specific data to the DMS through the DDHL.</p>	

As described, the DDHL succeeded in instantiating both Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and uploading both the generic and the mission specific data to the DMS concerning the AEROCAM case.

4.5.2. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform - VIADDRONE (Viaduct visual inspection in the surveying target installation use case.)

The DDHL as part of the I&M PILOTING platform is responsible to obtain the Mission Specific Data originating from the VIAD_DRONE robotic system and upload it to the DMS.

Regarding the Viaduct case, the VIAD_DRONE robot successfully performed a number of missions for the surveying target installation use case. The Mission specific data has been successfully uploaded to the DMS through the DDHL for the surveying target installation use case. Below you can find an example of the unique identifiers of the objects created on the DMS regarding the Inspection Plans, the Missions, and the Mission Tasks.

Table 43. DMS Information regarding VIAD_DRONE Mission - Viaduct surveying target installation use case.

Inspection Plan	Mission	Mission Tasks	SyncID
6220ff3c-0ae7-4049-a552-cdd567715613	edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c	b58040d9-4f2b-4bfe-af94-6ebb8ed12075	1333299004

Figure 133. Workflow diagram – Post Mission Data (VIAD_DRONE).

As already described in Section 2.2.3, the gRCS communicates with the DDHL prior to the execution of the Mission in order to instantiate both Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and post the generic data to the DMS.

Progressing, the VIAD_DRONE robotic system uploads the mission specific data (Table 44) to the DDHL enclosed in a compressed folder. This operation is similar for both VIAD DRONE use cases. The DDHL is responsible to unzip the folder, transform and post the data under the right Mission by utilizing the APIs of the DMS., as illustrated in Figure 133. To find the Mission created by the gRCS and to correlate the data with, the DDHL uses the SyncID property included in the mRCS data. As described in Section 2.2.3, SyncID is a property included in both generic and mission specific data towards the synchronization of the data.

In case of failure, the DDHL will roll back the changes that have been made to the database and eventually inform the VIAD_DRONE about the failure.

Table 44. Mission Specific Data provided by VIAD_DRONE - Viaduct surveying target installation and sensor box installation use cases.

File Type	Description	Example Data Format
Localization Telemetry	Localization stamp and pose from the fusion sensor solution. Origin referred to the viaduct 3D model	timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w
Installation Log	Position with stamp of the installed sensor box or	timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, success

	surveying target referred to the viaduct 3D map, and a variable to represent the success of the mission	
Config File	Configuration file with the sensor configuration of the robotic platform. This file provides the sensor list and the physical offset between them as well as inspection information (eg: Inspection Plan UUID, SyncID)	<pre>{ "startDate": "2022_01_04-09_51_12", "endDate": "2022_02_07-09_51_12", "syncId": "9100", "uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionPlanUuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionTaskUuids": ["XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX", "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX"], "type": "install_sensor", "map": "alora_2021_03_11.pcd", "files": { "installation_log": "mission_log.csv", "telemetry_data": "localization_telemetry.csv" }, "sensors": [{ "name": "gRCs" }] }</pre>

Seen below are indicative screenshots originating by the DDHL logs that capture the communication between the mRCS (VIAD_DRONE – both cases), the DDHL and the DMS modules regarding the implementation of several Inspection Plans.

Table 45. Indicative screenshots from DDHL Logs.

Inspection Plan UUID: 6220ff3c-0ae7-4049-a552-cdd567715613	Mission UUID: edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c
---	---

```
2022-08-31 13:38:29,022,22 ddhl.common INFO Get Full Inspection Plan commonView.py 62
13:38:29,22 ddhl.common INFO Get Full Inspection Plan commonView.py 62
2022-08-31 13:38:29,022,22 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionPlan/6220ff3c-0ae7-4049-a552-cdd567715613/All/ dms.py 24
13:38:29,22 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionPlan/6220ff3c-0ae7-4049-a552-cdd567715613/All/ dms.py 24
2022-08-31 13:38:29,324,324 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionTask/208b1cf1-ac2c-44bc-a327-469c16a66f31/All/ dms.py 71
13:38:29,324 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Full Inspection Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionTask/208b1cf1-ac2c-44bc-a327-469c16a66f31/All/ dms.py 71
2022-08-31 13:38:29,611,611 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Payload/66176cdf-e694-4037-b49e-e87c73e4f2ae/ dms.py 57
13:38:29,611 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Payload/66176cdf-e694-4037-b49e-e87c73e4f2ae/ dms.py 57
2022-08-31 13:38:29,834,834 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Payload/acbead72-235b-4e2f-9333-918588d0470a/ dms.py 57
13:38:29,834 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Payload/acbead72-235b-4e2f-9333-918588d0470a/ dms.py 57
2022-08-31 13:38:30,080,80 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Payload/043e91ca-c224-4115-ac33-cccfab359f6/ dms.py 57
13:38:30,80 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get RCS Payload - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Payload/043e91ca-c224-4115-ac33-cccfab359f6/ dms.py 57
2022-08-31 13:39:51,666,666 ddhl.common INFO Get Full Inspection Plan commonView.py 62
```

Figure 134. gRCS fetches the Inspection Plan.

```
2022-09-08 14:39:33,362,362 ddhl.gRCS INFO Post Generic Data gRCsView.py 18
14:39:33,362 ddhl.gRCS INFO Post Generic Data gRCsView.py 18
2022-09-08 14:39:33,371,371 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Mission By SyncID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/Properties-w78x25yncId0q2203a201333299004x70 dms.py 77
14:39:33,371 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Mission By SyncID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/Properties-w78x25yncId0q2203a201333299004x70 dms.py 77
2022-09-08 14:39:33,685,685 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionPlan/6220ff3c-0ae7-4049-a552-cdd567715613/All/ dms.py 24
14:39:33,685 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Plan - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionPlan/6220ff3c-0ae7-4049-a552-cdd567715613/All/ dms.py 24
2022-09-08 14:39:33,939,939 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post Mission - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/ - Body: {'Name': 'mission_20220725094024', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-07-25T09:40:24.871', 'Properties': {'SyncId': '1333299004'}, 'InspectionPlan': '6220ff3c-0ae7-4049-a552-cdd567715613'} dms.py 91
14:39:33,939 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post Mission - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/ - Body: {'Name': 'mission_20220725094024', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-07-25T09:40:24.871', 'Properties': {'SyncId': '1333299004'}, 'InspectionPlan': '6220ff3c-0ae7-4049-a552-cdd567715613'} dms.py 91
2022-09-08 14:39:34,204,204 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Type By Inspection Task ID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionTask/208b1cf1-ac2c-44bc-a327-469c16a66f31/InspectionType/ dms.py 173
14:39:34,204 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Inspection Type By Inspection Task ID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/InspectionTask/208b1cf1-ac2c-44bc-a327-469c16a66f31/InspectionType/ dms.py 173
2022-09-08 14:39:34,432,432 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post Mission Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/MissionTask/ - Body: {'Name': 'mission_task_0', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-07-25T09:40:57.316', 'InspectionTask': '208b1cf1-ac2c-44bc-a327-469c16a66f31', 'InspectionType': '5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267c382fba07', 'Mission': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c'} dms.py 119
14:39:34,432 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post Mission Task - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/MissionTask/ - Body: {'Name': 'mission_task_0', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-07-25T09:40:57.316', 'InspectionTask': '208b1cf1-ac2c-44bc-a327-469c16a66f31', 'InspectionType': '5b186846-f73a-44b7-8f19-267c382fba07', 'Mission': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c'} dms.py 119
2022-09-08 14:39:34,770,770 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {'tempFiles/Gb4b861c-8f96-4899-9c35-44846067e849/event_log.csv dms.py 126
14:39:34,770 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {'tempFiles/Gb4b861c-8f96-4899-9c35-44846067e849/event_log.csv dms.py 126
2022-09-08 14:39:35,012,12 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/54c23183-ff42-4451-8dc2-1c74d612e925/', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '858', 'OriginalName': 'event_log.csv', 'Content': 'gRCS - event_log', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-09-08T14:39:35Z', 'objectId': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c', 'contentType': '7} dms.py 161
14:39:35,012 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/54c23183-ff42-4451-8dc2-1c74d612e925/', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '858', 'OriginalName': 'event_log.csv', 'Content': 'gRCS - event_log', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-09-08T14:39:35Z', 'objectId': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c', 'contentType': '7} dms.py 161
2022-09-08 14:39:35,243,243 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {'tempFiles/Gb4b861c-8f96-4899-9c35-44846067e849/path_followed.csv dms.py 126
14:39:35,243 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: {'tempFiles/Gb4b861c-8f96-4899-9c35-44846067e849/path_followed.csv dms.py 126
2022-09-08 14:39:35,524,524 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/6439bec1-0e73-4b21-a512-22876cb93991/', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '782', 'OriginalName': 'planned_trajectory.csv', 'Content': 'gRCS - planned_trajectory', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-09-08T14:39:35Z', 'objectId': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c', 'contentType': '7} dms.py 161
14:39:35,524 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/6439bec1-0e73-4b21-a512-22876cb93991/', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '782', 'OriginalName': 'planned_trajectory.csv', 'Content': 'gRCS - planned_trajectory', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-09-08T14:39:35Z', 'objectId': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c', 'contentType': '7} dms.py 161
2022-09-08 14:39:36,140,140 ddhl.gRCS INFO Success Response: {'mission': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c', 'missionTasks': ['b58040d9-4f2b-4bfe-a94-6ebb8d2075'], 'files': ['Sec23183-ff42-4451-8dc2-1c74d612e925', '6baf4356-dbe5-4788-bf6c-b08ed83246cf', '6439bec1-0e73-4b21-a512-22876cb93991'], 'fileMetadata': ['a0933bdd-f911-472a-9932-553229123627', '92ad98e5-1291-43f8-9205-5f44ac829fe', '5345a03d-5411-4050-acbd-a0f6782656e']} gRCsView.py 28
14:39:36,140 ddhl.gRCS INFO Success Response: {'mission': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bbf33c', 'missionTasks': ['b58040d9-4f2b-4bfe-a94-6ebb8d2075'], 'files': ['Sec23183-ff42-4451-8dc2-1c74d612e925', '6baf4356-dbe5-4788-bf6c-b08ed83246cf', '6439bec1-0e73-4b21-a512-22876cb93991'], 'fileMetadata': ['a0933bdd-f911-472a-9932-553229123627', '92ad98e5-1291-43f8-9205-5f44ac829fe', '5345a03d-5411-4050-acbd-a0f6782656e']} gRC
```

```

11:03:24,665 ddhl.mRCS INFO Start - Post Mission Specific Data: /apis/Mission/mRCS_VIAD_DRONE/Installation/mRCSView.py 31
2022-10-26 11:03:24,665 ddhl.mRCS INFO User: USE-GRVC mRCSView.py 32
11:03:24,665 ddhl.mRCS INFO User: USE-GRVC mRCSView.py 32
2022-10-26 11:03:24,677 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Mission By SyncID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/Properties?syncId=222234320133329900470 dms.py 77
11:03:24,679 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Mission By SyncID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/Properties?syncId=222234320133329900470 dms.py 77
2022-10-26 11:03:24,937 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Mission By Mission Task ID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bf33c/MissionTask/ dms.py 84
11:03:24,937 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Get Mission By Mission Task ID - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bf33c/MissionTask/ dms.py 84
2022-10-26 11:03:25,204,204 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: ./tempFiles/1b310f17-0d76-4b60-a066-fbc840b97ba/Localization_telemetry_b58040d9.csv dms.py 126
11:03:25,204 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: ./tempFiles/1b310f17-0d76-4b60-a066-fbc840b97ba/Localization_telemetry_b58040d9.csv dms.py 126
2022-10-26 11:03:25,623,623 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/94dfe763-2732-40f8-abdd-f4c86689b8d5/', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '156336', 'OriginalName': 'localization_telemetry_b58040d9.csv', 'Content': 'mRCS - localization_telemetry', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-10-26T11:03:25Z', 'object_id': 'b58040d9-4f2b-4bfe-af94-6ebb8ed12075', 'content_type': '12'} dms.py 161
11:03:25,623 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/94dfe763-2732-40f8-abdd-f4c86689b8d5/', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '156336', 'OriginalName': 'localization_telemetry_b58040d9.csv', 'Content': 'mRCS - localization_telemetry', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-10-26T11:03:25Z', 'object_id': 'b58040d9-4f2b-4bfe-af94-6ebb8ed12075', 'content_type': '12'} dms.py 161
2022-10-26 11:03:26,011,11 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: ./tempFiles/1b310f17-0d76-4b60-a066-fbc840b97ba/installation_log_b58040d9.csv dms.py 126
11:03:26,11 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/ - Body: ./tempFiles/1b310f17-0d76-4b60-a066-fbc840b97ba/installation_log_b58040d9.csv dms.py 126
2022-10-26 11:03:26,374,374 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/c22a0f2e-56b8-4163-89cc-a52f01668b13/', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '74', 'OriginalName': 'installation_log_b58040d9.csv', 'Content': 'mRCS - installation_log', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-10-26T11:03:26Z', 'object_id': 'b58040d9-4f2b-4bfe-af94-6ebb8ed12075', 'content_type': '12'} dms.py 161
11:03:26,374 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Post File Metadata - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/FileMetadata/ - Body: {'URL': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/c22a0f2e-56b8-4163-89cc-a52f01668b13/', 'MimeType': 'text/csv', 'Size': '74', 'OriginalName': 'installation_log_b58040d9.csv', 'Content': 'mRCS - installation_log', 'CreationDatetime': '2022-10-26T11:03:26Z', 'object_id': 'b58040d9-4f2b-4bfe-af94-6ebb8ed12075', 'content_type': '12'} dms.py 161
2022-10-26 11:03:26,690,690 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Patch Mission - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/ - Body: {'UniqueID': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bf33c', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-07-25T04:28:22Z', 'Properties': {'SyncID': '1333299004', 'Completed': True, 'Sensors': [{'uid': '14506157-8937-4a46-a895-352f091be59', 'Name': 'Lidar', 'Description': 'RPLIDAR A3', 'tf': {'Translation': {'x': 0.0, 'y': 0.0, 'z': -0.36}, 'Rotation': {'x': 0.0, 'y': 0.0, 'z': 0.0, 'w': 1.0}}]}, 'Map': 'alona.2021.03.11.pcd']} dms.py 98
11:03:26,690 ddhl.dms INFO DMS: Patch Mission - URL: https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/Mission/ - Body: {'UniqueID': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bf33c', 'ExecutionDatetime': '2022-07-25T04:28:22Z', 'Properties': {'SyncID': '1333299004', 'Completed': True, 'Sensors': [{'uid': '14506157-8937-4a46-a895-352f091be59', 'Name': 'Lidar', 'Description': 'RPLIDAR A3', 'tf': {'Translation': {'x': 0.0, 'y': 0.0, 'z': -0.36}, 'Rotation': {'x': 0.0, 'y': 0.0, 'z': 0.0, 'w': 1.0}}]}, 'Map': 'alona.2021.03.11.pcd']} dms.py 98
2022-10-26 11:03:27,017,17 ddhl.mRCS INFO Success Response: {'mission': 'edc0638d-7c99-4893-b9d9-06f312bf33c', 'images': [], 'localization_telemetry': [{'fileMetadataID': '81e0f21b-f21b-4329-9655-293deb8309b7', 'url': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/c22a0f2e-56b8-4163-89cc-a52f01668b13/'}], 'ags_telemetry': [], 'installation_log': [{'fileMetadataID': 'bd2deccf-794c-4b54-9083-60035a2c200', 'url': 'https://isense-piloting.iccs.gr/apis/File/c22a0f2e-56b8-4163-89cc-a52f01668b13/'}], 'haptic_data': [], 'objects_found': []} mRCSView.py 46
11:03:27,17 ddhl.mRCS INFO End - Post Mission Specific Data: /apis/Mission/mRCS_VIAD_DRONE/Installation/mRCSView.py 47
11:03:27,17 ddhl.mRCS INFO End - Post Mission Specific Data: /apis/Mission/mRCS_VIAD_DRONE/Installation/mRCSView.py 47

```

Figure 135. gRCS uploads the generic data to the DMS through the DDHL.

As described, The DDHL succeeded in instantiating the Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and Inspection Tasks and uploading both the generic and the mission specific data to the DMS concerning the Viaduct surveying target installation use case performed by the VIAD_DRONE robot.

With respect to the sensor box installation since it was not fully demonstrated in this first pilot experiments, no complete mission data was generated and transferred to the DMS through the DDHL.

4.5.3. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – VIAD DRONE (Bearing Inspection use case)

The DDHL as part of the I&M PILOTING platform is responsible to obtain the Mission Specific Data originated by the VIAD_DRONE robotic system and upload it to the DMS.

Figure 136. Workflow diagram – Post Mission Data (VIAD_DRONE).

As already described in Section 2.2.3, the gRCS communicates with the DDHL prior to the execution of the Mission to instantiate both Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and post the generic data to the DMS.

Progressing, the VIAD_DRONE robotic system uploads the mission specific data (Table 46) to the DDHL enclosed in a compressed folder. The DDHL is responsible to unzip the folder, transform and post the data under the right Mission by utilizing the APIs of the DMS., as illustrated in Figure 136. In order to find the Mission created by the gRCS and to correlate the data with, the DDHL uses the SyncID property included in the mRCS data. As described in Section 2.2.3, SyncID is a property included in both generic and mission specific data towards the synchronization of the data.

In case of failure, the DDHL will roll back the changes that have been made to the database and eventually inform the VIAD_DRONE about the failure.

Table 46. Mission Specific Data provided by VIAD_DRONE - Viaduct bearing inspection use case.

File Type	Description	Example Data Format
Pictures	Individual files in a specific folder	
Pictures Metadata	Metadata for each taken picture	picture_file_name, timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w, mm_per_pixel, distance
Localisation Telemetry	Localization stamp and pose from the fusion sensor	timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w

	<p>solution. Origin referred to the viaduct 3D model</p>	
<p>Config File</p>	<p>Configuration file with the sensor configuration of the robotic platform. This file provides the sensor list and the physical offset between them as well as inspection information (eg: Inspection Plan UUID, SyncID)</p>	<pre> { "startDate": "2022_01_04-09_51_12", "endDate": "2022_02_07-09_51_12", "syncId": "9999", "uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionPlanUuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionTaskUuids": ["XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX"], "type": "visual", "map": "alora_2021_03_11.pcd", "files": { "pictures_metadata": "pictures_metadata.csv", "pictures_folder": "pictures", "telemetry_data": "localization_telemetry.csv" }, "sensors": [], "pictures": { "folder": "pictures", "sensor_uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "format": "jpg", "size": { "width": 6000, "height": 4000 }, "fov": { "horizontal": 32.7, "vertical": 21.8 } } } </pre>

5. Tunnels Experiments

Egnatia Odos AE (EOAE) is the end user representing Tunnel Inspection operations on actual parts of the transport network. For the purposes of this formal round of experiments, two different tunnels were used by the consortium as first deployment and integration exercises. The experiments lasted for 9 days and EOAE with the support of INLECOM and the rest of the partners. The event was fully organised by the EOAE and INLECOM personnel, where EOAE was also responsible for the actual infrastructures provision, participants' safety, lanes closure, access and delivery as well as most aspects of the pilots validation, KPIs and feedback to the technical team

5.1. Description of Tunnel Location

The part of Egnatia motorway selected for these experiments, was the tunnel of Metsovo (in Ioannina) and a drainage tunnel very close to this one. These two tunnels were selected as i) the Metsovo tunnel indicates some interesting inspection points while is in full traffic and can represent traffic scenarios and realistic tunnel inspections and ii) the drainage tunnel used as a reference tunnel without any traffic (so experiments can run in safety) while indicates a concrete tunnel without internal lining that could represent tunnels under construction.

Figure 137. Exact area of inspections.

There were various different scenarios used, that are detailed below, that focused on i) experiment on various robotic missions execution, ii) test procedures, mechanisms and configurations in real settings, iii) validate the system, create feedback and measure KPIs. The different scenarios used were created much before the experiments to make sure that all above, but also the tunnel and realistic settings (traffic, weather conditions, access), together with the robotic system peculiarities are fully covered and carefully considered before the actual visit.

The first type of validation scenarios included preliminary capabilities and functions validation to measure robot dimensions, weight, clearance from the road and check that a suspension is enabled and batteries on place and test basic functions (onboard safety lights, remote emergency shut down and manual control override). Other scenarios focused on the autonomous navigation such as placing the robot at the crosspassage near the defected/under inspection area, robot autonomously navigates in the tunnel through a set of waypoints while avoiding obstacles. In the same approach there were some other more inspection focused scenarios for the sensors activation as an actual mission execution. These included, robot autonomously navigating in the tunnel through a set of waypoints,

robot stops at each point of interest and triggers cameras to take photos of the area, the robot automatically controlling the pan and tilt mechanism to take all images on one side of the tunnel, captured images are associated with a location and a timestamp, images are viewed through the ground control station and time is automatically tracked in the mission data. Finally, some scenarios were created to test the 3D laser scanning mechanism including the robot autonomously navigating in the tunnel through a set of waypoints, the robot stops at each point of interest and performs 3D laser scanning (automatic triggering of the laser scanning device), and time is automatically tracked in the mission data.

As two different tunnels were used, the scenarios above were adapted and organized in means to solve the operational difficulties of real tunnel inspection (some times in traffic). As described below, the scenarios were separated in road and drainage tunnel scenarios with local and general tunnel inspections for each.

Figure 138. road tunnel experiments (left) and the drainage tunnel experiments (right).

5.2. General Tunnel inspection

The general inspection experiments were performed on both tunnels. First tests were performed in the drainage tunnel since the preparation of the experiments are easier, and also the lack of traffic facilitates the execution of initial tests. Then, the general inspection experiments were performed on a 60m distance area inside the road tunnel at Metsovo with real traffic. The area is picked for the pilot due to the known defects that exist (Spallation/Rebar exposure areas and cracks). Images were captured, depicting one of the side walls of the tunnel, as we had access to one of the two traffic lanes for the purposes of the pilot.

For the tunnel inspection, we need to consider that similar tests were conducted for both General and Local inspections when it comes to the main ground robot CART. A dedicated section of Local Inspection will focus on the drone tests later on.

For both tunnels, and in relation with the General tunnel inspection, the following experiments were performed

- Robot capabilities and function verification
- Autonomous navigation
- Inspection mission (Image capturing)
- Inspection mission (3D laser scanning)

Robot capabilities and function verification

- *Measure robot dimensions, weight, clearance from the road and check that a suspension is enabled and batteries on place.*
- *Test basic functions (onboard safety lights, remote emergency shut down and manual control override).*

Physical verification was taken for granted as per a first visual inspection and while setting up the robot. Some highlights in this regard:

- The electric cart is smaller than a regular car. While in a road lane, there is space enough to manoeuvre.
- The weight consideration was affecting mainly the transportation to the site. The total weight is less than a regular trailer can handle without problem and this was checked as well.
- The suspension requirement came in place specifically for the rough and steep terrain. We could validate this issue while accessing the drainage tunnel.
- Batteries performed better than expected, as the robot was never below 50%.
- Control override and remote emergency was checked with the very first run. E-stop works ok and robot can be driven anytime provided the driver is in the driving seat and MANUAL mode is switched.
- Safety signalling works ok, however the pulsing light can affect the pictures and AI defect recognition. The ability to change its position (as it attaches by magnetism) proved to be very helpful.

Figure 139. CART robotic vehicle in drainage tunnel.

Autonomous navigation

- *The robot is placed at start point in the tunnel.*
- *The robot autonomously navigates in the tunnel.*
- *No GNSS coverage.*
- *No fixed lighting.*

The navigation system generates a map in the form of a 3D point cloud. The map contains LIDAR points with high density as well as a sparse set of globally unique landmarks. The landmarks allow the system to relocalize and to correct for drift along the length of the tunnel. These landmarks are today as set of APRIL tags that we stick on the walls of the tunnel with roughly 20m between.

Figure 140. APRIL tag stuck to wall of drainage tunnel.

In order to test the mapping and localization functionalities of the navigation, data gathering missions were performed along the length of both tunnels creating a map. See an example map from the drainage tunnel in Figure 141, and an example of the map generated on the road tunnel in Figure 142.

Figure 141. Map from drainage tunnel, geometry in white, landmarks in blue and carts trajectory in red (left). Real-time map generated in the drainage tunnel by CART (right).

Figure 142. Example map from road tunnel (grid size 10m) landmarks in blue (left). CART in road tunnel during navigation experiments (right).

The results that can be highlighted are:

- The navigation system creates a map that is geometrically consistent with the environment.
- Localization in existing maps works well.
- During map creation the system seems to underestimate the length of the traversed distance, resulting in a map approx. 10% shorter than what manual measurements would indicate.

With respect to the autonomous navigation, first it was tested basic missions where the robot was just commanded to cover certain distance at a stable speed. The objective here was to receive a waypoint and then command the robot to such point but with different constraints, such as maintaining the robot always at the same distance from the wall (this feature is critical for a quality data retrieval). The wall following feature was tuned in order to use a specific speed of 0.5m/s with waypoints at 4 to 5 meters apart. With such distance, it was successfully tested that autonomous navigation system the works ok in the road tunnel. However, the drainage tunnel presents a significant slope that complicated the navigation system since CART vehicle does only counts with the break coming from the engine itself. This aspect will be considered in order to improve the navigation system of the CART robotic vehicle, and being able to also cope with tunnels with slope.

An additional challenge was introduced with the 1.5m steps data request in order to obtain images of the tunnel with enough overlapping for the visual inspection (see next section), which then needed a different configuration as the Ackermann kinematics needs a more aggressive action in order to reach goals with shorter distances. The current navigation system does not cope well with this requirement, and the navigation was not smooth enough. Then, this aspect will be also covered during the improvements of the navigation functionality of the CART robotic vehicle during the second development phase.

Inspection mission (image capturing)

- *The robot is placed at start point in the tunnel near the defected/under inspection area.*
- *The robot autonomously navigates in the tunnel through a set of waypoints.*
- *Robot stops at each point of interest and triggers cameras to take photos of the area.*
- *The robot automatically controls the pan and tilt mechanism and the arm to take images of the entire left side of the tunnel.*
- *Time is automatically tracked in the mission data.*

This experiment makes use of the autonomous navigation functionality that was previously commented, but due to problems on the SW that was in charge of automatically triggering the photographic camera during the experiments, these tests were not completed fully automatically.

With respect to the image capture procedure, and since it was the first time in the project that the CART robotic vehicle easy in the tunnel, distances and working steps were defined in an experimental way. The results were that camera was positioned around 1.8m from the wall, and then considering the overlapping and a convenient pixel size, pictures should be made each 1.5m. With these constraints in the navigation, two different approaches were proposed:

- For the robot to hold position while the camera takes 4 pictures overlapping in vertical (considering that the inspection load interferes in the overhead field of view, the last picture is done lifting the column and with a deviation in order to look at the crown in the previous step), and just then advance to the next waypoint 1.5m ahead in order to repeat the process.
- For the robot to hold the camera and lifting mechanism in one of the relevant position to take just one picture at a time, and proceed each 1.5m for the length of the tunnel, having to repeat the full tunnel recording for each picture position.

Both approaches were tested and data gathered (including timing) in order to define the best procedure, after this first experience, for the final pilot experiments in 2023.

With respect to the results, the general visual inspection was performed on a 60m distance area inside the road tunnel at Metsovo. The area is picked for the pilot due to the known defects that exist (Spallation/Rebar exposure areas and cracks). Images were captured, depicting one of the side walls of the tunnel, as we had access to one of the two traffic lanes for the purposes of the pilot.

In total 133 images were collected depicting the area of interest. The images were captured in 3 different heights, for every 1.5m in the covered area and with at a working distance of 1.8m, this includes an overlap of 20%. The highest captured point being at around 4m with the robotics' arm extended to its limit at 3m. An inspection image covers an area of 2.5m x 1.6m and with a resolution of 9504x6336 pixels.

Using the AI-based defect detection system on the captured inspection images, we are able to first train the system on the collected images and then to extract the potential defected areas. This includes the areas of interest with the spallation/rebar exposure as well as cracks that are in the area. Below some examples of the system are shown.

Figure 143. Input and predicted potential defected areas from the defect detection system on the images collected from the Metsovo road tunnel.

Inspection mission (3D laser scanning)

- *The robot is placed at start point in the tunnel near the defected/under inspection area.*
- *The robot autonomously navigates in the tunnel through a set of waypoints.*
- *Robot stops at each point of interest and performs 3D laser scanning.*
- *Time is automatically tracked in the mission data.*

As part of the general inspection, the FARO scanner was used at the tunnel experiments for 3D scan capturing to illustrate defects with a very high accuracy (millimeter). Although the scan capturing is related to the local inspection of the tunnels, the experiments took place in both the road and the drainage tunnel. These experiments were performed only using the CART robot due to the scanner weight and size (difficult to be carried by the drone).

Regarding the scanner resolution, it was decided to use a 43.7Mpxs/3x quality. This was decided providing 6.1mm (cloud point to point) at 10m. In mind of the 1m distance from the wall, the actual system accuracy (towards the lane side of interest) was 0.6mm which seemed more than adequate for our system construction. A quality of 3x was selected to maximize the scan quality while keeping the scan time quite low. These settings were later modified to provide a similar accuracy with a lower precision but also lower inspection time (<3 minutes) for the usage in the actual and complicated CART robot missions. Colour preferences were also modified and tested to test the system accuracy with and without colour scanning. This seemed to not affect accuracy but improve visual perception of the situation at the inspected points.

Following the scope of this mission, the 3D laser scanning scenarios were executed during this set of experiments. The inspection mission included stopping of the robot (CART) at particular points and then performing 3D laser scan measurements. The validation scope was to test the interfacing of the robotic system (CART) with the scanner interface in order to execute the scans fully driven by the robotic mission.

Some indicative examples of the local inspection using the laser scanner are presented below. Figure 144 shows the collected point cloud at mm accuracy while Figure 145. shows the rendered image of the tunnel reconstructed in 3D. Different measurements and local calculations can be done with various ways and software packages.

Figure 144. Collected point cloud at mm accuracy.

Figure 145. Rendered image of the tunnel reconstructed in 3D.

Similarly, a 3D laser inspection was performed in the drainage tunnel as well. Some indicative results are presented below:

Figure 146. Rendered image of the drainage tunnel reconstructed in 3D.

5.3. Local Tunnel inspection

The objective of this use case is to perform a more thorough inspection of the tunnel, using two robotic systems: one ground robot and one aerial robot. The ground robot stops at some points of interest where potential defects have been previously detected. Then, the aerial robot takes accurate measurements of these defects, even detecting new ones, and inspects those difficult to access locations for the ground robot. Since the ground robot part is very similar to the general inspection, this section will be focused on the drone part.

Figure 147 depicts the procedure performed by the aerial robot in the tunnel local inspection missions. In short, the aerial robot takes off from the starting point, located on ground robot, and navigates to some approach points, close to the tunnel walls. Here, the aerial robot takes pictures of some detected defects (inspection points) which allows the detailed visual assessment of the tunnel. The images are captured at a specific distance from the defects, which is estimated in order to provide an appropriate level of detail for the best performance of the AI detection algorithms. Finally, the robot comes back to the start point and lands on the UGV.

Figure 147. Tunnel local inspection procedure developed by the TTRDRONE.

Regarding the local inspection conducted by the aerial robot, two different scenarios were designed for the first pilot experiments:

- Scenario 1: the aerial robot performs the visual local inspection of the drainage tunnel, without being tethered from the ground robot. The objective is to test the inspection functionality and the safe autonomous GNSS-denied navigation.
- Scenario 2: the aerial robot flights tethered from the ground robot, visiting some inspection locations but without taking images. The main objective is to test the tether system.

The aforementioned approach was designed for the demonstration of the developed system functionalities, in particular, for the KPIs evaluation and the requirements validation of the use case in a real tunnel, presented in Section 6. and Annex I: Requirements Validation. The two designed scenarios and the results obtained in each of them are described in detail below.

Scenario 1: Aerial robot inspection mission

The objective of this scenario was to perform a visual local inspection of the drainage tunnel by using an aerial robot, taking high-quality images of previously detected defects of the environment, close to them and using image stabilization devices. These pictures enhance the accuracy of the general inspection measurements, providing more level of detail of the defects and also providing new ones, above all in those difficult to access locations for the ground robot. Moreover, the aim of this scenario was to test and demonstrate the robustness and reliability of the tunnel local inspection procedures carried out by the developed aerial robot and the repeatability of the obtained results. As the aim was to demonstrate the aerial robot related functionalities, the ground robot was not involved in this scenario for the first pilots.

A map of the drainage tunnel was built with a Leica Total Station and uploaded to the IVP following the same procedure as in Section 2. . The map, shown in Figure 148, is a point cloud that contains

information of about the first 150 meters of the tunnel, having more level of detail in its first 60 meters which was the area of the tunnel where the first pilot experiments of both scenarios were executed. In order to perform a good local inspection, the inspection points should be accurately located in the environment for allowing the robot to visit and capture them, otherwise, the captured images could not contain information of the defects to be inspected or could contain only information of part of them. For that, a precise map of the environment is required. The accuracy of the built map of the drainage tunnel, about 2 centimeters (the accuracy of the total station device), accomplished the required precision for precisely locating the inspection points in the environment and hence, enabled a good inspection plan design and a good local inspection performance.

Figure 148. Drainage tunnel map built during the first pilot experiments. It was uploaded to the IVP web portal.

Next, the inspection plans for the experiments were designed in the IVP following the steps described in Section 2. . Qualified personnel from the use case end-user, Egnatia ODOS, visually analyzed the state of the drainage tunnel walls and selected some interesting defects to be inspected by the aerial robot. Also, the most common types of tunnel defects detailed in Deliverable 3.1 were taken into account for the design of the inspection plans. Considering all this information, two different inspection plans were designed.

On the one hand, the first inspection plan (Mission-5), depicted in Figure 149-left, involved five different inspection points in the tunnel, shown as four yellow points located in the left and the upper walls of the tunnel, and in blue in the right wall. Meanwhile, the second inspection plan (Mission-8) was a longer mission which involved the inspection of eight different locations. The map of the drainage tunnel shown below was downloaded to the gRCS where the entire missions were planned following the same procedure as in Section 2. . Figure 149-right shows the complete Mission-5 downloaded and running in the gRCS. It commanded the robot from the ground in real time and also monitored the telemetry of the drone, the battery state and consumption, the development state of the inspection, the time of the inspection procedure, etc. Besides, the gRCS autonomously controlled the position of the aerial robot for making it to capture the inspection points from the specified distance. Additionally, it also controlled the position of the gimbal taking into account both the position of the aerial robot and the location of the inspection points in the tunnel, and commanded the image capture with the inspection camera when the aerial robot was at the approach point for each inspection location.

Figure 149. Inspection plan created in the IVP for the Mission-5 (left) and the downloaded mission in the gRCS (right).

The aerial robot used in the Scenario 1 is shown in Figure 150-left. The CAD design of this platform and each of its components are described in the Deliverable 4.1. The TTDRONE aerial frame built is the same as in the designed CAD model described in the document, as well as the used models of the gimbal and the inspection camera devices, on top of the robot, and the electromagnets, installed on each leg. They are used to attach the aerial robot to the metallic take-off and landing platform, shown in Figure 150, when the ground robot is navigating in the tunnel. On the other hand, and to achieve the goals of the first demonstration experiments, some hardware improvements and component changes were performed in TTDRONE. First, the configuration of the platform was changed from a quad-rotor to an octa-rotor configuration. It aimed the improvement of the flight stabilization considering the high payload added by the gimbal and the camera on top of the robot, and also it allows the aerial robot to carry more powerful batteries and thus, enlarge time endurance to perform the inspection missions. For the Scenario 1 experiments, the power module was not installed in the robot since the objective was to validate the inspection perception capability. The perception system was comprised of two LIDAR sensors, placed at the front and right side of the robot, and a distance beacon sensor, at the rear of the robot.

Figure 150. TTDRONE hardware setup used (left) and the 3D printed structure built (right) for the Scenario 1 experiments.

Figure 151 shows some pictures of the TTDRONE performing the tunnel local inspection experiments. The two abovementioned designed missions (Mission-5 and Mission-8) were executed several times and in different days and conditions to test and demonstrate the robustness and the reliability of the developed system, as well as the repeatability and the accuracy of the obtained visual

inspection results. After take-off, TTDRONE autonomously navigated in the tunnel and captured the inspection points defined in each executed inspection plan. The distance from the walls at which the pictures were captured by the aerial robot was set in the gRCS. This distance was iteratively and accurately adjusted in the real environment for the best performance of the AI detection algorithms. The gimbal device was autonomously controlled by the gRCS considering the robot pose and orientation with respect to each of the defects to be captured. The camera capture was also controlled autonomously by the gRCS.

Figure 151. TTDRONE performing the visual inspection of some defects of the drainage tunnel in the first pilot experiments.

As detailed in Deliverable 5.1, the perception system for accurately estimating the aerial robot localization in the tunnel was designed considering the deployment of some sensors on the surface of the ground robot. As the ground robot was not involved in the Scenario 1 experiments, the 3D printed structure shown in Figure 150-right was built with specific dimensions that allowed to locate four beacon sensors in the environment as they were installed in the front side of the UGV. Figure 152-top shows in blue the TTDRONE localization estimation during one of the first pilot flights in each axis and in red the aerial robot localization estimated with a Total Station, used as ground truth. Figure 152-bottom depicts the errors of the aerial robot localization in each axis, being the mean error in the x axis of about 0.1103 cm, 0.0648 cm in the y axis and 0.0451 cm in the z axis, highlighting the high accuracy of the aerial robot localization estimation in the drainage tunnel, critical to perform autonomous and accurate inspection missions.

Figure 152. VIAD-DRONE robot localization estimation in blue against the ground truth localization estimated with a Leica Total station in red (top) and the related localization errors (bottom).

Figure 153 shows some of the visual local inspection results obtained in the first pilot experiments, in particular, from the execution of the Mission-8 inspection plan. The depicted images were taken at 1.7 meters from the inspection points. Images on the left column were obtained in a different flight from the right column images. As it can be noticed, the high-quality images contain information of the defects that should be captured in each of them, validating the high accuracy of the aerial robot localization estimation, as well as the precise control of the gimbal device taking into account the position and orientation of the aerial robot with respect to each defect. Moreover, by comparing the respective images of each column, the repeatability of both the TTDRONE localization estimation and the execution of the inspection missions were validated as well as the robustness and reliability of the flights and the developed system functionalities in a real scenario.

Figure 153. Results from the tunnel local inspection obtained with the TTDRONE. Images of the left column were captured in a different flight from the images of the right column. Both flights were commanded by the gRCS following the same designed inspection plan.

Additionally, as detailed above, the distance from the walls at which the TTDRONE flew was also tested in the drainage tunnel in order to provide the AI detection algorithms with the appropriate level of detail of the defects to achieve their best performance. Images collected in Figure 154 were captured at different distances from the defects, in particular at 1.3 meters (Figure 154-left) and at 1.7 meters (Figure 154-right), demonstrating the availability of the TTDRONE to take pictures close to the inspection points. The aerial robot position was precisely controlled in real time, allowing it to capture the inspection points despite the aerodynamic effects produced by the proximity to the tunnel structure.

Figure 154. Pictures of the same defect of the tunnel gathered by the aerial robot from 1.3 meters (left) and 1.7 meters (right) of distance.

Concluding with the integrated workflow of the PILOTING project, all the visual local inspection results were uploaded to the IVP where the operator can assess the captured defects of the drainage tunnel. Figure 155 depicts the inspection results obtained from one of the experiments performed in the drainage tunnel. The executed aerial robot trajectory is represented by the colored lines. The blue arrows show the location from which the defects were captured and the gimbal orientation used. In addition, each inspection point contains its own captured image, as it is shown in the figure for one of the inspection points that has been selected.

Figure 155. Results obtained from the execution of one of the visual local inspection plans. They were uploaded to the IVP after the first pilots.

Finally, preliminary results from using the AI-based defect identification system are encouraging. The system is able to detect and extract defected areas of the tunnel. The identified defects are:

- Spallation
- Rebar exposure
- Cracks

- Efflorescence

Below some examples of the obtained results are shown.

Figure 156. Input and predicted defected areas from the defect identification system on the images collected from the Metsovo drainage tunnel.

Scenario 2: Tethering tests

The objective of this scenario was to demonstrate that TTDRONE was able to reliably flight tethered from the ground robot in a real tunnel. Thus, these experiments involved the TTDRONE and the UGV robots. Both robots were joined by the tether system, which was installed in the space of the UGV reserved for the copilot, as it is shown in Figure 157. The cable passed through the roof of the UGV and the take-off and landing platform to the power module installed in the underside of the aerial robot. Figure 158 shows the procedure for the execution of the Scenario 2 experiments. As depicted in the figure, the aerial robot will navigate in the environment and will get close to some inspection points of the tunnel walls. When all the planned inspection points are visited, the robot will land on the ground robot and the mission will be completed. In the first pilots, tethering flights did not involve capturing the inspection points visited by the aerial robot.

Figure 157. TTDRONE hardware setup for the Scenario 2 experiments. Also, the tethered system is shown.

The platform used in this scenario is also shown in Figure 157. In this case, the TTDRONE used a different hardware configuration than in Scenario 1. As this scenario was focused on the validation of the tethered system, the image capture was not required. Hence, the gimbal and the inspection camera, as well as the on-board computer were removed from the platform for their safety and also for reducing the payload of the TTDRONE during the tethering tests. Instead, the power module of the tethered system was installed on-board. In the first pilot experiments, the platform was not powered by this module but by the safe battery. This development will be carried out for the final version of the platform as well as the merge of the Scenario 1 and Scenario 2 hardware configuration of the platform.

In this scenario the flights were fully performed in manual mode, so the inspection plans were not required to be designed in the IVP, neither that they were uploaded and planned in the gRCS. Thus, no post-mission data was generated from the Scenario 2 experiments as they were focused on the validation of the tethering flights. Figure 158 collects some pictures of the experiments. It was demonstrated the ability of TTDRONE to flight tethered from the ground robot. Moreover, the flights were reliable and robust. For the second pilot experiments, the aerial robot will be powered by the tether system and also the platform will comprise only one hardware setup. The objective of the first pilots, the validation of all the functionalities of the system, was reached. This validation will be further described in Section 6. and Annex I: Requirements Validation.

Figure 158. The TTDRONE performing a local inspection experiment tethered to the UGV.

5.4. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform – Data transmission, transformation and storing

5.4.1. Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform - CART

The DDHL as part of the I&M PILOTING platform is responsible to obtain the Mission Specific Data originating from the CART robotic system and upload it to the DMS. Although the DDHL is fully integrated with the CART robotic system, the problems emerged during the tunnel inspection made it impossible to upload the data to the DMS through the DDHL. We intend to re - execute this scenario in the next integration meeting.

The following paragraphs analyze the input data provided by the CART robotic system and describe the process followed by the DDHL to transform, harmonize, and upload the data to the DMS.

Table 47. Mission Specific Data to be provided by CART- General tunnel inspection use case.

File Type	Description	Example Data Format
Pictures	Individual files in a specific folder	
Pictures Metadata	Metadata for each taken picture	picture_file_name, timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w, mm_per_pixel, distance
Localization Telemetry	Localization stamp and pose from the fusion sensor	timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w

	solution without GPS information.	
<p>Config File</p>	<p>Configuration file with the sensor configuration of the robotic platform. This file provides the sensor list and the physical offset between them as well as inspection information (eg: Inspection Plan UUID, SyncID)</p>	<pre> { "startDate": "2022_05_12-10_37_43", "endDate": "2022_05_12-10_55_19", "syncId": "52954881", "uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionPlanUuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionTaskUuids": ["XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX"], "type": "visual", "map": "name_AAAA_MM_DD.pcd", "files": { "pictures_folder": "sony_bea86486-8f08-11ec-b909-0242ac120002", "pictures_metadata": "camera_stamp_pose.csv", "telemetry_data": "telemetry_stamp_pose.csv" }, "sensors": [], "pictures": { "sensor_uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXX", "format": "jpg", "size": { "width": 9504, "height": 6336 }, "fov": { "horizontal": 23.9, "vertical": 16.1 } } } </pre>

As already described in Section 2.2.3, the gRCS communicates with the DDHL prior to the execution of the Mission to instantiate both Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and the Inspection Tasks and post the generic data to the DMS.

Progressing, the CART robotic system uploads the mission specific data (Table 47) to the DDHL enclosed in a compressed folder. The DDHL is responsible to unzip the folder, transform and post the data under the right Mission by utilizing the APIs of the DMS., as illustrated in Figure 159. In order to find the Mission created by the gRCS and to correlate the data with, the DDHL uses the SyncID property included in the mRCS data. As described in Section 2.2.3, SyncID is a property included in both generic and mission specific data towards the synchronization of the data.

In case of failure, the DDHL will roll back the changes that have been made to the database and eventually inform the CART robot about the failure.

Figure 159. Workflow diagram – Post Mission Data (CART).

5.4.2. *Interconnection with the PILOTING I&M platform - TTDRONE*

The DDHL as part of the I&M PILOTING platform is responsible to obtain the Mission Specific Data originating from the TTDRONE robotic system and upload it to the DMS.

The TTDRONE robot successfully performed 2 Missions regarding the tunnel local inspection use case. The Mission specific data has been successfully uploaded to the DMS through the DDHL. Below you can find an example of the unique identifiers of the objects created on the DMS regarding the Inspection Plans, the Missions, and the Mission Tasks.

Table 48. DMS Information regarding TTDRONE Missions.

Inspection Plan	Mission	Mission Tasks	SyncID
22520ddb-83b7-4299-a8a9-8ebf365785ee	415a75d1-9818-458e-b786-8094d226f850	d1307047-056b-466a-9815-ffbdffbf7c13	1065449314
		15b375a6-e848-45de-aa50-6f8a7f70c014	
		1173c05c-2f9d-4bbb-bca9-fb831cd2de1a	
		807eb9cc-7379-42fa-a994-d41084541419	
		4d8f8ea5-362c-4075-8670-f312a163bae7	

Figure 160. Workflow diagram – Post Mission Data (TTDRONE).

As already described in Section 2.2.3, the gRCS communicates with the DDHL prior to the execution of the Mission to instantiate the Mission and Mission Tasks with respect to the Inspection Plan and Inspection Tasks and post the generic data to the DMS.

Progressing, the TTDRONE robotic system uploads the mission specific (Table 49) data to the DDHL enclosed in a compressed folder. The DDHL is responsible to unzip the folder, transform and post the data under the right Mission by utilizing the APIs of the DMS., as illustrated in the Figure 160. In order to find the Mission created by the gRCS and to correlate the data with, the DDHL uses the SyncID property included in the mRCS data. As described in Section 2.2.3, SyncID is a property included in both generic and mission specific data towards the synchronization of the data.

In case of failure, the DDHL will roll back the changes that have been made to the database and eventually inform the TTDRONE robot about the failure.

Table 49. Mission Specific Data provided by TTDRONE in the local tunnel inspection use case.

File Type	Description	Example Data Format
Pictures	Individual files in a specific folder	
Pictures Metadata	Metadata for each taken picture	picture_file_name, timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w, mm_per_pixel, distance

<p>Localization Telemetry</p>	<p>Localization stamp and pose from the fusion sensor solution without GPS information. Origin referred to the viaduct 3D model</p>	<p>timestamp, inspection_task_uuid, p_x, p_y, p_z, q_x, q_y, q_z, q_w</p>
<p>Config File</p>	<p>Configuration file with the sensor configuration of the robotic platform. This file provides the sensor list and the physical offset between them as well as inspection information (eg: Inspection Plan Uuid, SyncID)</p>	<pre>{ "startDate": "2022_01_04-09_51_12", "endDate": "2022_02_07-09_51_12", "syncId": 8200, "uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionPlanUuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX", "inspectionTaskUuids": ["XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX", "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX"], "type": "visual", "files": { "pictures_metadata": "pictures_metadata.csv", "pictures_folder": "pictures", "telemetry_data": "localization_telemetry.csv" }, "sensors": [], "pictures": { "folder": "pictures", "sensor_uuid": "XXXXXXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXX-XXXXXXXXXXXXXXXX", "format": "jpg", "size": { "width": 6000, "height": 4000 }, "fov": { "horizontal": 32.7, "vertical": 21.8 } } }</pre>

Seen below are indicative screenshots originating by the DDHL logs that capture the communication between the mRCS (TTDRONE), the DDHL and the DMS modules regarding the implementation of the Inspection Plans.

Table 50. Indicative screenshots from DDHL Logs.

<p>Inspection Plan UUID: 22520ddb-83b7-4299-a8a9-8ebf365785ee</p>	<p>Mission UUID: 415a75d1-9818-458e-b786-8094d226f850</p>
<p>Figure 161. gRCS fetches the Inspection Plan.</p>	

6. Evaluation of KPI's

This section summarizes the evaluation of the KPI's for each robotic solution as defined in PILOTING deliverable 3.2

6.1. Refinery Pilot

6.1.1. Tank Inspection

Table 51. Tank - Large structure business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
RLS-KPI-B-01	Inspection Time; Reduce by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with traditional inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The AEROX platform is capable of doing this. The reduction in time required to erect scaffolding around a tank structure, and possible requirement to take a tank out of service is eliminated through the use of this technology. The AEROX platform was able to achieve full line scans on the tank within minutes, with the ability to then move to complete additional line scans as necessary. Extrapolation of inspection time shows what would normally take at least a day or two can be achieved in a matter of hours.</p>		
RLS-KPI-B-02	Inspection costs: Reduce the inspection bill by at least 25% by using robotic inspection technologies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Yes, reduction in personnel involved, overall man hours, reporting time and equipment such as scaffolding and safety kit makes this a viable proposition to come in 25% under current costs.</p>		
RLS-KPI-B-03	Quality of inspection: Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Quality of inspection with the AEROX platform during the phase 1 experiments was mixed. More work needs to be done with the roller probe assembly and its measurement accuracy against hand tool measurements and calibration block equipment to increase the accuracy and reliability of the data collected. These improvements are recognized by the developers and improvements already in development for final experimentation in 2023.</p>		
RLS-KPI-B-04	Personal Safety: Reduce the number of hours of personnel working at height inspecting tank walls.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

Meets all safety criteria. The removal of personnel working at height and on scaffolding is a huge improvement on current work practices for tank inspection.

Table 52: Tank - Large structure technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
RLS-KPI-T-01	AEROX platform integrates the following hardware systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gas detection system. • Robotic device to perform contact operations. • RMCP as the end-effector. • Datalink for ground communications. 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The AEROX platform has successfully achieved full integration with all the previously listed systems. Thus, it included a gas-detecting sensor, a robotic device and RMCP (in the form of a robotic arm coupled with a crawler carrying the measuring tools), as well as the widely standardized MAVLink protocol (carrying out the role of communications datalink).</p>		
RLS-KPI-T-02	AEROX platform integrates the following software systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous/Assisted navigation system while not in contact. • Autonomous control of the aerial platform while contacting the surface. • Force control over the surface. • Emergency procedures. 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The AEROX platform has demonstrated its ability to perform autonomous flights during contact operations, where only the approach to the targeted surface is manually assisted by the pilot. Furthermore, while on state of contact, the system keeps an automatic controlled force over the surface to maintain the RMCP in contact even in case of having external disturbances (such as wind). Throughout all AEROX’s flight time, the platform was always ready to cope with the different considered emergencies (loss of communications, losing force over the surface, etc.).</p>		
RLS-KPI-T-03	The AEROX platform is shipped to Oronite plant on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. It is depalletized in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The AEROX system was indeed depalletized in a designated protected storage area from where it was later hand carried to the deployment location, but instead of an airfreighted EUR-pallet, a custom-design pallet was made for AEROX’s safe ground transportation that was a little bit larger than a EUR-pallet. Next version of AEROX will be able to be carried on a standard EUR-pallet.</p>		

RLS- KPI- T- 04	The RMCP performs ultrasonic measurements with telemetry valid to generate an inspection report.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
As it was shown in section 3. , it has been evidenced that the RMCP was capable of providing consistent telemetry in a valid format for report generation.		
RLS- KPI- T- 05	Repeatability of the measurements is possible between operations, with 10cm of precision.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Repeatability of the measurement location has been substantiated by means of a centimetre-accurate position estimator, that has been thoroughly tested against CATEC's ground truth systems. This position estimator, based on a total station, together with the 3D model of the asset and a real-time representation of the robotic vehicle position allows to repeat measurements with the desirable precision.		
RLS- KPI- T- 06	Wall thickness measurements are taken from 3mm to nominal	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The wall thickness accuracy was validated by way of comparison with a certified ultrasonic measurement hand tool in a set of different scenarios. For detailed information, please refer to Table 20. However, as it was previously commented, the wall thickness accuracy needs to be improved for next experiments.		
RLS- KPI- T- 07	The AEROX platform meets the safety, operational and best practices requirements and procedures of a standard refinery.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The AEROX platform has repeatedly shown its compliance with all the required criteria regarding its operation in refinery grounds. Also, AEROX obtained an operational authorization for the aviation authorities (the same one that it is required for commercial aerial services).		
RLS- KPI- T- 08	Ground HMIs give access to the pilot and inspector to the required systems during the operation.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Developed HMIs have demonstrated a top-level integration that has facilitated a seamless operation of the AEROX system by the inspector and the aerial robot operator.		

6.1.2. *Vessel Inspection*

Table 53. Vessel inspection business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
RV-KPI-B-01	Inspection Time; Reduce by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with traditional inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The BIKE platform can reduce the ‘inspection time’ by over 5 times based on current practices. This will be more pronounced in vessels with complex internals that are difficult for an operator to inspect manually. Preparation time for conducting a vessel inspection is not significantly reduced as vessels still require isolation, some form of manual cleaning and erection of scaffold to introduce the robot to the manway.</p>		
RV-KPI-B-02	Inspection costs: Reduce the inspection bill by at least 25% by using robotic inspection technologies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Agree that overall the use of the BIKE platform when in frequent use to conduct a number of vessel inspections on a site could reduce the cost of inspection by 25% or more, by reducing the man hours required to inspect and verify measurements.</p>		
RV-KPI-B-03	Quality of inspection: Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Quality of inspection is vastly improved through the BIKE platform. Inspection in confined spaces can be subjective but the BIKE with its 3D modelling package and localization accuracy gives more confidence in repeat and accurate inspection with standardized reporting.</p>		
RV-KPI-B-04	Personal Safety: Reduce the number of hours of personnel working in hazardous confined spaces performing internal pressure vessel inspections.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Meets all safety criteria. The removal of personnel working in confined and contaminated space is a huge improvement on current work practices for vessel inspection.</p>		

Table 54. Vessel inspection technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
RV-KPI-T-01	System shipped to Chevron Oronite’s Gonfreville plant on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. Depalletizing in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially

		<input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 3.4 - Transportation		
RV-KPI-T-02	Capability of BIKE (crawler robot) driving on the surface of carbon steel materials, where the surface is oriented vertical, upright, and overhead. A non-magnetic layer on the surface and rubberized magnetic wheels of minimum total thickness 0.2 mm are to be accounted for.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 3.4 - Mobility Capabilities and Safety Demonstration		
RV-KPI-T-03	Capability of the BIKE to be driven into the vessel by remote control from a manual deployment location on the manhole flange or its cylindrical branch. The BIKE can be driven through the transition from the manhole to the vessel shell. No infringement on the confined space of the vessel by the operator either during the manual deployment or the remote-controlled driving.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
The flange was out of scope. The requirements stated that the flange needs to be flush with the vessel head. The flange was protruding, preventing the BIKE to transition onto the vessel head. A mitigation will be worked out to prevent this issue in future tests.		
RV-KPI-T-04	Position determination accuracy in a vessel within 3 cm / 6 cm / 10 cm using a 3D model generated from provided 2D drawings of the asset. Deployment and approach to location repeated multiple times to establish repeat accuracy.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
As described in section 3.4 - Localization Demonstration and Map Verification, all tests were within 10cm. (worst case observed was 7cm deviation). With an improved environment model, 6 cm or better can be expected in a pressure vessel of similar dimensions.		
RV-KPI-T-05	Wall thickness measurements taken at a predefined location. Results stored with id number, absolute position and thickness value.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 3.4 - Inspection Demonstration. Mission data files were successfully uploaded to the Data Harmonization Layer, including location, id number and thickness values.		
RV-KPI-T-06	Multiple wall thickness point measurements arranged in a grid pattern of a predefined area size and point spacing. Results are stored with id number and thickness values, as well as absolute position of the grid origin and relative values for each measurement point.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 3.4 - Inspection Demonstration. Mission data files were successfully uploaded to the Data Harmonization Layer, including location, id number and UT scanfiles for raster scan.		

RV-KPI-T-07	Detection of dangerous concentration of flammable gases (LEL). System response of removing any ignition source and alerting the user of danger.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 3.4 - Mobility Capabilities and Safety Demonstration.		
RV-KPI-T-08	Preparation a predefined vessel area for subsequent inspection. Visual and ultrasound inspection performed before and after cleaning to establish impact on technique.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 3.4 - Surface Preparation Demonstration.		
RV-KPI-T-09	Capability of system for automatic navigation of the robot to a predetermined point of interest.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 3.4 - Inspection Demonstration.		
RV-KPI-T-10	Equipment and procedures fulfil the requirements of API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 and API 510.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The design of the inspection procedure and equipment is based on the requirements defined in API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 and API 510 and extended by the requirements of the specific application.		
RV-KPI-T-11	Performance of visual inspection of tank interior. Images stored with identification number and absolute position of both robot and location of picture center on 3D model.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 3.4 - Inspection Demonstration.		
RV-KPI-T-12	Live feed to operator or inspector of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UTM A-Scan • Camera • Location in 3D model 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Successfully tested as described in section 3.4 - Inspection Demonstration.		

6.1.3. *Pipe Inspection while ground monitoring*

Table 55. Pipes inspection and ground monitoring business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
PGM-KPI-B-01	Inspection Time; Reduce by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with traditional inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>HYBRID platform and IoT sensors have the potential to reduce the time taken to conduct inspection on pipework. This is particularly evident when dealing with pipe work at height on congested racks where inspection access or leak detection is challenged. The ground monitoring vehicles can also reduce inspection times, this is most evident in remote locations where a resident ground vehicle could be deployed to an inspection point much faster than a person having to travel to/from a facility.</p>		
PGM-KPI-B-02	Inspection costs: Reduce the inspection bill by at least 25% by using robotic inspection technologies	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>For pipework at Height – YES there would be a marked saving on inspection cost due to reduction in safety and at height equipment to access pipework. For ground monitoring vehicles, the cost saving is no a driving factor for deployment and likely would not be competitive version a human operator, however the safety benefits out weight this cost saving and still makes Ground monitoring a viable work stream for robotics in a refinery environment</p>		
PGM-KPI-B-03	Quality of inspection: Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>All of the robotic platforms from HYBRID, IoT sensors and Ground vehicles are proven capable of acquiring repeat and accurate data from pipework, vessels, large structures and other key ground inspection points.</p>		
PGM-KPI-B-04	Personal Safety: Reduce the number of hours of personnel working at height inspecting pipes.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Meets all safety criteria. The removal of personnel working at height is a huge improvement on current work practices for pipe and large structure inspection.</p>		

<p>PGM-KPI-B-05</p>	<p>Quality of data: Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of operational plant checks by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of operational data</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>The IoT sensors are capable of doing this, but in the case of the first experimentation runs we suffered failures of the gateway. Reliability needs to be improved to make this a viable solution for continuous ‘Operational’ data. No such issues encountered with ground vehicles or HYBRID pipe inspection platform. End users feel confident these data and reliability issues can be overcome and improved to fulfil the success criteria for this KPI.</p>		
<p>PGM-KPI-B-06</p>	<p>Personal Safety: Reduce the number of hours of personnel working in hazardous areas performing routine operations.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Meets all safety criteria. The removal of personnel working in dirty congested pipe racks is a huge improvement on current work practices for pipe inspection and the removal of people from dirty and congested spaces (Vessels) or the need to travel to a site for ground inspection purposes is an important use case for robotics.</p>		

Table 56. Pipes inspection and ground monitoring technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
<p>PGM - KPI-T-01</p>	<p>Hybrid vehicle integrates the following hardware systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gas detection system • Landing and attachment system. • Photographic camera. • Satellite robot for precise ultrasonic inspection. • Datalink for ground communications. 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>The HYBRID was tested as a fully integrated system including all the mentioned systems.</p>		
<p>PGM - KPI-T-02</p>	<p>Hybrid vehicle integrates the following software systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advanced Autonomous navigation and motion planning system. • Detect and Avoid system. • Autonomous landing system (including decision making on well clearance area). • Emergency procedures. 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>

<p>The HYBRID robot integrated all the mentioned software systems. However, and it was previously commented, it was decided that this iteration of the aerial robot was not permitted to fly due to safety concerns.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-03	The Hybrid vehicle is shipped to Oronite plant on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. It is depalletized in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The HYBRID system was transported to site using a truck, but stored in custom-designed pallet for safe transportation of equivalent size of a standard EUR-pallet. At site, it was hand carried from the storage area to the deployment location.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-04	The Satellite robot (of the Hybrid vehicle) performs ultrasonic measurements at least 1m far from the landing point and with telemetry valid to generate an inspection report.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Full remote inspection was performed using the integrated HYBRID system and cross-verified with manual measurements by a qualified NDT engineer.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-05	The Satellite robot (of the Hybrid vehicle) performs inspections as described in D3.1/ RP-DA-(45-47, 52-53).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>It has been demonstrated that the system is capable of performing inspections in line with the stated requirements.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-06	Repeatability of the measurements is possible between operations, with 2cm relative precision along and around the pipe (3, 6, 9 and 12 positions).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The satellite was shown to be capable of positioning itself on a predefined location with accuracy well below 2 cm.</p>		
PGM-KPI-T-07	Wall thickness measurements are taken from 3mm to nominal.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>A standard UT step gauge with step sizes from 2.5 to 20 mm was used to calibrate the complete system prior to the measurement of pipes with nominal wall thicknesses around 8.18 mm.</p>		

PGM-KPI-T-08	The Hybrid vehicle meets the safety, operational and best practices requirements and procedures of a standard refinery.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Aside from not being permitted to fly by refinery owner, the aerial robot was able to get the aviation authorities operational authorizations meeting all the safety and operational requirements by the European Drone Regulation.</p>		
PGM KPI-T-09	Robot control station HMIs give access to the pilot and inspector to the required systems during the operation.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>For the scope tested, the HYBRID satellite and UT inspection system was remote operated by a pilot and inspector using only the HMI and without direct line of sight to the robot.</p>		
PGM KPI-T-10	Images obtained by the Hybrid vehicle are used to automatically detect corrosion in the refinery infrastructure using PILOTING AI services.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<p>First iteration satellite only had a wireless video feed to a portable display without recording capability. No aerial images from the aerial robot could be obtained either in this iteration. Then, it was decided to use a different robot (AEROCAM) to get corrosion images for the PILOTING AI services.</p>		
PGM KPI-T-11	<p>Ground robot integrates the following hardware systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gas detection system ● Traction system that allows for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operation on a range of different surfaces (e.g. gravel, grating) - Climbing stairs <p>Datalink for ground communications. Robot manipulator with force sensor</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Due to changes in the robotic manipulator (already explained during the first review meeting), it was not possible to integrate all the components in a single ground robot. UGV integrates all the systems except the traction system, while RISING integrates all the systems but the robotic manipulator.</p>		
PGM KPI-T-12	The ground robot builds a 3D map representation of the plant area to inspect in teleoperation mode.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Both ground robots are able to compete a 3D representation using only on-board sensors.</p>		

<p>PGM - KPI-T-13</p>	<p>The ground robot autonomously navigates on prebuilt 3D map following predefined inspection paths and waypoints or returning to a predefined base checkpoint.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>UGV and RISING has followed the inspection plan in autonomous manner.</p>		
<p>PGM - KPI-T-14</p>	<p>The ground robot autonomously detects and avoids obstacles while continuing with the inspection plan.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Added obstacles no present in the prebuilt map were successfully avoided.</p>		
<p>PGM - KPI-T-15</p>	<p>The ground robot automatically detects and reads analogue gauges of 100mm diameter.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>This KPI will be validated during the second phase of the project.</p>		
<p>PGM - KPI-T-16</p>	<p>The ground robot automatically detects and localizes small hand wheel valves.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Detection was validated with several hand wheel valves located in the refinery.</p>		
<p>PGM - KPI-T-17</p>	<p>The ground robot’s manipulator can identify the state of small hand wheel valves (open/close) and change it according to a high-level operator’s command.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>The manipulation following the high-level command has been demonstrated. The state (open/close) detection will be validated during the second phase of the project.</p>		
<p>PGM - KPI-T-18</p>	<p>The ground robot logs visual and thermal images, and audio, with timestamp and associated pose with respect to the prebuilt 3D map.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Visual and thermal images and the metadata with poses and timestamp have been successfully recorded and compiled in the mission files. Camera streams and additional data can be retrieved from a log file.</p>		

PGM - KPI-T-19	Ground robot is able to charge autonomously.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Wireless charger station has been validated as well as the commands to start recharging.		
PGM - KPI-T-20	Ground robot is dustproof and waterproof.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Robot operation has been successfully tested under different conditions and also with light rain		
PGM - KPI-T-21	The ground robot can be transported and deployed by one person at any time.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Robot can be teleoperated into and out of the box in an easy way. The specifically designed transportation box can be moved (with its on wheels) and manipulated by one person.		

6.2. Viaduct Pilot

6.2.1. Visual Inspection (including surveying target installation)

Table 57. Visual inspection and survey target installation business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VVI-KPI-B-01	Reducing by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with tradition inspection procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Traditional inspections are carried out in an 8-hour day by two operators. During this first phase I, the following mean times were spent:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspection Times = 19 min • Setup Times = 20 min • AI Analysis Time = 20 min • FERR Inspection Times = 20 min <p>Total time between two pillars and a board = 12 hours (estimation) to inspect the Alora viaduct, compared to 8 hours for the current operators. However, it is also true that the quality of data obtained from a robotic vehicle is much higher than the one performed manually by inspectors.</p> <p>As an improvement expected, inspection procedures should be simplified, and the speed of operations should be increased for the second phase of validation.</p>		

VVI KPI-B- 02	- Reducing the inspection bill by at least 25% thanks of the use of robotics technologies.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<p>A 25% reduction requires optimisation of the inspection processes for the entire infrastructure. Until the time reduction (the target will be reached during phase II of the project) per operation, no significant cost improvement is expected. However, the frequency of inspections will be reduced, which will have a direct impact on time control.</p>		
VVI KPI-B- 03	- Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The amount of data collected has increased considerably, which implies a substantial improvement in the amount of information. During phase II work will be done on filtering and optimising the processed information.</p>		
VVI KPI-B- 04	- Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments or work at	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Yes, due to 100% reduction of manual tasks during inspection with drones. Also, the use of heavy machinery is reduced drastically.</p>		
VVI KPI-B- 05	- Visual inspection can be repeated (e.g. every month) in a consistent manner, allowing continuous monitoring.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>During Phase I, monthly replications have not been pursued. This will be addressed during the second phase of the project. However, adequate measurements have been achieved in a closed time interval.</p>		

Table 58. Visual inspection and survey target installation technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VVI- KPI-T- 01	<p>The UAV integrates the following hardware systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Image stabilization system (gimbal) for horizontal and vertical surfaces adaptable to different types of cameras. • Datalink for ground communications. • Localization sensors for GNSS denied environments. • Lighting system for precise pictures 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>AERO-CAM includes a gimbal that allows photography of horizontal and vertical surfaces, as well as adapting to different cameras. The UAV establishes communication with the ground and has location sensors such as LiDAR and IMU. The camera has the ability to install a flash, if necessary.</p>		
<p>VVI - KPI-T-02</p>	<p>The UAV integrates the following software systems:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Mission planner logger. • Camera pointer and stabilization system. • An obstacle avoidance system that ensures that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pilot is warned when the aerial robot is closer than 10m to an obstacle. • An alarm is activated once the UAV is closer than 2m. • The UAV automatically stops once it is closer than 1m to the obstacle. • Emergency procedures. 	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>AERO-CAM implements all the above software functionalities except active obstacle avoidance, which will be implemented in the second phase of the project. However, the UAV can detect obstacles and trigger alarms to the UAV operator.</p>		
<p>VVI - KPI-T-03</p>	<p>Image quality is high enough to detect defects during the first part of the mission, and high enough to be able to measure with accuracy of 0,1mm.</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Images obtained with the camera are of a resolution of 9504x6336 px. In addition, the configuration of the 85mm lens allows to measure with an accuracy of 0,1mm from the distance the UAV usually flights from the surface of the viaducts.</p>		
<p>VVI - KPI-T-04</p>	<p>The positioning system is accurate enough to localize the defects with an error of less than 20cm, ensuring that the UAV to return to those defects detected during the first mission.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Repeatability has been tested by capturing the same defect in different experiments, but the 20 cm pressure could not be tested. Improvements in flight accuracy are expected in the coming months to address this requirement.</p>		
<p>VVI - KPI-T-05</p>	<p>The UAV flies under windy conditions of, at least, 3 m/s</p>	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Yes, AERO-CAM flew in those wind conditions during the first pilots of the project.</p>		

VVI - KPI- T- 06	Robot control station HMIs give access to the pilot and inspector to the required systems during the operation.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The gRCS and mRCS allow full control of the inspection and display all the information necessary for the execution of the inspection. From the pictures taken and visual feedback of where the camera is pointing to numerical data such as battery, flight altitude, etc.</p>		
VVI - KPI- T- 07	The UAV meets the safety, operational and best practices requirements and procedures for a viaduct inspection.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>AERO-CAM meets the safety requirements from the aviation authorities to fly on the viaduct. In addition to the legal permits and coordination, all necessary safety precautions were taken.</p>		
VVI - KPI- T- 08	The aerial robot in charge of the survey target installation integrates the following systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Robotic manipulator to stick the survey targets to the viaduct pillars. • Mission planner logger. 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The VIAD-DRONE platform integrates all the above systems. Its hardware configuration for the survey target installation carries a pole with a retractile mechanism on the tip, which allows to place the targets with a touch and go manoeuvre. In addition, the aerial robot was able to autonomous navigate in the environment using the on-board sensors measurements and without requiring GNSS information. The state of the mission execution (the telemetry of the drone, time of the mission, the installation location, etc.) was monitored and logged from the ground by the gRCS.</p>		
VVI - KPI- T- 09	The aerial robot sticks the passive survey targets next to the points of interest, with a precision of at least 50 cm, which allows being included inside the precise picture.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Mean errors of the estimated VIAD-DRONE localization are less than 50 cm, which enabled both the accurate navigation of the robot in the environment and the target installations near to the defects to be inspected with less than 50 cm of precision.</p>		
VVI - KPI- T- 10	System shipped to the Viaduct location on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. Depalletizing in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

For operational reasons and due to the proximity of the viaduct to CATEC's facilities, the AERO-CAM was transported on a van without a EUR-pallet, but is designed to fit on one if necessary.

6.2.2. Bearing Inspection

Table 59. Bearing inspection business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VBI-KPI-B-01	Reducing by at least 5 times the inspection time in comparison with tradition inspection procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Traditional inspections are carried out in an 8-hour day by two operators. During this first phase I, the following measurements were carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspection Times = 19 min • Setup Times =20 min • AI Analysis Time = 20 min • FERR Inspection Times = 20 min <p>Total time between two pillars and a board= 12 hours (estimation) to inspect the Alora viaduct, compared to 8 hours for the current operators. However, it is also true that the quality of data obtained from a robotic vehicle is much higher than the one performed manually by inspectors.</p> <p>As an improvement expected, inspection procedures should be simplified, and the speed of operations should be increased from now on.</p>		
VBI-KPI-B-02	Reducing the inspection bill by at least 25% thanks of the use of robotics technologies.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<p>A 25% reduction requires optimisation of the inspection processes for the entire infrastructure. Until the time reduction (the target will be reached during phase II of the project) per operation, no significant cost improvement is expected. However, the frequency of inspections will be reduced, which will have a direct impact on time control.</p>		
VBI-KPI-B-03	Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The amount of data collected has increased considerably, which implies a substantial improvement in the amount of information. During phase II work will be done on filtering and optimising the processed information.</p>		

VVI-KPI-B-04	Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments or work at height	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Yes, due to 100% reduction of manual tasks during inspection with aerial robots. Also, the use of heavy machinery has been reduced drastically.		
VBI-KPI-B-05	Bearing inspection can be repeated (e.g.: every month) in a consistent manner, allowing continuous monitoring	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
During Phase I, monthly replications have not been pursued. This will be addressed during the second phase of the project. However, adequate measurements have been achieved in a closed time interval.		
VBI-KPI-B-06	Bearing inspection provide with enough accuracy to measure defects in a consistent and objective manner.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Partially during phase I, as of the two expected perspectives of the bearing we can only see the outer face. It is expected that we will be able to receive images of the inner side of the bearings in the second set of experiments.		
VBI-KPI-B-07	System is suitable for inspecting bearings in different typologies of bridges with different types of bearings (neoprene, POT...).	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
During this phase I only two viaducts with similar characteristics have been tested. However, for phase II a roadmap is being detailed to ensure compliance with this KPI.		

Table 60. Bearing inspection technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VBI-KPI-T-01	The aerial robot integrates the following systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Image stabilization system for the inspection camera. • Mission planner logger 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>The VIAD-DRONE system integrates all the above-mentioned systems. The robot was able to autonomously navigate in a GNSS-denied environment carrying an image stabilization device for the inspection camera. The execution of the different inspection plans (telemetry of the drone, inspection locations, gathered sensor measurements, time of the missions, etc.) was monitored and logged by the gRCS from the ground.</p>		
VBI-KPI-T-02	The aerial robot is able to perform visual inspection of the bearings from all their sides, i.e., the external and the internal sides.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The VIAD-DRONE captured stabilized images of the bearings from their frontal side. The internal and external sides of the bearings will be captured in the second stage of the project.</p>		
VBI-KPI-T-03	The aerial robot flies under windy conditions of, at least, 3 m/s.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The VIAD-DRONE flew under the above-mentioned wind conditions in the viaduct location. Anemometer sensors were used to validate it.</p>		
VBI-KPI-T-04	The robot control station displays live video from the images taken on-board the UAV.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Measurements gathered by the on-board sensors of the VIAD-DRONE platform (camera and LIDAR sensors) were visualized and monitored from the ground.</p>		
VBI-KPI-T-05	System shipped to the Viaduct location on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. Depalletizing in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Due to the proximity of the viaduct to facilities of the University of Seville, the VIAD-DRONE was safely transported on a van without a EUR-pallet to the viaduct location, but is designed to fit on one if required.</p>		

6.2.3. *Sensor Installation*

Table 61. Sensors installation business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VSI-KPI-B-01	Wireless monitoring of viaducts using sensors to be placed on top of pillars that currently are not installed due to accessibility restrictions.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
During phase I, it has been possible to simulate the route to deposit the box on the pillar, but it has not been possible to complete it. So far it has been possible to place the box on the ground.		
VSI-KPI-B-02	Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments or work at height.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
It has not been completed and therefore cannot be evaluated.		

Table 62. Sensors installation technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
VSI-KPI-T-01	The aerial robot integrates the following systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Sensor installation system that allows installing sensors of different shapes and sizes. • Mission planner logger 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The VIAD-DRONE system integrates all the above-mentioned systems. The robot was able to autonomously navigate in a GNSS-denied environment. The cargo system, responsible for carrying the sensor box and deploying it, is designed to work with standard and also taller sensor boxes. The execution of inspection plans (telemetry of the drone, inspection locations, gathered sensor measurements, time of the missions, etc.) was monitored and logged by the gRCS from the ground.		
VSI-KPI-T-02	The aerial robot is able to install a sensor box in reduced and difficult to access spaces and in a consistent manner.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
The VIAD-DRONE was able to perform a route to the installation location but it did not perform the sensor box installation between the pillar and the deck of the viaduct. Instead, this area was accurately measured and its real dimensions are compatible with the aerial robot design and the operation. Additionally, the system that perform the sensor box installation was tested on the ground.		

VSI-KPI-T-03	The aerial robot flies under windy conditions of, at least, 3 m/s.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The VIAD-DRONE flew under the above-mentioned wind conditions in the viaduct location. Anemometer sensors were used to validate it.		
VSI-KPI-T-04	The robot control station displays live video from the images taken on-board the UAV.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Measurements gathered by the on-board sensors of the VIAD-DRONE platform (camera and LIDAR sensors) were visualized and monitored from the ground.		
VSI-KPI-T-05	System shipped to the Viaduct location on a standard EUR-pallet by airfreight cargo. Depalletizing in a designated protected storage area and hand carrying to the deployment location on the asset.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
Due to the proximity of the viaduct to facilities of the University of Seville, the VIAD-DRONE was safely transported on a van without a EUR-pallet to the viaduct location, but is designed to fit on one if required.		

6.3. Tunnel Pilot

6.3.1. General Inspection

Table 63. Tunnel general inspection business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
TG-KPI-B-01	Reducing by at least 5 times the time required for detailed inspection of tunnel concrete intrados in comparison with tradition inspection procedures.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>The existing conventional way using EGNATIA’s inspection procedures prescribes a 3h (180 minutes) work for 200m inspection (at two different heights).</p> <p>The approach used in PILOTING indicated the following measured times:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15 sec for two consecutive images at the same height • 1 min and 25 sec for 3 images in different height with the robot at the same position • 11 min for 60 m (40 images) at the same height <p>Which concluded to the following benchmark and KPI achievement: 74 minutes for 200m (two different heights).</p> <p>Although this is an important reduction from the traditional procedures, we plan to improve the systems to increase this reduction even more.</p>		
TG-KPI-B-02	Reducing the inspection cost by at least 30% thanks of the use of robotics technologies. (Considering the whole tunnel maintenance life cycle)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Since the required inspection time is 41% of the total time when comparing the conventional means, we expect a similar reduction in costs.</p>		
TG-KPI-B-03	Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Using the automatic robotic inspection, subjective data interpretation is drastically removed as the approach used uses 100% digital systems. This is related to robotic system positioning, sensor systems positioning, automatic measurements and analysis of inspection data.</p> <p>Also, the robot can capture images always with the same angle of the camera while with conventional ways it is difficult having the same angle for each capture.</p> <p>Moreover, capturing images or laser scans every ‘X’ meters is more accurate with the robot rather than manual methods.</p>		
TG-KPI-B-04	Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>This KPI is verified indirectly as it is not possible to compare accident rates. Instead, we investigated work accidents as being reduced due to the following factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreased inspection time being ~40% of the time in comparison with traditional methods • Reduced personnel • Reduced road blocking and deviations required <p>Reduced exposure to traffic, truck or supporting vehicles.</p>		

TG-KPI-B-05	Reducing the time and the cost of after inspection reporting / representation of findings/ interpretation of findings by 10 times in comparison with conventional in house or outsourcing consultancy	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The after-inspection time and precision of results has been drastically improved following fully automated results aggregation, reporting and formatting. Particular user interfaces (IVP) have been designed to present results in a more user- friendly approaches, as indicated, specified and validated by different end-users. It is planned for the second pilot campaign to perform complete inspections and measure this reduction time.</p>		
TG-KPI-B-06	Increasing the completeness, accuracy, objectivity of the structural evaluation of tunnel, in comparison with conventional in house or outsourcing assessment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The after-inspection time and precision of results has been drastically improved following fully automated results aggregation, reporting and formatting. Particular user interfaces (IVP) have been designed to present results in a more user- friendly approaches, as indicated, specified and validated by different end-users. On top, the automation of specific, high-accuracy apparatus (3D laser scanner) fully integrated with autonomous robotic systems provides greatly increased completeness evaluation of tunnels under inspection.</p>		

Table 64. Tunnel general inspection technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
TG-KPI-T-01	The robotic ground vehicle will operate fully autonomously.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Different subsystems were tested successfully in a fully autonomous mode. Integration issues with the robot localization prevented the full system of operating fully autonomously for a complete mission.</p>		
TG-KPI-T-02	The robotic ground vehicle will inspect tunnel segments up to 1 km in length in a single mission.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Integration issues prevented the system of performing a complete mission. Subsystems were tested and data gathered for smaller segments up to 200meters</p>		

TG-KPI-T-03	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will measure its position within the tunnel with an accuracy of 10 cm from the tunnel entrance under the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No GNSS coverage • No fixed lighting or partial lighting 	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Localization payload had issues regarding the data/map matchmaking. Different segments of the ground truth map were known to be missing, thus leading to (knowingly) bad localization. Data sync and recording frequency were probable causes. Basic odometry with a worse accuracy was used as a substitute.</p>		
TG-KPI-T-04	<p>Within inspected tunnel segments, the robotic ground vehicle will measure the following values to within an accuracy of 10 cm:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tunnel diameter • Segment length • Width of the paved road surface • 3D location of defects 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The 3D laser scanner has been fully integrated on the robotic vehicle (CART) and provides inspections at the required points. The process is fully automated following the robotic mission execution and the laser scanner performs inspections with an accuracy of 1 millimetre (could be even higher in some cases). Also, thanks to the information from the CART vehicle it is possible to locate defect within 10 cm accuracy.</p>		
TG-KPI-T-05	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will capture inspection imagery of a sufficient quality to enable automatic detection of the following defects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cracks • Spalling • Corrosion stains • Exposed bars • Damp areas or water leakage areas • Calcium leaching areas (salt deposits in general) <p>Under the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No fixed lighting or partial lighting • In the presence of moving vehicles (headlights) 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>The captured images have a sufficient quality to enable automatic defect detection. Results from the AI systems show that, defects that datasets where available to train the systems, are able to be correctly identified and extracted from areas of interest. Even though, from the mentioned defects, corrosion stains and calcium leaching areas are not tested, as the developed AI systems do not try to identify these defects, due to the lack of annotated data for the systems to be trained on, the captures images have a sufficient quality to enable automatic detection when training data is available.</p>		
<p>TG-KPI-T-06</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will have the following capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ground clearance of at least 20 cm and suspension system enabling operation on rough surfaces (e.g. asphalt, gravel) • Tolerate up to 15 cm standing water • Tolerate up to 15 deg surface inclination • Max dimensions 3.5 m x 2.5 m x 2 m and max weight 2t to be transportable by truck • Max width 2.5 m to fit within a single road lane • Operational range of at least 10 km or 2 hr • Obstacle avoidance for trespassing vehicles, humans and objects max 20cm height from the ground. • Batteries rechargeable on-site 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>All of the robot capabilities were tested against rough conditions, specially in accessory drainage tunnel where those were present.</p>		
<p>TG-KPI-T-07</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will operate safely, have will have the following functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboard safety lights and relevant warning placards • Remote emergency shut down • Manual control override 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>All 3 functionalities were present. Manual override and emergency shut down were also consistently tested by driving the robot in manual mode and triggering the radio e-stop before moving.</p>		
<p>TG-KPI-T-8</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will have continuous wireless communications link with the ground control station such that inspection images and robot pose can be viewed live.</p>	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Wireless comm link was present at all times. Different issues were experienced with more than 3 simultaneous users at a time (due to the bandwidth). Only robot pose, status and developer screens could be connected in almost real time.</p>		

TG-KPI-T-9	The data capture by the robot allows measuring the actual deformed geometry of tunnel perimeter along the inspection path, with an accuracy of 1-2cm.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The 3D laser scanner has been fully integrated on the robotic vehicle (CART) and provides inspections at the required points. The process is fully automated following the robotic mission execution and the laser scanner performs inspections with an accuracy of 1 millimetre (could be even higher in some cases).</p>		

6.3.2. Local Inspection

Table 65. Tunnel local inspection business KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
TL-KPI-B-01	Reducing by at least 5 times the time required for detailed inspection of tunnel concrete intrados in comparison with tradition inspection procedures.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>TT-DRONE for capturing images at 8 points only required 2 min and 30 sec. In comparison with traditional methods this is a great improvement.</p>		
TL-KPI-B-02	Reducing the inspection cost by at least 30% thanks of the use of robotics technologies. (Considering the whole tunnel maintenance life cycle)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Since the required inspection time is 5 times faster when comparing the conventional means, we expect a similar reduction in costs.</p>		
TL-KPI-B-03	Reduce subjective data interpretation, increase quality of gathered data and improve quality of inspection by using 100% digital information system that facilitates comparison and analysis of inspection data.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Using the automatic robotic inspection, subjective data interpretation is drastically removed as the approach used uses 100% digital systems. This is related to robotic system positioning, sensor systems positioning, automatic measurements and analysis of inspection data. Also, the robot can capture images always with the same angle of the camera while with conventional ways it is difficult having the same angle for each capture.</p>		
TL-KPI-B-04	Reducing to zero the number of work accidents due to exposure to dangerous environments	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>This KPI is verified indirectly as it is not possible to compare accident rates. Instead, we investigated work accidents as being reduced due to the following factors:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decreased inspection time by 5 times • Reduced personnel • Reduced road blocking and deviations required <p>Reduced exposure to traffic, truck or supporting vehicles.</p>		
TL-KPI-B-05	Reducing the time and the cost of after inspection reporting / representation of findings/ interpretation of findings by 10 times in comparison with conventional in house or outsourcing consultancy	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The after-inspection time and precision of results has been drastically improved following fully automated results aggregation, reporting and formatting. Particular user interfaces (IVP) have been designed to present results in a more user- friendly approaches, as indicated, specified and validated by different end-users. It is planned for the second pilot campaign to perform complete inspections and measure this reduction time.</p>		
TL-KPI-B-06	Increasing the completeness, accuracy, objectivity of the structural evaluation of tunnel, in comparison with conventional in house or outsourcing assessment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The after-inspection time and precision of results has been drastically improved following fully automated results aggregation, reporting and formatting. Particular user interfaces (IVP) have been designed to present results in a more user- friendly approaches, as indicated, specified and validated by different end-users. On top, the automation of the methods to obtain high quality images (from the aerial and ground robots) provides greatly increased completeness evaluation of tunnels under inspection.</p>		

Table 66. Tunnel local inspection technical KPIs.

ID	KPI	Achieved
TL-KPI-T-01	The aerial robot integrates the following systems: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous navigation system for GNSS denied environment. • Image stabilization system for the inspection camera. • Mission planner logger 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>The TTDRONE platform was able to autonomously navigate using only the on-board sensors measurements in the drainage tunnel where GNSS measurements are not available. The visual local inspection results were gathered with a stabilized inspection camera installed at the top of the robot. The execution of inspection plans was monitored in real time and logged from the ground by the gRCS.</p>		

TL-KPI-T-02	The aerial robot is able to obtain adequate enough high-quality images at less than 2 meters distance.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The TTDRONE platform performed the visual local inspection at 1.3 and at 1.7 meters from the defects to be inspected.		
TL-KPI-T-03	The aerial robot is able to perform advanced inspection operations and revisit previously identified spots.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The repeatability of the visual local inspection performed by the aerial robot was tested and validated by performing the same inspection plans repeatedly (see Section 5.). The gathered results validate the performance of the developed system.		
TL-KPI-T-04	The system can record the position of tunnel defects (x, y, z) with 10 cm accuracy.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
A Leica Total Station was used as ground truth to obtain the error of the TTDRONE localization during the execution of the missions. The estimated localization was accurate enough for localizing the defects with 10 cm accuracy in the environment.		
TL-KPI-T-05	The aerial robot has enough flight time to perform the required inspections (at least 15 minutes).	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
The aerial robot was powered by LiPo batteries and performed visual inspection plans of about 12 minutes of flight. This time was enough to carry out quality local inspection missions. In the second stage of the project, the platform will be powered by the tethered system for performing missions of at least 15 minutes.		
TL-KPI-T-06	The ground robot control station displays live video from the images taken on-board the aerial robot.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No
The inspection camera is used to capture the interesting defects of the environment, but they were not shown in real-time as live video on the mRCS.		
TL-KPI-T-07	The robotic ground vehicle will operate fully autonomously.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No

<p>Different subsystems were tested successfully in a fully autonomous mode. Integration issues with the robot localization prevented the full system of operating fully autonomously for a complete mission.</p>		
<p>TL-KPI-T-08</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will measure its position within the tunnel with an accuracy of 10 cm from the tunnel entrance under the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No GNSS coverage • No fixed lighting or partial lighting 	<p><input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>Localization payload had issues regarding the data/map matchmaking. Different segments of the ground truth map were known to be missing, thus leading to (knowingly) bad localization. Data sync and recording frequency were probable causes. Basic odometry with a worse accuracy was used as a substitute.</p>		
<p>TL-KPI-T-09</p>	<p>Within inspected tunnel segments, the robotic ground vehicle will measure the following values to within an accuracy of 10 cm:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tunnel diameter • Segment length • Width of the paved road surface • 3D location of defects 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>With the use of the 3D laser scanner, any position inside the tunnel can be measured with an accuracy of 1mm. Also, the aerial and ground robots are able to locate the images within 10 cm accuracy.</p>		
<p>TL-KPI-T-10</p>	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will have the following capabilities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ground clearance of at least 20 cm and suspension system enabling operation on rough surfaces (e.g. asphalt, gravel) • Tolerate up to 15 cm standing water • Tolerate up to 15 deg surface inclination • Max dimensions 3.5 m x 2.5 m x 2 m and max weight 2t to be transportable by truck • Max width 2.5 m to fit within a single road lane • Operational range of at least 10 km or 2 hr • Obstacle avoidance for trespassing vehicles, humans and objects max 20cm height from the ground. • Batteries rechargeable on-site 	<p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No</p>
<p>All of the robot capabilities were tested against rough conditions, especially in accessory drainage tunnel where those were present.</p>		

TL-KPI-T-11	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will operate safely, have will have the following functions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Onboard safety lights and relevant warning placards • Remote emergency shut down • Manual control override 	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>All 3 functionalities were present. Manual override and emergency shut down were also consistently tested by driving the robot in manual mode and triggering the radio e-stop before moving.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-12	<p>The robotic ground vehicle will have continuous wireless communications link with the ground control station such that inspection images and robot pose can be viewed live.</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Wireless comm link was present at all times. Different issues were experienced with more than 3 simultaneous users at a time (due to the bandwidth). Only robot pose, status and developer screens could be connected in almost real time.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-13	<p>Measurement of tunnel diameter deformation in tunnel slices every 100m, with 1-2m per slice, accuracy 1-2mm.</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>With the use of the 3D laser scanner, any position inside the tunnel can be measured with an accuracy of 1mm.</p>		
TL-KPI-T-14	<p>Detailed photographing of the defect or highly deformed areas, by taking photos of high resolution</p>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No
<p>Images obtained with the camera are of a resolution of 9504x6336 px. In addition, the configuration of the specific lens allows to measure with great accuracy defect or highly deformed areas as shown in Section 5. .</p>		

In summary, and considering the three scenarios, 66%² of all KPIs have been already completely fulfilled, 24% partially fulfilled and 10% have not been fulfilled. With respect to the overall business and technical KPIs the fulfillment distribution is the following:

Table 67. Overall fulfillment percentage per type of KPI.

KPI/Fulfillment	Yes	Partially	No
Business	58%	25%	17%
Technical	75%	18%	7%

² To facilitate the readiness, no decimals have been used and the percentages have been rounded to the closest whole number.

As expected, the business KPIs (more related to complete inspection missions) present a lower fulfillment percentage in this first round of pilot experiments where the technological validation was an important part of the pilot experiments.

With respect to each scenario, the fulfillment percentage of validation KPIs is:

Table 68. Fulfillment percentage of validation KPIs per type of scenario.

Scenario/Fulfillment	Yes	Partially	No
Refinery	80%	15%	5%
Viaduct	50%	27%	23%
Tunnel	60%	34%	6%

As can be seen in Table 68, the refinery is the scenario that has achieved to validate the biggest percentage of KPIs. The Viaduct and Tunnel scenarios are behind, but still more than half of the KPIs have been validated during this first set of pilot experiments.

If we analyze the fulfillment percentage of each type of KPI per validation scenario (see deliverable D3.2), the following results are obtained:

Table 69. Fulfillment percentage of validation KPIs per type of validation scenario.

Validation scenario	Type of KPI/Fulfillment	Yes	Partially	No
Refinery Large Structure (Tank) Inspection	Business	75%	25%	0%
	Technical	75%	25%	0%
Refinery Pressure Vessel Inspection	Business	100%	0%	0%
	Technical	92%	0%	8%
Refinery Pipe Inspection with Ground Monitoring	Business	83%	17%	0%
	Technical	71%	19%	10%
Viaduct Visual Inspection (including survey target installation)	Business	40%	20%	40%
	Technical	80%	20%	0%
Viaduct Bearing Inspection	Business	29%	29%	42%
	Technical	80%	20%	0%
Viaduct Sensor Installation	Business	0%	0%	100%
	Technical	80%	0%	20%
General Tunnel Inspection	Business	50%	50%	0%
	Technical	55%	33%	12%
Local Tunnel Inspection	Business	67%	33%	0%
	Technical	64%	29%	7%

From these results, it is important to point out that:

- The viaduct's validation scenarios are the scenario where the business KPIs present the lowest percentage of fulfillment due to fact that the current inspection procedure is too slow (as already commented). While the refinery already fulfills at least 75% of all the business KPIs for the three validation scenarios.
- The validation scenarios with the lowest percentage of technical KPIs are:
 - Refinery Pipe Inspection with Ground Monitoring (71%)

- General Tunnel Inspection (55%)
- Local Tunnel Inspection (64%)

This is aligned with the requirements fulfillment percentage per use case (see Table 71 below).

- The pressure vessel validation scenario has almost a 100% of coverage of all the business and technical KPIs. This is consistent with the fact that it is the most mature validation scenario of PILOTING with a high TRL robotic solution.

Apart from the KPI, we have also checked the verification during the pilot experiments of the original project requirements (see deliverable D3.1). The traceability matrices where it is indicated if the requirements have or not been verified during the pilot experiments are included in Annex I: Requirements Validation.

After analyzing the results of the traceability matrices, it is important to point out that:

- Around 72% of the total requirements of the project have been verified during the first pilot experiments. Only 16% of the requirements have been partially verified and 12% not verified. If we do not consider the optional requirements (classified as COULD in deliverable D3.1), the numbers are:
 - 77% of the requirements have been verified.
 - 13% partially verified.
 - 10% not verified.
- The requirements coverage per scenario is the following (not considering requirements classified as COULD):

Table 70. Percentage of requirements verified during first pilot experiments per scenario.

Scenario/Verified	Yes	Partially	No
Refinery	79%	13%	8%
Viaduct	81%	9%	10%
Tunnel	65%	20%	15%

As can be seen, the tunnel scenario is the one that requires to improve most during this last year of the project. Actions are already taken place to improve the performance of the tunnel scenario during the second pilot experiments. Anyway, the overall fulfillment of requirements is very good, and we are confident that most of the requirements will be fulfilled during the second pilot experiments.

- Finally, the requirements coverage per use case is the following (not considering requirements classified as COULD):

Table 71. Percentage of requirements verified during first pilot experiments per use case.

Use case/Verified	Yes	Partially	No
Refinery Large Structure (Tank) Inspection	93%	2%	5%
Refinery Pipe Inspection	70%	25%	5%
Refinery Pressure Vessel Inspection	87%	3%	10%
Refinery Ground Monitoring	75%	11%	14%
Viaduct Visual Inspection	83%	10%	7%
Viaduct Bearing Inspection	79%	9%	12%
Viaduct Sensor Installation	77%	9%	14%
General Tunnel Inspection	62%	27%	11%
Local Tunnel Inspection	68%	13%	19%

As can be observed, most of the use cases present a important of requirements already verified in this first set of pilot experiments. The three use cases that have verified below 75% of their requirements are:

- Refinery Pipe Inspection
- General Tunnel Inspection
- Local Tunnel Inspection

The main reasons were:

- No possibility to verify the aerial robot in the refinery for the pipe inspection due to safety concerns.
- Integration problems of the localization system of the CART vehicle in the real tunnels.

Contingency plans are already in placed and running for these two issues. We expect that they will be solved for the second set of experiments, and therefore, the % of requirements for these use cases will be much higher in the second set of experiments. Moreover, improvements are already in all the robotic vehicles and PILOTING platform and services in order to improve the performance in the rest of the use cases.

7. Lessons Learned, Improvements and Best Practices

This section of the report will outline a series of lessons learned and recommendations for future improvements to the PILOTING project based on the first large-scale industrial testing.

Lessons and improvements will be incorporated into the development of the various planning, logistics, design and development of the second iteration for the PILOTING technologies to ensure the PILOTING project is able to meet all its KPI's and mandatory requirements for the final round of industrial testing in Q3/Q4 2023.

7.1. Refinery Pilot

7.1.1. End user observations

The refinery environment is a complex industrial location to test robotics. These petrochemical sites are typically high security/restricted access areas with a number of pre-authorizations and permitting required to enable work. Due to the restricted nature of the refinery environment, there was less flexibility in the format of the testing, with strict scheduling and supervision required at all times.

The following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- Communications should be improved between the Refinery staff and consortium (Chevron project leads) to ensure that all experiment locations are properly prepared and set up with external power outlets prior to arrival. The team lost some time during an otherwise busy week due to certain logistics not being handled as quick as expected. We are developing a better working relationship with refinery staff and ensuring to better involve them in project planning in future to ensure these lessons learned are mitigated in 2023.
- Permitting and flight authorizations to allow aerial experiments at the site were acquired very tight to the deadline for commencing work. In future the consortium will aim to start the permitting process earlier to build additional time into the permitting schedule to ensure deadlines are appropriately met.
- The dangerous nature of the refinery meant that all visitors were required to watch a safety induction video, do a multi-hour site walk and wear mandatory Person Protective Equipment (PPE) at all times while out on the site. We found that due to the large numbers and occasional late arrivals to the site, some of the mandatory safety rules were not being followed. We encountered multiple violations during the first half of the week. The recommendation is that Chevron personnel in charge must do a better job of educating all external visitors on the types of safety equipment they must have with them, why it is needed with earlier engagement on the topic prior to arrival at the refinery. In addition to this, daily toolbox talks prior to commencing any work must ensure a full attendance to ensure all stakeholders are aligned on safety principles and rules.

Also, the following best practices have been identified:

- Chevron aimed to have a ratio of 1:4 between Chevron personnel and external visitors (Consortium members). This worked very well in practice and allowed multiple experiments to be conducted in tandem with the appropriate levels of site supervision and is a recommended lesson learned for the final round of experiments.
- We also found logistically, that splitting the week such that half of the robotic developers were on site Monday – Wednesday and the second half from Wednesday to Friday worked well and allows Chevron to maintain a comfortable number of external visitors on the site each day and kept the project manageable.

- During the Refinery experiments, Chevron engaged a media company to accompany the consortium for the full week of testing. This removes a level of administration and logistics to ensure that all experimentation was captured on film for EC review purposes and to allow generation of promotional material to support WP10.

7.1.2. *Large structure Inspection*

The following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- As mentioned in section 3.2, the crawler design, coupled with a subtle lack of robustness in the UT measure computation, was ultimately the main source of both issues and delays during field operations. When regarding the crawler's design separately, it has been made clear that some physical parts need to be overhauled, that is, to avoid mechanical jams, as well as to provide with a more reliable perpendicularity (relative to the tested surface).
- It is important to note that additional quality of life improvements have been taken into consideration, such as the employment of a better suited interfacing fluid for the UT probe (less prone to exhaustion due to a lower density), and the re-configuration of the commanding RC signals for a softened actuation over the crawler (thus, dimming the chance the mechanical failure).
- When tackling the subject of the UT measure repeatability, it is appropriate to bear in mind that although the base logic behind the computation is not that complex by itself, the end-result can be easily twisted by the dynamic pose of the UT probe (relative to the surface's point of contact). In our case, even the relatively small tolerances in the 3D-printed mechanism proved to distort to great effect the incident angle of the probe between tests. However, this is not to say that the algorithm managing the measurement shouldn't be able to cope with this challenge, as far more complex environments are to be encountered in our application, and of course we aim to deal with them too. For instance, the commonly used gate-based strategy is effortlessly bypassed by surfaces of complex disposition and ample range of thickness. Therefore, there is a call for a smart algorithm that facilitates testing in this context. We expect that a shared effort regarding both the crawler and the UT logic will solve this topic.
- Although the position estimation issue may be the less concerning of those which arose during the field testing, it deserves a mention. The main problem resided in the eventual loss of position tracking by the total station, due to the AeroX itself obstructing the line of sight between the station and the on-board prism that reflects the laser. Apart from the later, an overall improvement (covering mostly precision and reliance) is in our view for the near future.

7.1.3. *Vessel Inspection*

The following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- BIKE lost surface contact with at least one wheel when transitioning from the vessel head section to the cylinder section. BIKE had to be retrieved manually. No damage was registered. This incident occurred in automatic control, after multiple manual operations on the vessel head. BIKE was located too far away of the planned path before enabling auto mode. Then, it is important to ensure (by process or by path follower) that BIKE was moved back to the last valid path pose after manual operations.
- Semi-manual operations, such as auto pan would be safer if a collision check was performed prior to the operation.

- Cable windup due to path planner / and due to manual activity is not taking into account. A rotation counter would be useful to minimize cable windup.
- Vessel head deviated from real shape, which reduced overall positioning accuracy. Impact was minor, but LIDAR scans might be used to update the model if the modeling tool supports it.
- Sometimes nozzles do not break through the surface due to bug in modeling tool. This will be addressed on the portal level.
- Cleaning was executed manually. It was difficult to ensure surface coverage. The raster scan motion pattern can be used instead.
- Brush cover prevents operator from seeing if the brush rotates. A clearly visible rotating disk on the side of the brush will mitigate this issue.
- Pointcloud of a small asset is very coarse on gRCS user interface. This should be improved before next pilot experiments.

Also, the following best practices have been identified:

- With respect to BIKE deployment, manway flange was protruding (had a lip) that BIKE could not cross it. This was not indicated on the drawing. Then, it is important, that for every new asset to be inspect, it will be requested information from site after asset is opened specifically asking whether the flange is protruding, and design a flange deployment tool for BIKE.
- Brush was used freely running, which resulted in force variations due to gravity. Fix distance would make cleaning performance more consistent

7.1.4. *Pipe Inspection*

The following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- The current system for localization and re-localization, based on the feedback provided by the onboard RealSense cameras, has been deemed unfitting for the task. Thus, a more reliable and robust LiDAR based SLAM will take its place.
- The insight supplied by Chevron's staff calls for a more secure motor switch off method during landing, consequently, this procedure will be reevaluated in search of a more suiting strategy.
- The anchorage system that holds onto the pipe body has not shown the expected results, therefore a thoughtful revision of this mechanism is in order.

Therefore, a major redesign of the system is expected during the last year of the project. This redesign has already started.

Also, the following best practices have been identified:

- The communications between the robotic system and the robot station has shown excellent results and did not cause any complications.

7.1.5. *Ground Monitoring*

With respect to the installation of the IoT accelerometer sensors along the green water piping located in Chevron's facilities, the following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- Some deviations appeared in some sensors, with the main causes to be the inclination of the sensors and the G-forces that are distributed over the three axial axes.
- Regarding the power autonomy of the IoT system, which was assisted by the deployed solar power system, it seems that a malfunctional issue occurred with the gateway after a month of

successful operation, and thus, our future steps include the further examination of the gateway and resolve any identify issue, in order to be reinstalled in the determined pipes and operate with success.

On the other hand, and during the deployment of the ground monitoring with the UGV, the following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- High torque manipulation is not physically possible with current manipulator. However, the system has shown high reliability as the full mission was repeated more than 5 times without failures nor interventions. The safety of the system was also validated with successful obstacle avoidance, and compliant manipulation where small errors in valve detection did not cause any damage.
- The focus of the second iteration cycle for the mobile manipulator is to close the action perception loop. Thus, two functionalities are required: i) the autonomous pressure gauge reading and ii) the valve position estimation. Then, we will be able to proceed to a closed-loop autonomous pipe pressure regulation.

Once the manipulation has been tested, the pilot in the refinery with the RISING robot focused into checking the maneuverability and the other enhancements. Then, the following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- Next iterations will focus in implementing metrics related to the missions. The thermal imaging was especially interesting as unexpected high temperatures (related to steam) were triggering the capture as opposed to checking specific Points of Interests. This patrolling approach where alarms can be triggered could be interesting to explore as well.
- Difficulties were found in order to test the expected climbing feature. While other type of test with different stairs was previously conducted in a non-relevant environment, the stairs in the refinery with a higher steep degree were found a too risky challenge, where the possibility of flipping over and damaging the robot and infrastructure was real. Next iterations will focus in revising the load balancing and climbing technique of the robot.

7.2. Viaduct Pilot

7.2.1. *End user observations*

The following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- Total inspection time should be improved during operations for the second pilot experiments. Currently setting up time is too high and should be improved. Also, inspection procedures should be simplified, and the speed of operations should be increased from now on.
- During the tests, we have had the opportunity to get to know in more detail the traditional inspection procedures. In these we have found the checklist used, where the number of items to be inspected is higher than the ones that PILOTING covers today. PILOTING system should be adapted to be able to perform complete inspections.
- The first pilots were carried out during the month of July in the south of Spain with very high temperatures. This considerably reduced the window of hours in which it was possible to fly, also producing strong winds from noon onwards due to the incidence of the sun. As a lesson learned, we must try to look for months with lower temperatures in which we can take more advantage of the day and fly more.

- Search for the most suitable infrastructure for each use case in order to test in different scenarios.

Also, the following best practices have been identified:

- Transfer know-how on current inspection and maintenance operations from end user perspective.
- Standardise the setup of photo shooting to be able to generate and compare a background of photos from now on.
- Define a flow chart for drone inspections (one per use case) in order to optimize inspection actions.

7.2.2. *Visual Inspection (including surveying target installation)*

The following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- The global localization algorithm in AERO-CAM did not always work correctly. There were start positions where convergence was not achieved, and manual intervention was required to take off from a location that was converging. Moreover, when the algorithm converged, it performed very well for relatively close positions, but the errors increased as the UAV moved away from the takeoff point. Therefore, it is necessary to work on an improvement of the algorithm and/or a change of strategy when locating globally with respect to the map. Perhaps an alternative would be to not only perform it before takeoff, but during the flight as well.
- The relative localization algorithm in AERO-CAM performed well during the pilots, but small errors were detected in the IMU data reception that may induce more inaccurate dynamics especially in the height Z-axis. Therefore, work should be done to improve this so that it does not occur.
- As highlighted by the end-user, the total inspection time is higher than in current operations, then the speed of inspection should be increased during the second pilot experiments.
- During these first pilots with AERO-CAM, inspections have been carried out in a very specific area of the viaduct. In addition, given the stage of development in which we are, the speed and agility parameters in general have been very passive in order to validate the technology correctly. To improve the inspections, during the second phase we will try to improve the system so that it can cover more viaduct in the same flight. For example, this can be achieved by increasing the flight speed and photo-taking strategy, in addition to the localization algorithm improvements.

Regarding the surveying target installation, the main lesson learnt and improvements are addressed below:

- The VIAD-DRONE robot pose estimation method was accurate enough for revisiting defects and to allow the autonomous navigation of the aerial robot in the GNSS-denied environment. However, considering the level of development of the localization methods still in the first phase of the project, take-off, landing and the manipulation tasks (the most risky stages of the surveying target installation missions) were performed in manual mode. An approach with incremental accuracy and difficulty was adopted since the localization accuracy for physical contact interaction must be higher than for open-space robot navigation. Therefore, it is necessary to work on improving the localization methods for the execution of complete missions autonomously (take-off, navigation, target installation, and landing). Also, the required perception system will be analyzed and new sensors will be installed on-board if needed.

- As mentioned above, the contact stage of the inspection plans was performed in manual mode. Aerial interaction control for autonomous target installation will be developed in the second stage of the project.
- As highlighted by the end-user, the total inspection time is higher than in current operations. The reason for this is that for the first pilots, the inspection plans and the control of the VIAD-DRONE were set up strongly enhancing care and safety. In the second stage of the project, it is necessary to work on reducing the time required to carry out the inspections.

7.2.3. *Bearing Inspection*

The main lesson learnt and improvements are addressed below:

- As it happened with the survey target use case, the VIAD-DRONE localization method was accurate enough for autonomous navigation in the GNSS-denied environment. However, take-off and landing were performed in manual mode, as well as the contact with the viaduct's deck and the navigation along it. An approach with incremental accuracy and difficulty was adopted since the localization accuracy for physical contact interaction must be higher than for open-space robot navigation. In the second phase of the project, it is required the autonomous execution of the complete missions (take-off, navigation, contact, navigation along the viaduct's deck, bearing capture, and landing). Therefore, it is necessary to work on improving the localization methods and also to analyze and improve the perception system if necessary.
- As mentioned above, the contact with the viaduct's deck and the navigation along it were performed in manual mode. Aerial interaction control to the autonomous execution of these two stages will be developed in the second stage of the project.
- The navigation of VIAD-DRONE along the viaduct's deck did not always work properly. Sometimes, some misalignment of the crawler tracks were caused due to the irregularities of the surface. Therefore, it is necessary to work on improving the design of the crawler tracks to make it robust against different surfaces and to achieve better robot maneuverability along the viaduct deck.
- Given the level of development of the first stage of the project, only the frontal side of the bearings were captured. It is expected that, on the one hand, the improvements in the crawler tracks design and in the aerial robot localization for the autonomous mission executions and, on the other hand, the development of aerial interaction control, allow to capture of the internal and external sides of the bearings in the second phase of the project.
- Some further improvements should be addressed based on feedback of end-users. In particular, the total inspection time should be reduced for the second phase of the project. The inspection plans were designed to validate the technology and not for the efficiency of the missions. On the other hand, from the point of view of the future exploitation, it would be a great improvement to establish a standard setup of the inspection camera parameters to monitor the evolution of the bearings over time and to obtain a precise assessment of them.

7.2.4. *Sensor Installation*

The main lesson learnt and improvements are addressed below:

- The estimated localization of the aerial robot was accurate enough for autonomous navigation in the environment. As for the two previous VIAD-DRONE related use cases, given the level of development of the localization methods and also the high risks of the sensor installation use case, take-off and landing of the robot was performed in manual mode as well as the contact with the viaduct's deck and the navigation along it. An approach with incremental

accuracy and difficulty was adopted since the localization accuracy for physical contact interaction must be higher than for open-space robot navigation. In the second phase of the project, it is required the autonomous execution of the complete missions (take-off, navigation, contact, navigation along the viaduct's deck, bearing capture, and landing). Therefore, it is necessary to work on improving the GNSS-denied localization methods and also to analyze and improve the perception system if necessary.

- As for the viaduct bearing inspection use case, aerial interaction control for the autonomous contact of the aerial robot with the viaduct's deck and the navigation along it should be developed. Moreover, and particularly for the viaduct sensor box installation use case, due to the narrow area between the pillars and the viaduct's deck, the aerial robot control should also estimate and consider the aerodynamic effects produced when the aerial robot is performing the installation (ceiling, corner and ground effects).
- The designed cargo system for the box transportation and installation was tested on the ground. Currently, this installation is performed turning on two lineal actuators that drops the box off at the specified installation point. Although this system worked properly, it will be improved to optimize the installation.
- Although the contact with the pillars and with the viaduct's deck performed in both the surveying target installation and in the viaduct bearing inspection use cases are challenging tasks, VIAD-DRONE navigation between the pillars and the deck is the most challenging and risk task of all the viaduct use cases. The environment for the sensor box installation must comply some requirement to enable the robot to perform the inspections: the pilot must have direct line of sight of the aerial robot while it is performing the installation and the installation point should be accessible by an operator to remove the installed sensor or recover the aerial platform if necessary. Alora viaduct did not comply these requirements so, for the second stage of the project, an appropriate environment should be found in order to perform the sensor box installation on the viaduct pillars.
- As highlighted by end-users, the total inspection time is higher than in current operations. The reason for this is that for the first pilots, the inspection plans and the control of the VIAD-DRONE were set up strongly enhancing care and safety. In the second stage of the project, it is necessary to work on reducing the time required to carry out the inspections.

Finally, and regarding the IoT sensors in the viaduct, the following lessons learned and improvements have been identified:

- Measurement of acceleration at key points of the bridge has been achieved, but further analysis is required to draw conclusions about the condition of the structure.
- Battery life is better than expected, which allows us to reduce tracking costs considerably.
- For the time being, the analysed data does not reflect the exact reality on the ground, because due to the inclination of the sensors the G-forces are distributed over the three axial axes.
- One of the main conclusions is the need to incorporate some algorithm that analyse the data and helps to draw conclusions (not only put G-forces for each axis and every hour, make a small automated assessment).

7.3. Tunnel Pilot

7.3.1. *End user observations*

The following lessons learned and improvements have been identified from the first field pilots on the two tunnels of Egnatia motorway.

DRAINAGE TUNNEL

7.3.1.1. *General inspection*

With respect to the ground vehicle, there was an important learning to obtain a successful inspection of a part of the drainage tunnel by the robotic vehicle. Also, the rough and with anomalies bed of the tunnel and its high longitudinal slope (>10%) with obstacles were mitigated by the robotic vehicle.

In terms of visual general inspection, or inspection by distance, where visual check as well as measuring of the location of the defected areas are carried out, it was estimated that it will be required more than 30 minutes and a 2 person team.

However, the readjustment of the sensors/ laser scanner/cameras in order to consider the high slope of the unpaved tunnel is of first priority in order to improve the accuracy and the efficiency of the vehicle general inspection. For the final trials robotic vehicle first mission should provide an accurate model of the tunnel as well as an accurate detection of defects of the first inspected tunnel segments.

The aerial inspection carried out by the aerial robot was successful and fast, enabling to cover in some 5 minutes two segments of the drainage tunnel, pre-selected by Egnatia Odos AE.

In terms of visual general inspection, or inspection by distance, where visual check as well as measuring of the location of the defected areas are carried out, more than 10 minutes and a 2 persons team are needed.

Finally, and as the drainage tunnel is not paved, the dust produced during the flight was an unfavourable factor for both the pilot to fly the drone as well as for the quality of the pictures/videos that were captured during flight. Some preparatory measures are therefore required, such as artificial lighting and wetting of the tunnel bottom surface in order to increase the efficiency of the first general mission of the aerial robot.

7.3.1.2. *Local detailed inspection*

Based on the manually selected areas from the findings of the first mission, the local inspection mission was performed fastly and successfully completed by the aerial robot. The basic conclusion is that aerial local inspection will be differentiated from the first general inspection in the sense that a more focused inspection of the selected areas with defects will be carried out

Regarding the robotic vehicle local/detailed inspection, the basic conclusion is that the latter will be carried out by the vehicle in selected areas with defects, by visual scanning of the defected areas by the cameras of the robotic vehicle stopped and by scanning the deformed geometry of the defected sections of the tunnel by FARO laser scanner.

MOTORWAY TUNNEL

The same conclusions are valid for the general and local inspection of the motorway tunnel. Here the UAV aerial mission is not possible with the one traffic lane of the tunnel open to traffic, therefore the robotic vehicle is the only option to use for the two types of missions/inspection of the motorway tunnel.

7.3.2. *General Inspection*

The main identified lesson learnts and improvements are the following:

- The navigation payload had suffered from several broken components, in particular a lidar, IMU sensor and two Raspberry Pis. This made the experiments very challenging. Spare components had been brought to the test, but since both the Raspberry Pis broke, it was not possible to get the synchronization between the sensor streams. The root cause for the broken components may be a short circuit in a lidar power supply. Regardless, a more robust hardware design is needed, where components are better protected. This HW upgrade has already started.
- We experience that SLAM solution on the CART underestimates travelled distance along the tunnel length with approx. 10%. A good map, containing visual markers, will allow the system to correct for this drift when in operation, but as the SLAM system also creates the map the root causes for this drift will need to be resolved. To reduce the drift, we will include wheel odometry in the navigation solution, extend use of non-unique visual features, and filter out data from passing traffic which disturbs state estimates and pollutes map.

This problem in the localization system did not allow to validate complete inspection missions. Then, in the second integration cycle, specific emphasis will be done to the validation localization system prior to the pilot experiments. For this reason, validation experiments are planned in a tunnel in Spain.

7.3.3. *Local Inspection*

The main lesson learnt and improvements are addressed below:

- Accurate aerial robot localization was estimated during the flights, allowing the autonomous navigation of the TTDRONE robot. Despite this accurate localization, the errors in the orientation and position estimations increased slightly when the drone was navigating in the inclined parts of the drainage tunnel. Therefore, in the second phase of the project it is necessary to improve the localization methods to avoid this. Moreover, the take-off and landing of the aerial robot was executed in manual mode for ensuring the safety of the robot and the tunnel infrastructure. In the final phase, the complete missions will be executed autonomously.
- Two different hardware setups were used in the first pilots: one setup for autonomous inspection executions and defect capture, and another hardware setup to carry out the tethering experiments. For the second stage of the project, it is necessary to work on merging these two hardware setups to build an integrated platform that performs the autonomous inspection missions tethered to the ground robot. The TTDRONE robot will be powered by the cable instead of LiPo batteries. In addition, autonomous cable torque control will also be developed in the second phase of the project.

7.4. PILOTING I&M platform and services

7.4.1. *I&M Platform – Inspection planning until the mission execution*

Following the validation scenarios that were defined and executed in all the pilot demonstration, we could declare that in general the majority of the corresponding partners followed the workflow that was designed and presented within the D7.2.

Starting with the pre-mission phase, and as indicated in Section 2. , it seems that the associated entities reveal meaningful entries and stored data for most of the missions and robotic vehicles. However, after performing a cross-reference between the designed validation scenarios and the created inspection plans, we noticed some small deviations, being the most important ones the following:

- The ETHZ-UGV robotic system has not been defined in the related robotic system entity in the DMS, and though, we have been informed that the data collected by this robotic system has been stored. After an examination, we identified those records to be included in the properties of a mission with UUID: 001a2fd7-84ce-4688-9864-945a964db20d, which is associated with the inspection plan with UUID: de06400d-323a-4ebb-9459-131cd140a23f.
- Additionally, we find the HYBRID entity to be related to inspection tasks with the creation date to be on 02/05/2022. Thus, we believe that the definition of this inspection task was under a training experiment, prior to the pilot demonstrations. More dedicated search must be done in order to identify where this data has been stored and with which mission are related. Furthermore, we identified the “Firewater pipe elbow” asset (UUID: ce041964-892f-4469-9f1e-a62653b3528f), which is not related to any inspection plan, and one additional asset, the “RV-VT-06” with UUID: a942fef4-4261-45dd-93e9-37ea12dae0db, which has been created in different dates from all the pilot experiments, and thus also in this case we shall assume that was created during the testing period.

Then it is considered beneficial to schedule a new demonstration workshop at the beginning of 2023 covering the DMS API and the workflow that should be followed by all the users during the inspection planning. Thus, we are confident to say that with the upcoming integration and constant communications with the consortium partners, during the next pilot demonstrations an adequate definition of the inspection planning and proper use of the DMS will be achieved by all the use cases.

Moving towards to the during-mission phase and the execution of the defined missions, it appears that all partners used the gRCS satisfactorily, without identifying serious errors that could prevent the completion of the inspections of the uploading of the collected data to the I&M PILOTING platform. This is due to the work done in the previous months, in which proper demonstrations of the software itself and the integration with the additional components were organized, and thus both the gRCS and the consortium partners reached an adequate maturity level before the first pilots. In accordance to this, CATEC carried out a round of consultation among the partners that developed the robotic platforms to obtain feedback on the performance in a real environment, after the finalization of the first pilot demonstrations. This consultation was not only aimed at locating possible bugs in the gRCS software, but also as an opportunity to improve those features. In fact, the participating partners have been very active in this round of consultation, contributing many ideas. For example:

- WTR suggested the possibility of visually improving the 3D environment, being able to hide or change element sizes for a better visualization of the elements. In addition, they suggested other improvements to speed up the deletion of waypoints when the inspector falsely was defined them. A possible bug was pointed out and requires further investigation, in which the gRCS displays a non-interfering but annoying process warning.
- Other partners, such as USE and ETH suggest the possibility of accepting negative numerical parameters in high-level actions, in addition to other small improvements that may facilitate the use of the software. In the coming months, it is planned the implementation of these small improvements suggested by the partners, as well as the generation of a new release and the publication of the source code on Github for use by the community.

Encouraging outcomes have been also declared from the interconnection of the corresponding components (DMS and RCS (gRCS and mRCS)) with the essential presence of the DDHL. In general, no issues emerged during the post-mission part of the experiments for the three pilot cases. The mission-specific data uploading to the DMS via the DDHL was implemented with success in the fully

integrated robotic systems with the DDHL. A single issue that has been arisen in the generation of the log files from the DDHL. In particular, the DDHL was designed to maintain the generated logs for a certain time. Taking as a fact that the first pilot in viaduct took place in July, it is clear that the DDHL ought to keep the logs for at least 6 months, a time duration that exceeded the pre-defined limit threshold. This way, the robotic partners re-uploaded several data sets to the DMS in order for the DDHL to generate new log entries. However, as the time span will be increased, the aforementioned problem will no longer occur.

7.4.2. I&M Services (AI, IVP)

7.4.2.1. AI for inspection data analytics in refinery pilot case

From the Chevron experiments, we obtained 1680 images in total from 6 different drone missions. Analyzing the images, we concluded that some images have overlapping regions between them and sometimes different missions pass from the same places. This is increasing the annotation time and not adding value for training the algorithms to detect the corrosion in the images, thus we have to remove images with great overlapping and similar areas.

In terms of recommendations, we would suggest to increase the time between the pictures in order to have less overlapping between them. Moreover, for better training of the models it would be beneficial if we could have the same spot taken from different angles. This is a manual augmentation that will help the model become more robust to predicting corrosion.

Finally, in terms of the integration of the different services we did not encounter any problems. The mission was received by the RabbitMQ and the AI service for the refinery run to predict corrosion in all the images and send the data to DDHL and DMS. Figure 164 depicts example data that are enriched with annotations from the MaskRCNN algorithm. The data are taken from the Refinery Pressure Vessel Inspection – BIKE Inspection Plan UUID b3a4ef7b-2d99-4608-83b7-63014909c0ad and Mission UUID e76e31b7-dd83-45f2-8e73-76f5befd2132.

```

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  "MimeType":"image/png",
  "Size":"2560848",
  "OriginalName":"capture_1_bike_back_camera.png",
  "Content":"mRCS - Image",
  "CreationDatetime":"2022-11-15T13:44:23.015072Z",
  "UpdatedDatetime":"2022-11-15T13:44:23.015139Z",
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            "tags":[
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              "maskRCNN",
              "corrosion"
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            "boundingBox":{
              "top":358,
              "left":515,
              "width":565,
              "height":574
            }
          }
        ],
        "algoType":"MaskRCNN"
      }
    ]
  }
}

```

Figure 164. DDHL - DMS data enriched with MaskRCNN annotations from the RabbitMQ service.

7.4.2.2. AI for inspection data analytics in viaduct pilot case

After the successful execution of the AI models, the following activities have been scheduled and are already in progress. To begin with, USE is working with CATEC to obtain as many images as possible from the experiments, as a larger data set is key to improve the performance of the detection and segmentation network. In addition, USE is working on data augmentation with GANs to generate more images with defects, as in our test field in "Alora", there were only a few notable defects.

In addition, Ferrovial is working with USE so that from their experience they can get a good annotation of the images for training. All this will help to achieve a noticeable improvement.

Apart from this, no further improvements or lessons learned have been identified.

7.4.2.3. AI for inspection data analytics in tunnel pilot case

Regarding the deployment of the designed AI models for the tunnel pilot cases, after the examination of the collected images from both the drainage and road tunnels, we came with the following conclusions and recommendations, which should be taken into account during the next pilot demonstrations.

In both tunnels no external lighting was used. In the case of the drainage tunnel, the area was illuminated by natural means from the entrance of it. Because the tunnel does not have any lighting system on its own, we think that a lighting system on the drone is needed to capture images from the darker areas of the tunnel.

In the case of the road tunnel, the area was illuminated from the lighting system of Egnatia. Due to the low illumination levels of the tunnel's lights and the inconsistencies of their placements, a high ISO was used to capture the inspection images. Because of the height ISO, a lot of noise was also captured to the images, which affected the identification of some cracks (widths 1-4 pixels) in the pilot area. We think that a lighting system can reduce the levels of the introduced noise and boost the performance of the identification for the defected areas with cracks.

7.4.2.4. *I&M Intelligence Visualization Platform*

From the first pilot trials, it was demonstrated that the generic pre-mission workflow implemented in the IVP caters most of the needs of all use cases defined in PILOTING. While some improvements are required to ensure the relational integrity of the pre-mission data stored in the DMS (see Sections 3.7, 4.5 and 5.4), it can be concluded that all the relevant partners were able to use the web portal, as intended, to create digital twins of assets and inspection plans.

This comes also with learning and constructive feedback from the partners with regards to features consideration and user experience for the second version of the IVP (Deliverable D6.8). These include some improvements on the point cloud visualization, a consistency check between the coordinates systems across use cases for visualising the image locations, the camera orientations, or the robot trajectories. An important learning point was to develop a strong alignment between the partners on the specifications of the (minimal) data structure exchanged and stored in the DMS, in order for the DDHL to correctly transmit the inspection planning information to the gRCS, but also for the later to upload the mission results.

Regarding the post-mission data visualization, the first data collected from the different robotic systems, the IoT sensors, and the AI service components has been received and analysed. These data from the pilot demos will enable an improved data-driven development towards the final version of the IVP. This applies to the visualization of UT measurements on different 3D models, the analysis of the time series data from the installed static sensors, the integration of the output of the AI model predictions for all use cases, and the assessment of the metrics from the valve perception and dexterous manipulation. Furthermore, we are engaging the PILOTING end-users to define and capture the scope of the final inspection report.

8. Conclusions

This is the first technical report for WP8 which summarizes the results of the first large-scale industrial experiments on the PILOTING project.

This report highlights the steps taken during the planning of industrial experiments using the PILOTING I&M platform and service, covers the testing and results from the Refinery, Viaduct and Tunnel environments, discusses the evaluation of the Business and Technical KPI's, looks at the validation of the technical requirements of the system involve and concludes with a series of lessons learned and improvements to be made for the return to industrial experimentation as part of WP8 in Q3/Q4 2023.

These first large-scale industrial experiments were recognized a success within the PILOTING project consortium with a large number of highly relevant technical and operational results. In total more than 6 weeks of experimental testing was executed in real operational scenarios considering the three PILOTING scenarios. All industrial testing was conducted safety, on-time and per the initial planning expectations/requirements, which is testament to the collaboration of all the partners, developers and end users that make up the consortium.

From the evaluation of the KPI's and the validation traceability of the original project requirements, the following conclusions can be obtained:

- An important number of the KPI's (66%) and project requirements (72%) were validated in operational scenarios (TRL 7) during this initial phase of experimentation.
- PILOTING already have validated very mature use cases, such as the Vessel Inspection with the BIKE robotic vehicle where 100% of the business KPIs, 92% of the technical KPIs, and 87% of the project requirements have been validated.
- However, there are still improvements and work to be completed during the second iteration phase of the project. Special focus should be paid to the following validation scenarios that are behind the rest:
 - Refinery Pipe Inspection with Ground Monitoring.
 - General Tunnel Inspection.
 - Local Tunnel Inspection.

Then, specific plans have been designed to follow closely the development related to them and ensure that all the technological blocks are ready before next year experiments.

- Moreover, it has been detected that the speed of inspection is a crucial factor for the future success of most of the viaduct use cases. Then, special focus will be paid to this aspect in the second development phase of the AEROCAM and VIAD-DRONE robotic vehicles.

Also, it is important to highlight that a large number of these experiments were performed fully integrated with the PILOTING I&M platform and services being able to validate a 100% digital workflow for inspection works (including mission planning, execution and analysis). However, there are still three robotic vehicles that need to improve this aspect, specifically HYBRID, CART and RISING. Special attention will be paid to validate the integration with the PILOTING I&M platform as part of WP7 activities during 2023.

Finally, a comprehensive series of lessons learned and recommended improvements have been captured from both the 'End users' and 'robotic/service developers' perspectives during the initial round of experiments in WP8, ranging from planning, logistics, team behaviours, experiment locations, technical readiness and specifications of the technologies being tested. The project aims to incorporate these lessons learned and improvements into the final phase of experiments to be held in Q3/Q4 2023. This will allow the PILOTING project to cover additional testing scenarios to ensure

validation of all KPI's and mandatory requirements that were not fully achieved during this first phase of industrial testing.

9. Annex I: Requirements Validation

This section discusses the validation of the **requirements** of the robotic vehicles for different inspection use cases in the industrial scenarios. More specifically, we provide a validation check for all the requirements introduced in piloting deliverable D3.1, where these requirements have been divided in categories regarding their nature:

- Non-autonomous functional requirements.
- Autonomous functional requirements.
- System requirements:
 - Physics non-functional requirements.
 - Certification non-functional requirements.
 - Safety non-functional requirements.
- Operational Requirements.
- Autonomous Functional Data Representation requirements.

These requirements were checked about their ‘verification’ status in deliverable D7.2, and here we add a ‘Validation’ column with the outcome from the live industrial tests.

9.1. Refinery Pilot

9.1.1. Tank Inspection

Table 72: Verification of the requirements for the Refinery large structures inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.2	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
RLS-FNA-01	Fun-NA	A gas detection system must be installed on-board the robotic vehicle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-03	Fun-NA	Perform single point ultrasonic measurement	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-FNA-04	Fun-NA	Perform grid-type ultrasonic measurements	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Perform scan-type of ultrasonic inspections	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only possible B-scan inspection type when integrated SDK of the new UT system.
RLS-FNA-06	Fun-NA	The system must be able to reload ultrasonic coupling onsite (if applicable)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-07	Fun-NA	Be able to perform basic surface preparation operations, such as mechanical cleaning of the surface, particularly on areas of rust scabs, paint coating break down.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Implemented in a previous version of the RMPC but not the last one due to weight limitation. Expected to overcome this issue with the next version of the platform.
RLS-FNA-08	Fun-NA	The system must perform an ultrasonic inspection for wall thickness from 3mm to 100mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FNA-09	Fun-NA	The system must perform an ultrasonic inspection for wall thickness from <2.5mm to 100mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-FNA-10	Fun-NA	The UT sensor must be calibrated using an ultrasonic step calibration block	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FA-01	Fun-A	If gas is detected, the system must communicate the alarm to all the involved people in less than 1s start a getaway operation as fast as possible.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to come back to a previous location where an ultrasonic measurement has been performed, and perform a measurement in the same place (10cm precision)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to come back to a previous location where an ultrasonic measurement has been performed, and perform a measurement in the same place (2,54cm/1inch precision)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FA-04	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot's path is in no case fully autonomous and it's instead commanded by the on-ground technician.
RLS-FA-05	Fun-A	While the aerial robot is in contact with the surface, the aerial platform must generate a perpendicular force to the surface in order to keep the RMCP in contact	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	The system must be small enough to be transported in a box of maximum 2.2x0.8x0.8 m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	The system should be small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Theoretically it is possible, but it has not been tested due to the protections needed for the robot to be packed in this way.
RLS-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Batteries are located in a safe location in the last version of the vehicle. Destructive impact has not been tested.
RLS-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Maximum weight of transporting box 30Kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW must be less than 25Kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-06	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW should be less than 20Kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-Sys-07	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW could be less than 15Kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement
RLS-Sys-08	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 10 min	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-09	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 13 min	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-10	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 16 min	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-11	Sys-Cer	Flight plan including emergency paths approved before the operation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-12	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-Sys-13	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved, taking into consideration the possibility of gas detected (explosion).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-14	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-15	Sys-Cer	Have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-16	Sys-Cer	API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 must be followed for fitness-for-service assessment techniques	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-17	Sys-Cer	For tank inspections, procedures in API 653 must be followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-18	Sys-Safety	Only brushless motors can be used	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-19	Sys-Safety	Gas detection alarm must be clearly communicated to the pilot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-20	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a clear and fast interface to start the emergency procedure after gas detection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-21	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Sys-22	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allow the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Op-01	O	Any maintenance must be done within a safe area	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Op-02	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RLS-Op-03	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Op-04	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-Op-05	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	It is not safe to fly in these conditions.
RLS-FADR-01	Fun-A	In single points measurements, it is necessary to log: identification number, and wall thickness value	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FADR-02	Fun-A	In grid measurements, the system must log: identification number of the area and for each point it must log: the position (relative to the grid) and the wall thickness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FADR-03	Fun-A	In scan-type inspections, the system could log: identification number of the area, minimum wall thickness, and an image (using standard colour coding) that contains position (relative to the grid) and thickness for each point	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	This data is more relevant for C-scans, not available for this robot.

RLS-FADR-04	Fun-A	The system must incorporate similar ultrasonic sensor user interface on the ground as regular ultrasonic sensor systems	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FADR-05	Fun-A	The system must be able to use a mission plan data embedded from the pre-mission plan	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RLS-FADR-06	Fun-A	The system must be able to save and display in real-time A-SCAN data on the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.1.2. *Vessel Inspection*

Table 73: Verification of the requirements for the Refinery vessel inspection.

Requirement ID	Req_Group	Description	Verified in D7.2	Validated	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
RV-FNA-01	Fun-NA	The system must be able to climb vertical surfaces	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Be able to perform wall thickness measurements	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FNA-03	Fun-NA	The system must be able to reload ultrasonic coupling onsite (if applicable)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FNA-04	Fun-NA	Robotic system should be able to perform basic surface preparation operations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Be able to repeat the measurements between large period of times, for example performing the same inspection path than in previous operations within localization systems accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FNA-06	Fun-NA	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FA-01	Fun-A	Robotic system must be able to perform single point thickness measurement	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FA-02	Fun-A	Robotic system could be able to perform grid-type thickness measurements	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to obtain live video of the inspection site	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-FA-04	Fun-A	Localization of the sensor in the 3D asset model / environment map must stay within 10 cm of accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FA-05	Fun-A	Localization of the sensor in the 3D asset model / environment map should stay within 6 cm of accuracy	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Accuracy depends on asset size and mainly model accuracy.
RV-FA-06	Fun-A	Localization of the sensor in the 3D asset model / environment map could stay within 3 cm of accuracy	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Accuracy depends on asset size and mainly model accuracy.
RV-FA-07	Fun-A	Be able to read-in a 3D model of the PV or provide tools to model a PV from 2D drawings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by van or pallet. Each case can be transported on a EUR Pallet (1200x800 mm).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo. Each case must not exceed dimensions 224x318 cm. Hazard sources (magnets, batteries, pressure bottles, etc) mitigated to qualify for air transport.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The system must be deployable through standard manways, such as flush with cylindrical part on the inside (no lip), of min inner diameter 400 mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Manway flange was out of scope in field test pressure vessel.
RV-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Maximum weight of transporting box 30 kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	Robotic system must be deployable by a human operator.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations, plan ahead, and take into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider system failure or getting stuck. Mitigations must be planned ahead.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-Sys-08	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must take into consideration the possibility of gas being detected (explosion).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-09	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider the possibility of loss of communication.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<p>The JSA (Job Site Analysis) covers this and is specific to the deployment situation and asset type.</p> <p>JSA will be updated in collaboration with the site operators.</p>
RV-Sys-10	Sys-Cer	API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 must be followed for fitness-for-service assessment techniques.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	First pilot experiments were not completed following these standards
RV-Sys-11	Sys-Cer	For vessels inspections, procedures in API 510 must be followed.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	First pilot experiments were not completed following these standards
RV-Sys-12	Sys-Safety	Gas detection alarm should be clearly communicated to the operator visually or acoustically.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-13	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a clear and fast interface to start the emergency procedure after gas detection.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-Sys-14	Sys-Safety	System should have a gas detector on-board and in case of gas detection the robot will automatically shut down	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-O-01	O	The system must operate on vessels made of ferromagnetic materials	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-O-02	O	The system must be able to operate with a non-magnetic layer of 0.2 mm thickness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The vessel in the field trial did not have any coating layer.
RV-O-03	O	The system must operate on surfaces clean of loose debris and rust	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-O-04	O	The system must operate on surfaces that are not covered with scale rust layers thicker than 0.2 mm	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-O-05	O	The system must operate on an atmosphere free of explosive gas concentrations	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-O-06	O	The system must operate in empty and no more than 2 cm of standing fluid	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-01	Fun-A	In single points measurements, it is necessary to log: identification number, position and wall thickness value	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-02	Fun-A	In grid measurements, it is necessary to log: identification number of the area, position of the area, and for each point the position (relative to the grid) and the wall thickness	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-03	Fun-A	Real-time view on thickness signals must allow for analysis and evaluation by certified inspector	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RV-FADR-05	Fun-A	Be able to save high quality (HD) images where demanded by the system operator	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-06	Fun-A	Show high resolution (HD) images during inspection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RV-FADR-07	Fun-A	Show robot and sensor position in 3D model of asset	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.1.3. Pipe Inspection

Table 74: Verification of the requirements for the Refinery pipes inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.2	Validated	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
RP-FNA-01	Fun-NA	A gas detection system must be installed on-board the robotic vehicle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Batteries transported and used to power satellite, UT instrument and communication during onsite test.
RP-FNA-03	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to determine if the landing area is clear of obstacles or not	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	No flight test performed.
RP-FNA-04	Fun-NA	The satellite installed on the aerial robot must be able to move along the pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-05	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to allow the pilot or automatically the system to assess the condition of the whole pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-06	Fun-NA	The system will incorporate the sensors to allow the pilot or automatically the system to locate the weld of the pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-07	Fun-NA	The system must perform an ultrasonic inspection for wall thickness from 3mm to 100mm	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Calibrated on step gauge 2.5 to 25 mm and tested on nominal pipe thickness of 8.25 mm.
RP-FNA-08	Fun-NA	The system must perform an ultrasonic inspection for wall thickness from <2.5mm to 100mm	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially	Calibrated on step gauge 2.5 to 25 mm and tested on nominal pipe thickness of 8.25 mm.

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-09	Fun-NA	The system could be able to measure height of corrosion deposit or depth (at least with 0.5 mm relative accuracy)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-10	Fun-NA	The system must be able to perform ultrasonic inspection at 3, 6, 9 and 12 positions in the first, middle and second welds in horizontal elbows	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-11	Fun-NA	The system must be able to perform ultrasonic inspection at 3, 6, 9 and 12 positions in the first, middle and second welds in vertical elbows	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-12	Fun-NA	The system must be able to perform ultrasonic grid inspections on elbows following Chevron inspection procedures	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial grid scan performed
RP-FNA-13	Fun-NA	The system should be able to perform ultrasonic grid inspections on horizontal T joints (in 1 and 3 areas)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial grid scan performed on T-Section. No test on reducer.

RP-FNA-14	Fun-NA	The system should be able to perform ultrasonic quadrant inspections on horizontal T joints (in 1 and 3 areas)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial grid scan performed on T-Section. No test on reducer.
RP-FNA-15	Fun-NA	The system could be able to perform ultrasonic grid inspections on reducers and horizontal T joints (in area 2)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial grid scan performed on T-Section. No test on reducer.
RP-FNA-16	Fun-NA	The system could be able to perform ultrasonic quadrant inspections on reducers and horizontal T joints (in area 2)	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial quadrant scan performed on T-Section. No test on reducer.
RP-FNA-17	Fun-NA	The system must be able to perform quadrant inspection of a horizontal pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only partial quadrant inspection performed on horizontal pipe.
RP-FNA-18	Fun-NA	The system must be able to inspect racks of pipes of 25cm distance between pipes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-19	Fun-NA	The robotic system should be able to perform A-scan type of inspection in straight pipes and in areas close to welds	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-20	Fun-NA	The system could be able to perform A-scan type of inspections in straight pipes with elbows	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-21	Fun-NA	The system must be able to reload ultrasonic coupling onsite (if applicable)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FNA-22	Fun-NA	The system must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-01	Fun-A	If gas is detected, the aerial robot must start a getaway operation in less than two seconds.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	No flight and associated tests performed
RP-FA-02	Fun-A	The system must incorporate sensors to allow the pilot or automatically the system to assess the condition of the pipe	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-03	Fun-A	The system must allow positioning relative to a feature (e.g. weld) with an accuracy of 2 cm at 3, 6, 9 and 12 positions.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-04	Fun-A	The system should locate itself, autonomously, with respect to the weld in 3, 6, 9 and 12 positions with less than 2cm of accuracy	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No autonomy for satellite planned.

RP-FA-05	Fun-A	The system must allow positioning relative to a feature (e.g. weld) with an accuracy of 1 cm at 3, 6, 9 and 12 positions.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-06	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-07	Fun-A	In single points measurements, the system must log: identification number, and wall thickness value	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-08	Fun-A	In grid measurements, the system must log: identification number of the area and for each point it must log: the position (relative to the grid) and the wall thickness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	UT data acquisition for point and line measurements tested. Robot functionality to capture continuous grid measurements not yet implemented.
RP-FA-09	Fun-A	In A-scan type inspections, the system could log: identification number of the area, minimum wall thickness, and an image (using standard colour coding) that contains position (relative to the grid) and thickness for each point	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	UT data acquisition with full A-Scan data tested for point and line measurements. Grid measurement data acquisition outstanding
RP-FA-10	Fun-A	Real-time HD video or high-quality images of the surroundings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Drone flight not tested. Satellite video feed without recording functionality.
RP-FA-11	Fun-A	Be able to save HD images under operator demand	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	Drone flight not tested. Satellite video feed without recording functionality.

			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-12	Fun-A	The system must incorporate similar ultrasonic sensor user interface on the ground as regular ultrasonic sensor systems	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-13	Fun-A	The system must be able to save and display in real-time A-SCAN data on the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-14	Fun-A	The system must allow the operator to control the ultrasonic sensor from the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FA-15	Fun-A	While in assisted mode, the aerial platform must detect any obstacle and avoid them	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	No onsite flight test performed.
RP-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	The system must be small enough to be transported in a box of maximum 1.2x1x0.5 m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System could be small enough to be transported by helicopter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The system must be small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Maximum weight of transporting box 30 kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW must be less than 15 kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-06	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW should be less than 12 kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No
RP-Sys-07	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW could be less than 8 kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No

RP-Sys-08	Sys-Cer	Flight plan including emergency paths must be approved before the operation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Flight permit and site risk assessment created. No onsite flight test performed.
RP-Sys-09	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-10	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-11	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of the drop of the robotic vehicle while flying	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-12	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of gas detected (explosion).	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-13	Sys-Cer	In ATEX areas it is needed to follow standard procedures	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-Sys-14	Sys-Cer	The system should be designed taking into consideration major restrictions to be able to extend its capabilities to operate in ATEX zone 1 areas in the future	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-15	Sys-Cer	The operator must have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-16	Sys-Cer	API 579-1/ASME FFS-1-2016 must be followed for fitness-for-service assessment techniques	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-17	Sys-Cer	For piping inspections, procedures in API 570 must be followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-18	Sys-Safety	Only brushless motors must be used	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-19	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-Sys-20	Sys-Safety	The flight envelope and clearance requirements around the aerial vehicle must be provided for flying and landing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-21	Sys-Safety	Gas detection alarm must be clearly communicated to the pilot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-Sys-22	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a clear and fast interface to start the emergency procedure after gas detection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-01	O	Recharging and maintenance must be done within a safe area	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-02	O	The combination of both robotic systems must be able to operate in pipes from 8 to 20 inches of diameter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-03	O	The combination of both robotic systems must be able to operate in 6 inches diameter pipes	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	No onsite flight test performed. Satellite only on 8 inches and above.
RP-O-04	O	The combination of both robotic systems must be able to operate in pipes from 20 to 24 inches of diameter	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-05	O	The Aerial Robot must be able to land by means of a magnetic landing platform	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	No onsite flight test performed.
RP-O-06	O	The system must operate only on non-insulated pipes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-07	O	The system magnets must operate on a surface with a non-magnetic layer of 1mm or less	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	No onsite flight test performed.
RP-O-08	O	The system magnetics should operate with a non-magnetic layer of 2mm or less	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Weight limitation for the first version of the robot does not allow this.

RP-O-09	O	The system magnetics could operate with a non-magnetic layer of 3mm or less	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Weight limitation for the first version of the robot does not allow this. This is a COULD requirement.
RP-O-10	O	The robotic system should be able to cross 5 mm high welds	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-11	O	The robotic system should be able to cross horizontal elbows of OD>12”	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-12	O	The system should be able to operate on surfaces at 60°C	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-O-13	O	The system could be able to operate on surfaces at 100°C	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The components do not guarantee a correct operation under these conditions. This is a COULD requirement
RP-O-14	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RP-O-15	O	The operator must be able to perform critical repairs and maintenance onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-01	Fun-A	In single points measurements, the system must log: identification number, and wall thickness value	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	mRCS data gathering for single point measurements tested. Upload through DDHL analogous to refinery vessel inspection. But only tested with BIKE robot.
RP-FADR-02	Fun-A	In grid measurements, the system must log: identification number of the area and for each point it must log: the position (relative to the grid) and the wall thickness	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Grid measurement data gathering and upload through DDHL analogous to refinery vessel inspection. But only tested with BIKE robot.
RP-FADR-03	Fun-A	In A-scan type inspections, the system could log: identification number of the area, minimum wall thickness, and an image (using standard colour coding) that contains position (relative to the grid) and thickness for each point	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	mRCS A-Scan data gathering tested. Upload through DDHL analogous to refinery vessel inspection. But only tested with BIKE robot.
RP-FADR-04	Fun-A	Real-time HD video or high-quality images of the surroundings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-05	Fun-A	Be able to save HD images under operator demand	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Standard quality images are only possible in this version.

RP-FADR-06	Fun-A	The system must incorporate similar ultrasonic sensor user interface on the ground as regular ultrasonic sensor systems	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-07	Fun-A	The system must be able to save and display in real-time A-SCAN data on the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RP-FADR-08	Fun-A	The system must allow the operator to control the ultrasonic sensor from the ground	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.1.4. Ground Monitoring

Table 75: Verification of the requirements for the refinery ground monitoring.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified (ETH)	Verified (ROB)	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
RGM-FNA-01	Fun-NA	A gas detection system must be installed on-board the robotic vehicle	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-FNA-02	Fun-NA	System must be able to overcome small obstacles/debris	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FNA-03	Fun-NA	The system should be able to operate small low torque types of valves	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FNA-04	Fun-NA	The system could be able to operate large high torque types of valves	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement
RGM-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Be able to teleoperate the robot from a remote location	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FNA-06	Fun-NA	Be able to place static sensor in specific places	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Capability to be developed in the second integration cycle
RGM-FNA-07	Fun-NA	Be able to create a 3D map of the environment	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-FNA-08	Fun-NA	The system should need no major preparation from deployment to work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FA-01	Fun-A	The system should be able to come back autonomously to the recharge station and recharge itself	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FA-02	Fun-A	The system should be able to operate using waypoint-type of navigation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FA-03	Fun-A	The system should be able to autonomously navigate in a refinery area	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-FA-04	Fun-A	The system should be able to detect obstacles and avoid them, while reaching the goal location	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Containment areas can be seen as obstacles as well
RGM-FA-05	Fun-A	Be able to automatically read gauges and determine if reading is correct	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Capability to be developed in the second integration cycle
RGM-FA-06	Fun-A	Be able to automatically estimate the position of a valve and determine if valve position is correct	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Capability to be fully verified during the second integration cycle.
RGM-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System size fits an europallet	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System weight below airfreight cargo max weight	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	System is weatherproof	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	System runs on electric power sources	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-05	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of gas detected (explosion).	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Gas detector onboard. Actions to be taken in case of alarm to be implemented

RGM-Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-08	Sys-Cer	The inspection program must follow API RP 580	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No expert knowledge on API RP581 to validate this
RGM-Sys-09	Sys-Cer	The procedures and methodology of Risk-Based Inspections must follow API RP 581	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No expert knowledge on API RP581 to validate this
RGM-Sys-10	Sys-Safety	Emergency stop button on robotic vehicle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-11	Sys-Safety	System power source can be immediately removed in case of emergency	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-Sys-12	Sys-Safety	Robot vehicle speed is limited while moving autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-O-01	O	Recharging need to be done within a safe area	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-O-02	O	Critical maintenance operations need to be performed onsite.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-O-03	O	The system should be able to climb stairs with 45° stair angle or less	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Test avoided due to visible risk of flipping over. Robot stability to be revised in such steep conditions
RGM-O-04	O	The system must be able to operate on grating floors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-O-05	O	The system must be able to operate on gravel areas	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FADR-01	Fun-A	HD video in real-time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FADR-02	Fun-A	Thermographic video in real-time	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FADR-03	Fun-A	Be able to log HD images under operator demand	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
RGM-FADR-04	Fun-A	Be able to log thermographic images under operator demand	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

RGM-FADR-06	Fun-A	Be able to log surround noises and transmit them to the system operator	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Audio is logged. Transmission to be implemented
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9.2. Viaduct Pilot

9.2.1. Visual Inspection (including surveying target installation)

Table 76: Verification of the requirements for the viaduct visual inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.2	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
VVI-FNA-01	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to take pictures of the whole viaduct with enough resolution to detect any defect	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FNA-02	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to take detailed pictures of the previously detected defects, marked with a radiometric target.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FNA-03	Fun-NA	Be able to acquire high-resolution visual images	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	

			<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FNA-04	Fun-NA	The imagen must have enough overlap between them, so that the defect is completely located	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FNA-07	Fun-NA	The UAV must not overfly people or properties without a previous warning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-01	Fun-A	Be able to localize images with cm precision with respect to infrastructure	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to detect obstacles closer than 10 meters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-04	Fun-A	Be able to detect obstacles closer than 15meters	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VVI-FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot is able to stop its movement and maintain the distance without moving when it detects that it is too close to an obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet
VVI-FA-06	Fun-A	The system must take pictures in a way that it minimizes the deformation of the surface	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-07	Fun-A	The system must be able to fly and localize itself underneath the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FA-08	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously. Always with the pilot supervision and controlling the compliance of the security requirements	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	The aerial platform must be small enough to be transported in a box of 65x85x80 cm plus a dedicated box for the vision system (camera + stabilizer)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot must have a diameter lower than 2m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 1m	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The main dimension is slightly larger than 1 meter
VVI-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 10 min	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-06	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 15 min	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	It depends on weather conditions and battery cycles.
VVI-Sys-07	Sys-Phy	The capacity of the power system (batteries) must allow the system to have an autonomy of 20 min	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not possible with the current robot. This is a COULD requirement.
VVI-Sys-08	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW must be less than 25Kg	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-09	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW should be less than 20Kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	If the parts are separated in different boxes.

VVI-Sys-10	Sys-Phy	Robotic system MTOW could be less than 15Kg	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	If the parts are separated in different boxes.
VVI-Sys-11	Sys-Cer	Have a detail plan for obtaining the permit to fly one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-12	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-13	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-14	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of the drop of the robotic vehicle while flying	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-15	Sys-Cer	The operation is under supervision of the health and safety committee and all the entities involved	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-16	Sys-Cer	The conditions of the data acquisition should be contained in a report (flight parameters, meteorological conditions, incidences, environmental conditions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially	Not all this information was uploaded into the DMS.

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-17	Sys-safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allow the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-18	Sys-safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-19	Sys-safety	The pilot interface must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-Sys-20	Sys-safety	The UAV allows that the data acquired are controlled by another external system, besides the pilot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-01	O	Be able to work at night with artificial lighting	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-02	O	Be able to work at night without artificial lighting	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	Flashing system could be integrated in the camera, but it is not available in this version.

			<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-03	O	Be able to operate the aerial robot without having a direct visual line of sight between the operator and the aerial robot.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-04	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-05	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-OP-06	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Safety distance to the structure should be bigger.
VVI-FADR-01	Fun-ADR	Be able to see live video with the images that the aerial robot is taking	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VVI-FADR-02	Fun-ADR	Be able to have a 3D representation of the viaduct and represent the area that have been covered by the pictures taken during the flight	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VVI-FADR-03	Fun-ADR	Be able to log HD images under operator demand	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
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Table 77: Verification of the requirements for the viaduct surveying targets installation.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.2	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
VST -FNA-01	Fun-NA	The passive device, e.g. a surveying target, should be used for geometric and survey monitoring of the viaduct using a total station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-02	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-03	Fun-NA	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -FNA-04	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to determine if the landing area is clear of obstacles or not	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-05	Fun-NA	The system must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-06	Fun-NA	The robot should be able to adapt to piles with variable geometry	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FNA-07	Fun-NA	The UAV must have the manipulation capabilities to install the device on the pillar, so that neither the survey targets nor the structure are damaged	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FA-01	Fun-A	Be able to stick passive survey targets on the pillar	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to come back to a previous location where a survey target was sticked, and stick a new survey target (10cm precision)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot is able to revisit some installation locations but the quantitative precision of the installations has not been measured yet.
VST -FA-04	Fun-A	The system must be able to fly and localize itself underneath the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet. The aerial robot navigates autonomously once it has taken-off. The landing is also performed in manual mode.

VST -FA-06	Fun-A	The aerial robot is able to stop its movement and maintain the distance without moving when it detects that it is too close to an obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet. When the aerial robot is being manually controlled, it stops its movement when it is close to an obstacle.
VST -Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported in a box of 65x85x80 cm plus a dedicated box for the vision system (camera + stabilizer)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 2m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-04	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 1m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -Sys-05	Sys-Cer	The operator must have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The Collision Avoidance System of the aerial robot has not been implemented yet.
VST -Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-08	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allowed the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-10	Sys-Safety	The pilot interface must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-11	Sys-Safety	The operation is under supervision by the health and safety committee and all the entities involved	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -Sys-12	Sys-Safety	The UAV must not overfly people or properties without a previous warning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VST -Sys-13	Sys-Safety	The conditions of the data acquisition should be contained in a report (flight parameters, meteorological conditions, incidences, environmental conditions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The experiment report contains flight parameters information but does not contain other required information such as the meteorological conditions, incidences and environmental conditions.
VST -O-01	O	Be able to work at night	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot localization and thus, the navigation in the environment, would be less accurate. Future work is to incorporate a lighting system to the UAV. It is a COULD requirement.
VST -O-02	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -O-03	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Safety distance to the structure should be bigger.
VST -O-04	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot was tested under these wind conditions, although the safety and reliability of the flight could be improved.

VST -O-05	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FADR-01	Fun-A	Be able to see live video from an on-board camera	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FADR-02	Fun-A	Be able to see live video of the exact point of contact	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FADR-03	Fun-A	Be able to see a 3D representation of the viaduct and a representation where the aerial robot is with respect to the 3D model of the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VST -FADR-04	Fun-A	The operator on ground must be able to monitor the state of the aerial robot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.2.2. *Bearing Inspection*

Table 78: Verification of the requirements for the viaduct bearing inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.2	Validated	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
VBI-FNA-01	Fun-NA	Camera with enough resolution to allow reading the metric system on the bearing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-03	Fun-NA	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-04	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to determine if the landing area is clear of obstacles or not	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VBI-FNA-05	Fun-NA	The system must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-06	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to take detailed pictures of the previously detected defects	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-07	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to flight near enough to the bearings	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FNA-08	Fun-NA	The imagen must have enough overlap between them, so that the defect is completely located	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FA-01	Fun-A	Be able to take pictures of the external sides of each bearing while flying.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Only frontal side of the bearings have been captured.
VBI-FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to take pictures of internal sides (those in the longitudinal axis of the viaduct) of each bearing	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Only frontal side of the bearings have been captured.

VBI-FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FA-04	Fun-A	The system must be able to fly and localize itself underneath the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet. The aerial robot navigates autonomously once it has taken-off. The landing is performed in manual mode.
VBI-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported in a box of 65x85x80 cm plus a dedicated box for the vision system (camera + stabilizer)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 2m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VBI-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 1m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-05	Sys-Cer	Have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The Collision Avoidance System of the aerial robot has not been implemented yet.
VBI-Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-08	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allow the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VBI-Sys-10	Sys-Safety	The pilot interface must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-11	Sys-Safety	The operation is under supervision by the health and safety committee and all the entities involved	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-12	Sys-Safety	The UAV must not overfly people or properties without a previous warning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-Sys-13	Sys-Safety	The conditions of the data acquisition should be contained in a report (flight parameters, meteorological conditions, incidences, environmental conditions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The experiment report contains flight parameters information but does not contain other required information such as the meteorological conditions, incidences and environmental conditions.
VBI-O-01	O	Be able to work at night	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot localization and thus, its navigation, would be less accurate. Flashing could be activated in the inspection camera. This is a COULD requirement.
VBI-O-02	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VBI-O-03	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	More distance from the bearings should be needed for the safety of the platform.
VBI-O-04	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot was tested under these wind conditions, although the safety and reliability of the flight could be improved.
VBI-O-05	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FADR-01	Fun-A	Be able to see live video from an on-board camera	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FADR-02	Fun-A	Be able to see live video of the exact point of contact	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The camera sensor points downwards, so the exact point of contact (at the viaduct's deck) is not perceived.
VBI-FADR-03	Fun-A	Be able to see a 3D representation of the viaduct and a representation where the aerial robot is with respect to the 3D model of the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VBI-FADR-04	Fun-A	Be able to visualize in real-time the data related to the total station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes	

			<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
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9.2.3. Sensor Installation

Table 79: Verification of the requirements for the viaduct sensors installation.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.2	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
VSI -FNA-01	Fun-NA	The box of sensors has to be dropped from the aerial robot at a sufficient distance to the pillar surface that avoids any damage to it	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-02	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-03	Fun-NA	Batteries must be protected against impacts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -FNA-04	Fun-NA	The system must incorporate sensors to determine if the landing area is clear of obstacles or not	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-05	Fun-NA	The system must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-06	Fun-NA	The UAV must have horizontal stability during the flight so that the box sensor doesn't break	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-07	Fun-NA	The UAV must have the manipulation capabilities to install the device on top of the pillar, so that neither the box sensor nor the structure are damaged	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-08	Fun-NA	The UAV must be able to carry the sensor box	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FNA-09	Fun-NA	The robot should be able to adapt to piles with variable geometry	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes	The actual design of the UAV is prepared for the shape of the pilot viaduct.

			<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Next step is to design a system capable to adapt to different shapes.
VSI -FNA-11	Fun-NA	The UAV must not disturb the box sensor once it is placed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FA-01	Fun-A	Be able to place and position a box with sensors at the top of the pillar (in the empty space next to the bearings)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The sensor box was installed on the ground instead of at the top of the pillars for the safety of the platform given the level of development of the first stage of the project.
VSI -FA-02	Fun-A	Be able to remove the sensor box installed at the top of the pillar	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The UAV has not capabilities to remove the box of sensors. This is a COULD requirement.
VSI -FA-03	Fun-A	Be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -FA-04	Fun-A	The system must be able to fly and localize itself underneath the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet. The aerial robot navigates autonomously once it has been taken off. The landing is also performed in manual mode.
VSI -FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot is able to stop its movement and maintain the distance without moving when it detects that it is too close to an obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet.
VSI -Sys-01	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported in a box of 65x85x80 cm plus a dedicated box for the vision system (camera + stabilizer)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-02	Sys-Phy	System small enough to be transported by airfreight cargo	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -Sys-03	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 2m	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-04	Sys-Phy	The aerial robot should have a diameter lower than 1m	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-05	Sys-Cer	The operator must have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The Collision Avoidance System of the aerial robot has not been implemented yet.
VSI -Sys-07	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -Sys-08	Sys-Safety	The system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allowed the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-10	Sys-Safety	The pilot interface must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-11	Sys-Safety	The operation is under supervision by the health and safety committee and all the entities involved	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

VSI -Sys-12	Sys-Safety	The UAV must not overfly people or properties without a previous warning	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -Sys-13	Sys-Safety	The conditions of the data acquisition should be contained in a report (flight parameters, meteorological conditions, incidences, environmental conditions)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The experiment report contains flight parameters information but does not contain other required information such as the meteorological conditions, incidences and environmental conditions.
VSI -O-01	O	Be able to work at night	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The robot localization and thus, its navigation, would less accurate. This is a COULD requirement.
VSI -O-02	O	The aerial robot must be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -O-03	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The operational area for the sensor box deployment should be greater for the safety of the platform.
VSI -O-04	O	The aerial robot should be able to fly under windy conditions	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The robot should be tested under these wind conditions. This is a COULD requirement.

VSI -O-05	O	The system must be able to change or recharge batteries onsite (in safe areas only)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FADR-01	Fun-A	Be able to see live video from an on-board camera	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FADR-02	Fun-A	Be able to see live video of the exact point of contact	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	The camera points downwards, so the exact point of contact (at the viaduct's deck) cannot be perceived.
VSI -FADR-03	Fun-A	Be able to see a 3D representation of the viaduct and a representation where the aerial robot is with respect to the 3D model of the viaduct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
VSI -FADR-04	Fun-A	The operator on ground must be able to monitor the state of the aerial robot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.3. Tunnel Pilot

9.3.1. General Inspection

Table 80: Verification of the requirements for the tunnel general inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.2	Validation	Explanation (If Partially or No)
TG-FNA-01	Fun-NA	The robotic vehicle shall be able to operate on rough surfaces (unpaved, small obstacles, debris, etc)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-02	Fun-NA	The robotic vehicle shall be able to operate in areas partially submerged by water.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Drainage tunnel partially submerged could be reached but some sensors were not protected against falling water preventing testing further.
TG-FNA-03	Fun-NA	The robotic vehicle shall be able to operate on inclined slopes.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-04	Fun-NA	Robot vehicle to keep speed within appropriate range	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Robot vehicle to steer precisely	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-06	Fun-NA	The system shall enable continuous wireless communication between the robotic vehicle and remote-control interface.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Bandwith restricts the data that can be streamed.
TG-FNA-07	Fun-NA	Represent the visual images obtained by the robotic vehicle in a user interface	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-08	Fun-NA	Robotic vehicle position tracking at control station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FNA-09	Fun-NA	The system shall be able to create a 3D map of the environment.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FA-01	Fun-A	The system shall be able to autonomously navigate to specified waypoints.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-FA-02	Fun-A	The system shall be able to operate autonomously in GNSS-denied environments.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Sync issues arised and tests were done with a non accurate localization.
TG-FA-03	Fun-A	The system shall be able to autonomously avoid collisions with obstacles.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FA-04	Fun-A	The system shall be able to autonomously capture inspection data with complete coverage of the desired inspection area.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Different issues in the capture triggering and localization prevented us to have full coverage in the desired area.
TG-FA-05	Fun-A	The system shall be able to automatically detect defects such as cracks, spalling, corrosion stains, exposed bars, damped areas and calcium.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Preliminary verification using offline images captured from the acquired data sets.
TG-FA-06	Fun-A	The system shall be able to automatically localise detected defects within the tunnel.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Localization is not as accurate as expected.
TG-FA-07	Fun-A	The system should need no major preparation from deployment to work	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-FA-08	Fun-A	The system should need no major preparation from deployment to work	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	This requirement will be covered in the second iteration cycle.
TG-FA-09	Fun-A	The system should need no major preparation from deployment to work	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement
TG-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	Robotic vehicle size and weight to be transported by truck	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	Robotic vehicle size to be used on a single lane	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	Robot vehicle size to fit small drainage tunnel	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Robot runs on electric power	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-Sys-05	Sys-Cer	A risk assessment must be carried out and a hazard mitigation plan must be developed in preparation for on-site testing.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	A previous visual inspection of robot and site was done by the pilot owners.
TG-Sys-06	Sys-Cer	The risk assessment and hazard mitigation plan must at least include hazards due to technology failures, environmental factors, and operator error.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Preparations done in order to mitigate failures.
TG-Sys-07	Sys-Cer	Field testing must be carried out in accordance with the risk assessment and hazard mitigation plan.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Pilot owner representatives always present for test compliance.
TG-Sys-08	Sys-Safety	The system shall be equipped with an emergency shutdown button for the robotic vehicle.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Appropriate safety lighting and signage shall be used to ensure safe operation of the autonomous system.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-Sys-10	Sys-Safety	When operating autonomously, the robotic platform shall have a movement speed in accordance with limits identified in risk assessment and hazard mitigation plan.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-O-01	O	Robotic vehicle able to recharge batteries onsite	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-O-02	O	Robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Due to integration issues with the localization system, it was not possible to verify this requirement during the first pilot experiments.
TG-O-03	O	Robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Due to integration issues with the localization system, it was not possible to verify this requirement during the first pilot experiments
TG-O-04	O	Robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement.
TG-O-05	O	Inspection able to be performed during night hours	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No test performed out of working hours. No limitations were identified in that sense.
TG-O-06	O	Inspection able to be performed with one lane open to traffic	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TG-FADR-01	Fun-A	The system shall be able to capture high quality inspection data of defects.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TG-FADR-02	Fun-NA	The system shall enable measurement of the tunnel diameter at requested locations.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Scanner data is able to provide the measurements. Full integration of the laser is pending.
TG-FADR-03	Fun-NA	The system shall enable measurement of the length of inspected tunnel segments.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Scanner data is able to provide the measurements. Full integration of the laser is pending.
TG-FADR-04	Fun-NA	The system shall enable measurement of the width of the paved road at requested locations.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Scanner data is able to provide the measurements. Full integration of the laser is pending.
TG-FADR-05	Fun-A	Measurement of tunnel diameter deformation in tunnel slices	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

9.3.2. *Local Inspection*

Table 81: Verification of the requirements for the tunnel local inspection.

Requirement ID	Req Group	Description	Verified in D7.2	Validation	Validation Explanation (If Partially or No)
TL-FNA-01	Fun-NA	The system must be able to inspect detailed defects of the whole tunnel length	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	To be checked during first pilot experiments.
TL-FNA-02	Fun-NA	Ground robot vehicle able to move on rough surfaces (asphalt, gravel, etc.)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-03	Fun-NA	Ground robot vehicle able to move on tunnels partially merged by water	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	To be checked during first pilot experiments.
TL-FNA-04	Fun-NA	Ground robotic vehicle able to move with inclination	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-05	Fun-NA	Ground robotic vehicle must be able to carry onboard safety lights and signs	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-06	Fun-NA	Aerial robot able to take high quality images at short distances of the defects	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-07	Fun-NA	Aerial robot must be able to go to a specific location where a defect has been previously detected, and perform a detailed measurement of the crack length, width and orientation.	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FNA-08	Fun-NA	Aerial robot able to mark specific points of the tunnel surface	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Aerial robot is still not equipped with a marking tool. Planned for the second version of the aerial robot.
TL-FNA-09	Fun-NA	Aerial robotic vehicle has to be contact proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Not implemented yet.
TL-FNA-10	Fun-NA	Batteries of the aerial robot must be protected against impacts	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TL-FNA-11	Fun-NA	The aerial robot must integrate the necessary sensors to detect any unexpected obstacle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FA-01	Fun-A	Ground robotic vehicle able to navigate in GNSS-denied environments	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Sync issues arised and tests were done with a non accurate localization.
TL-FA-02	Fun-A	Ground robotic vehicle wireless communication with control interface	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FA-03	Fun-A	Aerial robot able to navigate without GNSS	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FA-04	Fun-A	The aerial robot must take off and land autonomously	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	The aerial robot takes off and lands in manual mode. It will be performed in the second pilots.
TL-FA-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot must be able to operate under "autopilot" mode where a path, previously planned, is automatically followed	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

TL-Sys-01	Sys-Phy	The system size and weight must suite to be transported by truck	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-02	Sys-Phy	The system size must suite to be used on a single lane	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-03	Sys-Phy	Enough drone flying time for inspection	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-04	Sys-Phy	Enough drone flying time for inspection	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Currently, the drone is powered by a battery. The flying time is enough for inspections of about 12 min. In the second stage of the project, the aerial robot will be powered by the cable system to have longer time of flight.
TL-Sys-05	Sys-Phy	Enough drone flying time for inspection	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Currently, the drone is powered by a battery. In the second stage of the project the aerial robot will be powered by the cable system so the flying time will be longer. This is a COULD requirement.
TL-Sys-06	Sys-Phy	Have a detailed plan for obtaining the permit to flight one year in advance of the experiments	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially	

			<input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-07	Sys-Phy	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of collision with obstacles	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-08	Sys-Phy	The risk assessment must consider safety mitigations plan ahead and approved taking into consideration the possibility of loss of communication	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-09	Sys-Safety	Emergency shut down button on ground robotic vehicle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-10	Sys-Safety	Safe operation with the aerial robot	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-11	Sys-Safety	Safe operation with the aerial robot	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	Tests were only performed in a tunnel without traffic. This is a COULD requirement.

TL-Sys-12	Sys-Safety	The aerial robotic system must incorporate a pure manual control mode to allow the pilot to take the control of the aerial robot in any case, moment and situation	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-Sys-13	Sys-Safety	Aerial robotic vehicle must be collision-proof (for example mechanical protection around propellers)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	It will be implemented for the second stage of the project.
TL-Sys-14	Sys-Safety	The pilot interface of the aerial robot must show the needed information to have a simple, fast and clear situation awareness to decide on the safety of the operation at any time	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-O-01	O	Ground robotic vehicle able to recharge batteries onsite	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-O-02	O	Ground robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Due to integration issues with the localization system, it was not possible to verify this requirement during the first pilot experiments
TL-O-03	O	Ground robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	Due to integration issues with the localization system, it was not possible to verify this requirement during the first pilot experiments

TL-O-04	O	Ground robotic vehicle able to inspect large parts of highway network	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement.
TL-O-05	O	Inspection demonstration doable during the night	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	No test performed out of working hours. No limitations were identified in that sense.
TL-O-06	O	Inspection doable with one lane open to traffic	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	This is a COULD requirement.
TL-FADR-01	Fun-A	Recording the position of all defects inspected in detail by the drone	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FADR-02	Fun-A	Ground robotic vehicle and drone position tracking at control station	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FADR-03	Fun-A	Aerial robot be able to see live video from an on-board camera	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	No cameras are used for streaming video purposes. It is a COULD requirement.

TL-FADR-04	Fun-A	Aerial robot be able to log HD images under operator demand	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	
TL-FADR-05	Fun-A	The aerial robot system records and send in real time the sensor data collected	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Partially <input type="checkbox"/> No	

